

**ST CLEMENTS UNIVERSITY
CLINICAL PSYCHOLOGY**

**PSYCHOLOGICAL AND TRAUMATIC OF REJECTION IN OUR
LIFE'S INVESTIGATION OF EFFECTS**

DOCTORAL THESIS

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SUMMARY

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND TRAUMATIC OF REJECTION IN OUR LIFE'S INVESTIGATION OF EFFECTS

PhD Thesis, Social Sciences, Department of Clinical Psychology

Thesis Advisor: Prof. Dr. Bilal Semih Bozdemir

This study, which was carried out in the form of a literature review, was carried out with the objective of examining the psychological and traumatic effects of rejection in our day-to-day lives. The review was carried out in order to do this. The investigation's objective was to determine whether or not the two topics under discussion are connected to one another in any kind by analyzing their relationships to one another. It brings to a much higher level a range of aspects of our lives that are connected to specific interpersonal connections. In addition to this, there are a lot of difficulties that come along with it, the most major of which is opposition from the family. The findings of this study point to the potentially detrimental impacts that being rejected can have on a person. These effects include melancholy, feelings of worthlessness, fear of being judged, social withdrawal, quiet, and insecurity. It has come to light that there is a connection that disrupts interpersonal communication and relationships, which will ultimately result in persons having to adjust to the growth of their personalities and the difficulties they face psychologically. The fact that there is a relationship allowed for the completion of this investigation and finding. This was discovered through the utilization of a link that creates barriers to interpersonal communication and disrupts one's connections with other individuals. On the other hand, studies have shown that the rejection of an individual's emotions of worthlessness when they were a child has an effect on the emotional attachment traits that parents have, namely their sensitivity to being rejected. This is because the experience of feeling worthless as a child is carried over into adulthood. The findings are presented with the intention of serving as a foundation for further investigation, and the analysis of the data is carried out with the incorporation of findings from earlier studies.

Even if we are not consciously aware of the significance of rejection, it has a significant influence on many elements of our lives, including the construction of our personalities, our behavioral reactions, and our cognitive and emotional processes. This is the case even if we are not consciously aware of the relevance of rejection. This is the case regardless of whether or not we understand the gravity of being rejected. On the other hand, being rejected is an essential component that is involved in the social as well as the psychological adjustment that occurs as a

direct result of contacts with other people. This adjustment is something that takes place as a direct result of these encounters. Because of the way that these connections are structured, this modification must take place. A child's parent is the most common and significant cause of rejection, and research has shown that this personality trait has a tight link to attachment patterns and methods of parenting. The most common and significant source of rejection is a child's parent. On the other hand, it has been hypothesized that rejection sensitivity is linked to a variety of distinct psychopathologies and has the most substantial impact on a person's capacity to maintain healthy love relationships. This is based on the fact that it is the factor that has been shown to have the greatest influence. When viewed from this angle, the overriding objective is to make a contribution to and help define the direction of future research by focusing on the preservation of interpersonal relationships, marriages, psychological disorders, and even some mental diseases. This will be accomplished by focusing on the protection of interpersonal relationships, marriages, psychological disorders, and even some mental diseases. In order to achieve this goal, we will center our efforts on the protection of interpersonal relationships, marriages, psychological ailments, and even some mental diseases.

Keywords: *Exclusion, Self, Attachment, Acceptance-Rejection, Rejection, Rejection Sensitivity, Rejection Fear, Rejection Maladaptive Schema, Rejection*

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Abstract

This study, which was carried out in the form of a literature review, was carried out with the purpose of analyzing the consequences of the psychological and traumatic repercussions of rejection in our everyday lives. The purpose of the research was to establish whether or not the two things under consideration are related to one another in any way. It takes to some much higher level a variety of facets of our lives that connect to individual relationships. In addition to this, it is accompanied with a number of challenges, the most significant of which is opposition from the family. The results of this study show to the potentially negative effects that being rejected may have on a person, including feelings of worthlessness, fear about being judged, social retreat, silence, and insecurity, in addition to melancholy. It has been revealed that there is a relationship that disrupts interpersonal communication and relationships, which will lead to individuals

adapting to personality development and psychological challenges. This discovery was made possible by the fact that there is a connection. This was uncovered via the use of a connection that interferes with interpersonal communication and interactions with other people. On the other side, it has been shown that the experience of having one's feelings of worthlessness as a child rejected has an effect on the emotional attachment traits that parents possess, namely their sensitivity to being rejected. The findings are given with the purpose of guiding future research, and the analysis of the results is performed by taking into consideration previous research.

Even if we are not consciously aware of the importance of rejection, it nevertheless has a big influence on many aspects of our life, including the formation of our personalities, our behavioral reactions, and our cognitive and emotional processes. This is true even if we are not aware of the significance of rejection. On the other hand, rejection is a crucial factor that plays a part in both the social and psychological adjustment that takes place as a result of interpersonal interactions. This adjustment takes place because of the nature of these connections. The most prevalent and major source of rejection is a child's parent, and research has revealed that this personality characteristic has a close link to attachment styles and methods of parenting. On the other hand, it has been postulated that rejection sensitivity is connected to a number of different psychopathologies and has the most significant effect on a person's ability to maintain healthy love relationships. When seen from this perspective, the overarching goal is to make a contribution to and assist shape the path of future research by concentrating on the protection of interpersonal relationships, marriages, psychological disorders, and even some mental diseases. This will be accomplished by focusing on the safekeeping of interpersonal relationships, marriages, psychological illnesses, and even certain mental diseases.

Keywords: *Rejection, Rejection Sensitivity, Rejection Fear, Rejection Maladaptive Schema, Exclusion, Self, Attachment, Acceptance-Rejection*

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

According to Rohner (1986), the acceptance or rejection of the kid by the parents has a significant impact on the child's overall development, particularly on the social, emotional, and mental development of the child.

According to the Parental Acceptance Rejection Theory (Ekar), the acceptance-rejection scenarios experienced by parents may be broken down into the following four dimensions:

1. Warmth and love include all verbal and nonverbal acts that indicate care, affection, proximity to the kid, and support for the child.

2. Hostility-aggression: This is an expression of anger towards the kid, both vocal and non-verbal. Feelings of animosity and hate are often indicators of aggressive behavior.

3. Indifference and neglect: The child's many needs are not satisfied in a timely manner and/or to the child's satisfaction. Indifference on the part of parents is another common cause of child neglect.

4. Undifferentiated Rejection: This is the sense that the kid has of being rejected, despite the fact that the youngster does not actively engage in behaviors that are indicative of rejection (Rohner, 1986).

It is said that children who are rejected by their parents have seven fundamental traits in common, and those traits are as follows: These include rage that is shown in response to issues, aggressiveness; addiction; poor levels of self-efficacy and self-esteem; emotional unresponsiveness; emotional instability; and a pessimistic outlook. (Rohner and Khaleque, 2005; Khaleque and Rohner, 2002a). According to Rohner and Khalique's research (2005), it has been shown that children who are rejected by their parents throughout childhood may have more behavioral difficulties and are more likely to become sad in adolescence and adulthood than children who are accepted by their parents. According to research conducted by Rohner between 1975 and 1986, children's personalities suffer when they are rejected by their parents. In addition, research carried out in a variety of societies, linguistic communities, genders, and racial and ethnic

groups has shown that the positive and negative effects of parental approval and rejection are likely to remain the same (Khaleque & Rohner, 2002a; Rohner & Veneziano 1998).

In addition, certain significant new degrees of vulnerability might be introduced into our lives via the development of particular connections. These things come with a number of challenges, some of which are associated with being rejected by love relationships, friends, and family. An emotional state known as rejection is one that interferes with interpersonal communication and relationships. As a result, people are forced to adjust, which may result in conditions such as sadness, sensitivity, and social anxiety.

Problems such as criticism, individual worthlessness, social phobia (also known as social anxiety), social avoidance, sadness, stress, fragile, oppressive, violent, humiliation, unsuccessful, introverted, quiet, insecure, damaged self, psychological exclusion, and wrath are caused by rejection. causes.

The capacity to communicate verbally is one of the features that sets humans apart from other living beings because of their evolutionary history. This quality is a crucial aspect at the beginning of the process of sharing one's emotions and ideas with other people, thus it's vital to pay attention to it.

In this process of contact, parents, relatives, friends, romantic partnerships, and other types of interactions all play a role. It plays a significant role in the interaction process including feelings, ideas, and actions. Being accepted by other people is one of the most crucial components in establishing and maintaining healthy relationships. That is, the feeling of belonging, being sociable, having value, acquiring an identity, and having their needs met.

Rejection or acceptance may be seen as referring, in a way, to the adopted or unadopted condition of the connection that people are attempting to form at that same time.

In Turkey, an increasing number of studies on parental acceptance and rejection have been conducted during the last several years. However, when the research is analyzed, it is apparent that the studies done with preschool children are relatively few (Gulay, 2011; Toran, 2005). This is because there are very few preschool children in the studies.

1.1 Purpose of The Research

The purpose of this research is to provide a descriptive analysis of the contributions and impacts of rejection to the challenges that people go through in their lives. With the use of this descriptive research, the consequences of these difficulties on individuals will be studied owing to the problems that they have encountered from time to time until now. Additionally, the studies that have been conducted on this topic will be evaluated, and information will be provided about this topic.

1.2 Importance of Research

several research have been conducted on the topic, and several dangers associated with rejection have been identified. Rejection has major detrimental consequences on people's psychological well-being as well as their morality. This descriptive study is essential because it contributes to the body of knowledge on the question of whether or not rejection or psychological exclusion has an effect on individuals and how it might influence them.

In the framework of this research, the two significant variables of rejection and social anxiety, which are highly important in the context of interpersonal relations in human life, are also important in terms of gender, socio-economic level, and parental attitudes in people's lives. This is because rejection and social anxiety are very important in the context of interpersonal interactions in human life.

1.3 Method of The Research

This descriptive research is the presentation of the information that can be found in studies, papers, books, and publications relevant to the topic that were sourced from local and international databases. In descriptive research, the data is presented in a descriptive language, based on what people say, what they write, the contents of the documents, and the content of the relevant literature, while keeping loyal to the data's original form (Karada, 2010).

A preliminary literature research was conducted on the topic, and as a consequence of that review, the primary ideas associated with the topic were isolated, and compilations were created in line with the descriptive presentation of the data within the confines of this framework. In the

form of a review, the literature review summarizes existing research on the topic and establishes connections to explain a problem via the investigation and assessment of prior research (PEGEM, 2011). In addition, compilation studies have the goal of reaching and presenting the most recent information and advancements in a particular subject. These types of studies may be presented in the form of an appraisal of recent developments, an evaluation of the current situation, or a review, and they serve as a guide (Aslan and Holly 2007).

In addition, the literature in the fields of psychiatry and psychology, both domestic and foreign, was combed through in order to investigate the idea of rejection from a theoretical vantage point. In order to achieve this goal, electronic databases, such as PubMed and Google Scholar, as well as electronic books and PsycINFO, were analyzed and scanned. Several alternative keyword combinations, including "Rejection Sensitivity," "Psychiatry," "Theories," and "Rejection," were used in the search. Both the examined papers and the sources of the articles were put through a series of evaluations, with the results of those evaluations being taken into account for this research.

1.4. Abbreviations

BN: Bulimia Nervosa

EKR: Parental Acceptance-Rejection

VB: And Similar

VS: Etc.

RD: Rejection Sensitivity

BPD: Social Anxiety Disorder

OCD: Obsessive Compulsive Disorder

YB: Eating Disorders

CHAPTER 2

FRAMEWORK OF THE RESEARCH

2.1 Definition of Rejection

There have been a lot of different interpretations of what "rejection" means over the course of human history. Some of the following examples are those:

Rejection may be defined as the experience of not being accepted by important persons in interpersonal relationships (such as parents, close friends, classmates, love partners, and so on). (Creasey-McLinnis, 2001, page 86).

Rejection is a scenario in which the individual is made to feel less valued in interpersonal social connections as a result of not being accepted by important others and social groups (parents, close friends, classmates, romantic partners, and other significant others) that are significant for the individual (Marston et al. 2010). Rejection is a circumstance that leads the individual to feel less valuable in interpersonal social relations.

In Turkish, "Rejection" literally translates to "Rejection."

Rejection; to be rejected, to be rejected, to refuse, not being accepted from the family, disregarding the kinship links, and being expelled from the family (Kubbealt Academy).

In the context of interpersonal relationships, rejection refers to the experience of not being accepted by important people, which may result in an individual feeling as if they have no value. Creasey and McLinnis, in their book from 2001, page 87.

It is difficult for people to adjust because rejection is a condition that causes emotions of rejection and despair, rejection sensitivity, and social anxiety. Rejection is a disorder that destroys interpersonal connections.

The attachment theory developed by Bowlby (1969, 1973, and 1980) is a significant paradigm that demonstrates there is a connection between the functioning of interpersonal relationships and rejection. Bowlby hypothesized that children build their own mental models and formations, which would later have an effect on the connections they had in adulthood. Bowlby contends that children are more prone to experience rejection in situations in which their parents respond to the needs they have stated by rejecting them.

According to Downey, Lebolt, and O'shea (1995), rejection sensitivity is a process that involves anxious rejection expectations that disturbs interpersonal connections by producing

issues in intimate adolescent/adult relationships with their parents, instructors, friends, and romantic partners. Rejection sensitivity also includes anxious expectations of being rejected.

We may say that rejection or psychological exclusion is a concept that explains the "ignoring, rejection, or exclusion" of people by leaving them out of the group by other individuals or groups (Williams, 2007). We can say that rejection or psychological exclusion is a concept that explains the "ignoring, rejection, or exclusion" of individuals by leaving them out of the group. According to Gerber and Wheeler (2009), psychological isolation may function as a kind of rejection in relationships.

According to J. Gerric's research from 2003, persons who are shy anticipate being rejected and failing socially, and they judge their social connections adversely. This contributes to emotions of inadequacy and vulnerability. G. Zimbardo's research from 2012).

It has been found through a number of studies that the concept of rejection sensitivity originates from childhood rejection, and this sensitivity continues into adolescence and adulthood. The relationship between rejection sensitivity and exposure to rejection by parents in childhood has been examined to determine whether or not there is a correlation between the two.

In other words, emotional and behavioral overreactions may be caused by rejection, wrath, hostility, anxiety, despair, phobia, anxiety, self-mutilation, loneliness, violence, yelling, cursing, imposition, hostile attitudes, hopelessness, and jealousy. However, as a consequence, they are unable to maintain healthy social and interpersonal interactions as a result of this.

Additionally, there is a correlation between being rejected and acting aggressively, according to the findings of a number of earlier research (Leary, Twenge, & Quinlivan, 2006). These investigations range from experimental to longitudinal to relational in nature. According to Leary, Twenge, and Quinlivan (2006), aggressiveness may take the form of either physical or verbal behavior and can be shown in a variety of ways, including those that are psychological, social, or financial. These behaviors are carried out with the intention of causing harm to another individual. To put it another way, one might say that those who feel hurt when they are rejected have a tendency to harm the person who rejected them in return. An example of this would be research that used the Hot Sauce Paradigm and looked at the amount of violent behavior shown by participants after they had been rejected by a possible partner on an online social interaction platform. When participants in the rejection condition were asked to share a portion of hot sauce with their potential partners, it was observed that they added more hot sauce to their partners compared to those participants in the non-rejection control condition (Ayduk, Gyurak, & Luerssen,

2008). This was the case despite the fact that they were aware that their potential partners did not like hot sauce.

In research carried out in a variety of nations, children who were rejected by their parents. Anxiety (Hill & Bush, 2001), Depression (Crockenberg & Leerkes, 2003), Delinquency (Simons, Robertson & Downs, 1988), Negative Self-Esteem (Kitahara, 1987), Social Relationship Problems (Paley, Conger, & Downes, 1988), and Depressed Mood (Crockenberg & Leerkes, 2003) are some of the conditions that have been linked to depression. Harold, year 2000). Another international research indicated that those who experience feelings of rejection are more likely to engage in violent behavior, to have lower levels of self-esteem and self-efficacy, and to be more emotionally vulnerable. According to Rohner (1986), it was discovered that he created a worldview that was unresponsive, inconsistent, and negative.

As a consequence of this, the idea of being rejected may be seen of as a social experience that individuals have (Gerber & Wheeler, 2009), and one might anticipate that having this experience will have a variety of effects on people.

2.1.1 Rejection Sensitivity (Rejection Sensitivity) and Mental Health

According to Creasey and McInnis (2001), he described the idea of rejection as a circumstance in which emotions of worthlessness originate as a consequence of unseen acceptance from persons who are given significance in interpersonal relationships. He said that these sentiments might come from unseen acceptance from people who are given importance in interpersonal relationships.

According to AYDUK et al. (2000), p.776, rejection sensitivity is a process that is shaped by negative experiences that occur during childhood. This process also includes anxious rejection expectations, and it disrupts interpersonal relationships by creating difficulties in close relationships that adolescents and adults have with their parents, teachers, friends, and romantic partners.

Rejection sensitivity is a phenomenon that can be explained as a cognitive-emotional information processing tendency that causes a person to expect and easily perceive rejection clues in the behavior of others, as well as to react intensely to rejection (De Rubeis et al., 2017; Sommerfeld & Shechory Bitton, 2020). Rejection sensitivity causes a person to expect and easily perceive rejection clues in the behavior of others, as well as to react intensely to rejection.

According to Feinstein and 2020's research, rejection sensitivity is connected to the manner in which an individual experiences and interprets stress.

Another description of rejection anxiety is the propensity to detect rejection readily and to respond to it (Kross, Egner, Ochsner, Hirsch, & Downey, 2007; Downey & Feldman, 1996). Rejection anxiety may also be described as nervous waiting for rejection.

The unpleasant expectation of being rejected is the single most crucial component of rejection sensitivity. Low rejection sensitivity may be characterized as expecting to be accepted and not experiencing a great deal of worry about the chance that one would be rejected (Downey and Feldman 1996). High rejection sensitivity is described as both expecting to be rejected and having a high level of fear that it will occur.

According to Baumeister and Leary (1995) and Maslow (1954), one of the most fundamental and important sources of motivation and energy in the organism is the drive to be accepted by the society. According to Butler, Doherty, and Potter (2007), the primary objective of the organism throughout its lifetime has been to become a member of the community in which it resides.

In a way, it satisfies a broad range of need that other people have, such as love, acceptance, a feeling of belonging, the capacity to share, an increase in the strength to bear difficult circumstances, the capacity to increase pleasure via the act of sharing, and the acquisition of an identity. To put it another way, it is essential for him to acknowledge his status as a social entity. According to Sapmaz (2006:43), the most fundamental need for a person to not be separated from society and to be able to survive within a community is to engage with other people. As a consequence of this, the human experience of not being able to create healthy connections or of not being rejected by them will be one that may be avoided and is even one that can be unpleasant. Rejection from other people will not only be unpleasant, but it will also diminish one's capacity to deal with earlier instances of rejection as well as future social encounters. The idea of rejection is somewhat wide, but for the sake of this discussion, we will focus on the rejection of the person within the context of social connections. According to Harb, Heimberg, Fresco, Schneider, and Leibowitz (2002), the concept of rejection sensitivity is only applicable to instances of interpersonal rejection. This circumstance, which may be interpreted as disapproval or rejection in the context of human interactions.

According to what they found, those who are very sensitive to rejection anticipate that others will reject them, and they see ambiguous interpersonal signals as signs of rejection.

(Downey & Feldman, 1996; Downey & Feldman, 2007; Downey & Feldman, 1996). According to them, those who have a high rejection sensitivity also have an excessive response when they are rejected, whether the rejection is genuine or imagined. Studies have shown that adults who were exposed to a rejecting attitude by their parents when they were children have a stronger sensitivity to rejection (Downey, Lebolt, & O'Shea-Lauber, 1995); and play a negative role in interpersonal interactions (Creasey & McInnis, 2001; et al., 2012). Studies have shown that adults who were exposed to a rejecting attitude by their parents while they were children have a higher sensitivity to rejection.

Persons who are sensitive to being rejected are also seen to display the cognitive, physiological, and behavioral traits of persons who suffer from social anxiety.

When comparing social anxiety and rejection sensitivity from a developmental standpoint, researchers found that both conditions have comparable characteristics. According to research published by Mulkens and Bogels (1999), Kimbrel (2008), and Stemberger, Turner, Beidel, and Calhoun (1995), traumatic events that a person has personally experienced or observed in the past are a significant factor in the development of social anxiety. Childhood is the time when a person first develops a sensitivity to rejection. Based on dysfunctional attitudes in relationships as opposed to fundamental worry about humiliation and betrayal, theorists said that the foundation of rejection sensitivity is interpersonal problems and rejection experiences in the past (Bowlby, 1969, 1973, 1980; Erikson, 1950; Horney, 1937; Sullivan, 1953). Bowlby, Erikson, and Horney all stated that the basis of rejection sensitivity is rejection experiences in the past.

A youngster who grows up to be sensitive to rejection is less able to generalize their learning and more likely to struggle in their relationships with other people later in life. People who are very sensitive to rejection, on the other hand, have a tendency to avoid or participate in less personal connections in an effort to cut down on the likelihood that they would be rejected. According to Thomas (2000), the fear of being rejected is what causes both rejection sensitivity and social phobia. People who suffer from both conditions tend to avoid expressing their thoughts and feelings.

Because of the evidence presented here, it has become clear that the notions that are classified as sensitivity to rejection and sensitivity in interpersonal relationships are directly connected to social anxiety.

According to the data that were collected, it was discovered that there was a difference between rejection sensitivity and gender, as well as the education level of the mother, the education

level of the father, and the socio-economic level. In conclusion, it was found that there was a substantial connection between social anxiety and sensitivity to rejection (Erozkan, 2004b). This was one of the findings.

According to the findings of many research on the topic of rejection sensitivity, those who are very sensitive to the feeling of being rejected tend to restrict their interactions with other people and go to great lengths to avoid being rejected by others. According to Downey and Feldman (1996) and Downey, Mougios, Ayduk, London, and Shoda (2004), the actions that were shown in order to avoid being rejected have disturbed or hampered social contact.

However, one of the distinguishing characteristics of those who had a high rejection sensitivity was that they had a bias in the way that they processed information. It was revealed that there was a substantial association between social anxiety and rejection sensitivity in research that was conducted in Turkey by Erozkan (2004b). In this study, university students' sensitivity to rejection and their social anxiety levels were studied according to several characteristics. In addition, if we make the premise that our biopsychosocial past is responsible for our sensitivity to rejection, then... That is to say, in a way, via our experiences, in combination with our innate biological responses to danger, we learn to anticipate either acceptance or rejection (Romero-Canyas et al. 2010). In a nutshell, we may say that developing sensitivity to rejection is a process that continues throughout one's whole life. In addition, it has come to light that the variable of rejection sensitivity plays a function as a partial mediator between self-hiding behavior and fragile narcissism (*Mirror Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 2019, 6(2), 127–148). This understanding was published in the *Mirror Journal of Clinical Psychology*. According to Horney (1937), the main anxiety tendencies about being abandoned, abused, humiliated, and betrayed in close relationships are rejection sensitivity. Studies have shown that individuals with an increased level of fragile narcissism show an increase in rejection sensitivity due to their low self-esteem (Besser & Priel, 2009; Besser & Priel, 2010).

According to research done by Koc, Ugur, Olak, and Yolcu (2018), both rejection sensitivity and avoidance are factors that may be used to predict mental health. According to Fontana et al. (2018), psychopathology was connected with rejection, anger over rejection, and fear of rejection, whereas internalization issues were associated with fear of rejection. It has been discovered that persons who are sensitive to rejection have a decline in the clarity of their self-concept when they experience rejection (Ayduk, Gyurak, & Luerssen, 2009). According to Oktan (2012), there is an inverse correlation between teenagers' levels of subjective well-being and their sensitivity to being rejected. Rejection sensitivity, borderline personality features, borderline

personality disorder (Ayduk et al., 2008; Berenson et al., 2016; Staebler, Helbing, Rosenbach, & Renneberg, 2011), and depression (Ayduk, Downey, & Kim, 2001; Beeson, Brittain et al., 2011) are some of the conditions that have been linked to BPD. The year is 2020 in Vaillancourt. 2006 publication by Harper, Dixon, and Wales. The Cranes and the Wells, 2017. The year Mersin, 2008. 2017 according to Normansell and Wisco. Zimmer Genbeck, Nesdale, Webb, Katibi, and Downey, 2016) ... However, sensitivity to being rejected. There is many research that indicate the link with social anxiety (McDonald et al., 2010; Bintas-Zorer, 2015), post-traumatic stress disorder (Wang & Chung, 2020), and hostile self-actualization (Breines & Ayduk, 2015). Some of these studies are included in the previous sentence. According to the findings of the research that were discussed, we are able to conclude that an overly sensitive response to rejection is detrimental to one's mental health.

When looking at the research that have been done on rejection sensitivity, it has been discovered that our nation has relatively few studies and resources dedicated to the topic of rejection sensitivity. Protecting and enhancing people's mental health is critical work that has to be done for the sake of society.

2.1.1.1 Rejection Sensitivity Related Disorders

If we think about rejection sensitivity as a cognitive sensory process, then we can anticipate that it will have a significant impact on the relationships that are the most important to us (Downey & Feldman, 1996). Extensive study on social processes has shown that sensitivity to rejection is very necessary in the process of fashioning interpersonal connections. According to Purdie and Downey's research from 2000, high rejection sensitivity is linked to increased levels of both anxiety and aggression in romantic relationships. However, a higher risk of sexual assault (Young & Furman, 2008) is also associated with lower academic performance (Downey et al. 1998), social withdrawal (Holliday, 2008), emotional regulation deficits (Silvers et al., 2012), and hostility and aggression (Ayduk, Gyurak, & Luersen, 2008. Ayduk, May, Downey, & Higgins, 2003). Jacobs and Harper (2013); Waisbrod, Rosenbaum, and Ronen (2012); Cassidy and Stevenson (2005)). In addition to this, greater levels of rejection sensitivity are linked to higher degrees of neuroticism (Brookings, Zembar, & Hochstetler, 2003) as well as problematic Internet usage (Davis, 2004).

According to research conducted by Parker (2002), rejection sensitivity manifests itself as a persistent personality style that is widespread. As a result, atypical sadness is the condition in which this style is seen most often. (Derecho, Wetzler, McGinn, Sanderson, & Asnis, 1996), he

advocated for the modification of the clinical definition of atypical depression as a disorder that is rather frequent. People who have been diagnosed with atypical depression and have a high rejection sensitivity react differently to antidepressants than those who have a lower rejection sensitivity, according to research by Joyce and colleagues (2004). According to the findings of a recent research conducted by Johnson et al. (2013), those who have been diagnosed with bipolar illness have a higher risk of being rejected in comparison to healthy controls. In addition, when we examined the sensitivity to rejection of persons with active depressed mood and those with acute mania, we found that people diagnosed with depression were more likely to be rejected. This was the case regardless of whether or not they had mania.

Beck (1967) and Linehan (1993) found that those who suffer from depressive disorders and borderline personality disorder are more likely to worry about being rejected or having their feelings rejected by others who are important to them. People who are easily hurt by rejection always have a greater chance of being rejected by others than they do of being accepted by them. They are fast to feel social rejection, even in social contexts that are neutral, which is why they often act badly against other people. A self-fulfilling prophesy is characterized as a vicious spiral that leads to beliefs of prospective rejection and maladaptive behavior (Feldman, Downey, Kowalski, & Leary, 2004). The rejection sensitivity model (Feldman, Downey, & Leary, 2004) is a self-fulfilling prophecy. It has the potential to result in true rejection. This makes it more likely that we will be denied again and again. There are not many research that have attempted to find evidence-based hypothesis testing and rejection sensitivity as well as related variables. After four years, Brendgen et al. (2002) discovered that a kid who reported experiencing parental hostility at the age of 12 was more sensitive to being rejected. This conclusion is in line with the findings of Downey and Feldman, who investigated the role of family history in young people's experiences of physical aggressiveness. According to the American Psychiatric Association (2000), borderline personality disorder is a mental illness that is characterized by interpersonal instability, poor self-image, and high impulsivity. People who have this diagnosis have an extremely high sensitivity to the stress caused by interpersonal interactions. As borderline personality disorder, it has made its way into the canon of Turkish literature. The dread of being abandoned is another characteristic that plays a significant role in borderline personality disorder. As a result, border features have significant rejection sensitivity associated with them. In certain non-clinical research (Ayduk, Zayas et al., Boldeo et al., 2009, Meyer et al., 2005), the frequency of borderline symptoms has been shown to be linked with rejection sensitivity. The relationship between childhood experiences and borderline personality traits was investigated by some researchers (Ball & Links, 2009; Battle et al., 2004; Bornovaalova, Gratz, Delany-Brumsey, Paulson et al. Lejuez). These researchers

argued that childhood traumatic experiences play an important role in the etiology of borderline personality traits. Rogosch and Cicchetti (2005); Trull (2001); Carlson, Egeland, and Sroufe (2009); Lobbestael, Arntz, and Bernstein (2010); Rogosch and Cicchetti (2005); Trull (2001). According to Zanarini (2000), between 40 and 70 percent of those who have borderline personality disorder had experienced some kind of sexual abuse.

Not just one's own parents but also one's own contemporaries have a significant role in one's development. (Wolke, Schreier, Zanarini, & Winsper, 2012) Recent research has demonstrated that people display borderline traits as a result of being physically and emotionally abused by their peers while they were children. This abuse occurred throughout their formative years. When these studies are taken into consideration, there is evidence that abuse at the hands of a parent or peer is a risk factor for borderline symptoms (Ihan, 2018).

Patients who are depressed and who exhibit signs of depression such as feelings of worthlessness, despair, and poor self-esteem may be more prone to being rejected than patients who are not depressed. Multiple studies (Gilbert et al. 2006, Harper et al. 2006, Mellin 2008) have shown that there is a substantial correlation between depressive symptoms and how sensitive an individual is to feeling rejected by others. In recent research that examined the causal link between depression and rejection sensitivity, Pearson, Watkins, and Mullan (2012) discovered rejection sensitivity as a predictor of rumination depression. This finding was made possible by the fact that rejection sensitivity was shown to be associated with rumination depression. A high sensitivity to rejection is a risk factor for the development of depressive symptoms in adulthood. It also seems to magnify the effect that adverse life experiences have. On the other hand, McCarty and colleagues (2007) demonstrated that sadness is a predictor of rejection sensitivity and, as a result, of the cyclical relationship between depressed symptoms and rejection sensitivity. In addition, McDonald et al. (2010) discovered that the number of supportive connections that person has is a determining factor in the association between rejection sensitivity and depressive symptoms. As a result, having strong social support may play a role in mitigating the impact that being sensitive to rejection might have on depression. Brown et al. (2007) discovered that the effects of mother rejection and a lack of love were more powerful than the effects of other types of maltreatment in causing persistent depression. According to the findings of Van Hamelen et al. (2010), emotional abuse is a more significant risk factor than either physical or sexual abuse. According to the findings of Tronic and Reck (2009), the absence of contact between a mother and her kid might lead the youngster to experience sadness and anguish. In addition to rejection, hypersensitivity to

rejection has been shown to be connected with depression (Rosenbach, 2013). These conclusions are based on evidence-based research on the subject of depression.

People who have a high rejection sensitivity may have problems creating learning methods and retaining a feeling of self-efficacy as a result of anxious expectations and defensive responses to social rejection (Downey & Feldman, 1996; Feldman & Downey, 1994; Romero, Canyas & Downey, 2005). These difficulties may be caused by anxious expectations and defensive reactions to social rejection. Dignat, Buettner, and Langfeld (2008) and Pintrich and DeGroot (1990) define learning strategies as "conscious efforts to improve learning outcomes arising from cognitive, meta-cognitive, and motivational strategies." Learning strategies may be broken down into three categories: cognitive, meta-cognitive, and motivational. According to Butler, Doherty, and Potter (2007), it has a detrimental effect on an individual's sensitivity to rejection, their interpersonal skills, and their capacity to form new connections. According to Ayduk et al.'s research from 2000, rejection sensitivity is also linked to a loss of self-esteem that is connected to perceived levels of ability. In this scenario, we are able to make the assumption that individuals who have a high rejection sensitivity may not have the capabilities to construct learning methods and demonstrate self-efficacy (Ihan, 2018). According to Harper, Dickson, and Gal (2006), high sensitivity is associated with conduct that demonstrates self-control. According to the findings of Harper et al., self-restraint behavior in sensitive persons results in the suppression of personal opinions in an effort to sustain relationships and maintain an intimate level of connection.

2.1.1.2 Theories of Rejection Sensitivity

According to Maslow's theory from 1954, one of the most fundamental wants of humans is the need to be accepted and approved of by other people. When we consider rejection sensitivity within the context of attachment theory, individuals start to take on the characteristics of people. If they are unable to receive the support that they are searching for during this phase, they begin to form the expectation that they will be rejected, and they begin to take steps to ensure that this does not occur (Bowlby, 1969). This strenuous effort is performed in an attempt to rid oneself of the mental anguish caused by being rejected. At the same time, those who make this effort start looking for signs of being rejected. The individual believes that if they can locate any hints, they will be able to defend themselves from being rejected. According to Bozkus and Araz (2015), when people make an attempt to uncover these hints, it leads to their taking little facts personally and finding negative meaning in such information.

Two presumptions form the basis of the idea that rejection sensitivity is a process that continues throughout one's life. The acceptance/rejection dichotomy is the first one of these dimensions. In this aspect, the importance of the need that individuals have for one another as a factor in their continued existence is underlined. The emotional and mental well-being of individuals is improved as a direct result of the connections that are formed between them. It's likely that people may see the lack of these links as a potential danger. According to Romero-Canyas et al. (2010), individuals see the prospect of achieving approval while simultaneously avoiding rejection as a driving motivation.

The second method is known as the biopsychosocial approach to sensitivity to rejection. This is based on the assumption that individuals learn how they are rejected and accepted based on the experiences they have had with potential danger. Anxiety over being rejected might be triggered by various situations. According to Romero-Canyas et al. (2010), the individual may have developed the expectation that they would be rejected by certain groups or persons, such as their parents or their classmates.

According to Romero-Canyas et al. (2010), the ways in which individuals receive information and their feelings of being accepted or rejected varies. According to this theory, processing both cognitive and emotional information is involved in the development of rejection sensitivity. According to Mischel and Shoda (1995), this system, which is known as the cognitive-emotional processing system, is considered to be significant in terms of making sense of rejection sensitivity and stressing interpersonal differences. In the cognitive emotional processing system, there are five components that are discussed on how individuals receive information, and each cognitive characteristic describes how a person would interact with their surroundings. It has been found that individuals' items vary from one another (Mischel & Shoda, 1995).

The explanation of how information is handled, utilized, and stored is provided through coding. In the section under "Expectations and Beliefs," the individual discusses how he or she infers meaning from the actions of other people. Values are the component that are associated with the process of rewarding an individual's objectives and actions in life. Emotion is the component that defines how a person emotionally responds to different situations. talents and self-regulation refer to a person's level of intellect, as well as their knowledge and talents.

Feldman and Downey (1994) developed the rejection sensitivity model in order to investigate the ways in which psychological and mental elements influence interpersonal connections. According to Downey, Lebolt, and Rincon (1998), the Rejection Sensitivity paradigm

is a paradigm that explores the relationship between social learning and attachment in a holistic manner. According to this point of view, it is anticipated that the relationship between a parent and a kid would be connected to rejection sensitivity. According to Sarcam (2011), it was discovered that the rejection sensitivity of a group of university students who indicated that they were exposed to democratic parental views was lower than that of the other students. It has been shown that persons who are very sensitive to rejection (RD) have more experiences of rejection than those who are not highly sensitive to rejection; experiences were assumed to be effective in the creation of RD (Lou & Li, 2017).

According to the rejection sensitivity hypothesis, individuals who have a high level of rejection sensitivity read irrelevant signs and see them as rejection because they anticipate being rejected in the context of their connections with other people throughout their life (Downey & Feldman, 1996). According to Downey, Feldman, and Ayduk (2000), having an expectation of rejection makes it easier to have perceptions of rejection, and these perceptions, in turn, reinforce the person's expectations of being rejected. Due to the fact that the individual reinforces their expectations, they are unable to develop a connection that is to their liking. These individuals avoid having any form of connection or relationship at all in order to avoid the possibility of being rejected. There are two possible emotional responses that might happen as a direct consequence of rejection sensitivity. According to Downey and Feldman (1996), there are two types of rejection sensitivity: one is rejection sensitivity in the form of furious anger, and the other is rejection sensitivity in the form of nervous anticipation.

When a person has furious rejection sensitivity, when they are presented with the hint they uncover, they may overreact and get upset, demonstrate aggressive conduct, or experience hostile sentiments. This might happen if they have angry rejection sensitivity. On the other side, the person who nervously anticipates to be rejected is continually self-affirming by putting it in their psyche. They believe that they deserve to be rejected. Even while these two feelings may be seen independently of one another, it is nonetheless feasible for them to be experienced simultaneously in certain people. They first believe that the conduct of the other person is unfriendly, which causes them to experience feelings of isolation; as a consequence, they exaggerate their response to the circumstance and start looking for approval (Downey & Feldman, 1996).

Researchers Downey and colleagues (2004) looked examined rejection sensitivity as a potential defensive motivation mechanism. People who have anxious expectations of being rejected are more likely to engage in behaviors that reinforce their worry, as was noted before.

According to Downey et al. (2004), the dynamics of rejection sensitivity serve to safeguard an individual against potential "touch-ups" from the actions of other individuals or groups.

Research into the organizational principles of behavior typically discusses two primary systems. The first of them is referred to as the incentive system, and it refers to the reactions to positive stimuli (reward). The second system is termed the defensive motivation system, and it refers to the reactions that are delivered in response to negative stimuli (threat, punishment). The individual's actions and decisions about flight or fight in dangerous circumstances make up the defensive motivation system. It is dependent on the perceived condition as to which of these two systems should be activated. When we are confronted with a challenging circumstance, our defensive motivation system kicks into gear so that we can defend ourselves. A comparison may be drawn between the rejection sensitivity system and the defensive motivation system. According to Lang et al. (2000), those who have a high rejection sensitivity are better able to perceive dangers and immediately engage the defensive motivation system when they are in a setting where they are likely to be rejected. People who have a low sensitivity to rejection, on the other hand, are less likely to activate the defensive motivation system in the same context. This is due to the fact that these individuals give very little thought to the prospect of being rejected.

Horney proposed that feelings of concern about being mistreated emerge with early experiences of rejection and that this predisposes individuals to a painful sensitivity to any kind of rejection, regardless of how little it may seem. According to Horney's definition, rejection sensitivity is a neurotic personality characteristic that an individual unknowingly cultivates in order to alleviate his discomfort. In spite of the fact that the individual believes that they are protecting themselves, the truth is precisely the reverse of what they believe. Because they are so sensitive to being rejected, the individual causes issues in their social relationships (Horney, 2007). According to Horney (1991), the fact that rejection includes feelings of shame is the root cause of the genesis of rage as a consequence of sensitivity. It is possible for the individual to express his anger via actions that are classified as passive aggressive, and as a consequence, these behaviors might lead to avoidance (Horney, 2007).

According to Ayduk (1999), the concept of rejection sensitivity places an emphasis on the fact that the expectation of the individual should not be considered the main issue. People who have a low sensitivity to rejection have a different way of understanding both acceptance and rejection than those who have a high sensitivity. It has been claimed that what really counts is how one chooses to perceive the events that are taking place. It illustrates how the parental acceptance-rejection theory is interpreted, which is the point at which it is molded in the person. According to

Feldman and Downey (1994), infants internalize their perceptions of either explicit or implicit rejection throughout childhood, which results in rejection sensitivity. It would seem that sensitivity to rejection is a significant factor in the relationship between psychiatric symptoms and the acceptance or rejection of children by their parents.

The notion of regulatory foci is another one of these theories. In cases of rejection sensitivity, it is also considered a kind of coping technique (Higgins, 1997). According to this hypothesis, the individual's level of motivation is determined by two different self-regulation processes. The first kind of regulatory system is known as the orientation-oriented regulatory system, while the second type is known as the avoidant-oriented regulatory system. While the approach strategy that seeks to maximize benefits in order to accomplish the outcomes that have been sought is referred to as an "oriented regulatory focus," the avoidance strategy that seeks to minimize losses in order to steer clear of outcomes that are not desired is referred to as an "avoidant regulatory focus system" (Higgins, 1997).

2.1.1.3 Etiology

The development of rejection sensitivity may be traced back to formative events, which play a significant role in the process. In order to maintain a good connection between a parent and kid, there must be a feeling of trust present. The fundamental trust connection has been proposed as a component that shields the person from great mental effort following the experience of rejection and from emotional effects that may disturb their social interactions. This protection applies to persons who have had a high number of rejections in their everyday lives. The kid who exhibits secure attachment—that is, who is consistent, approachable, and attentive to his or her needs—is the child who is able to know for certain that the anxiety he feels when his mother leaves him is just transitory and that he is or will be with his mother again. The establishment of schemas that lead to protective expectancies of rejection in later relationships might be triggered by rejection experienced in intimate interpersonal interactions. Bowlby (1969, 1973) put out the hypothesis that an essential component of an individual's personality is a response to the many interactions that person has with other people. Those individuals who are subjected to verbal or physical aggression, emotional neglect, and severe disciplinary attitudes on the part of their parents while growing up in a conditional love environment have a diminished feeling of confidence in their parents and likely to develop attachment patterns that are avoidant or anxious. If we take the dismissive attachment style as an example of the defensive aspect of attachment styles, we see that

the person who has this style avoids deep connections, shields himself from disappointments, and keeps himself from feeling wounded. Similarly, even though anxious and avoidant persons want to have deep connections with other people, they avoid getting too close to the other person in their relationships out of fear of being hurt (Baldwin & Kay, 2003; Godleski et al., 2019; Kesebir et al., 2011; Pomerania's et al., 2010). This is due to the fact that they are afraid of being rejected or rejected by the other person. In research involving humans and functional magnetic resonance imaging, there was an increase in activity in the dorsal anterior cingulate cortex and anterior cingulate, both of which are areas of the brain, when the participants had experiences of social rejection (Williams, 2003; and Williams, 2003). Rejection from others, whether real or imagined, triggers the release of the stress hormone cortisol and leads to an increase in the production of inflammatory cytokines. According to DeWall and Bushman (2011), a stressful circumstance may have an effect on progesterone, a hormone that can be influenced by changes in mood. This condition also produces stress.

2.1.1.4 Common Rejections

The conditions in which a rejection takes place may have a significant influence on the one who was rejected (<https://www.yasantipsychology.com/kisisel-gelisim/reddilme-neden-aci-verir>). Rejections can take place in a number of settings, and the impact they have on the individual who was rejected can vary. Additionally, for a single person, the person or people who delivered the rejection is just as crucial as the message itself. According to Uncu and 2021, there are four different types of rejection: rejection from one's parents and other family members, rejection from one's peers, rejection in romantic relationships, and societal rejection.

2.1.1.4.1 Parent and Family Denial

According to Rohner and Rohner (1980), parental acceptance is defined as attitudes and actions that are influenced by parental love and warmth in the face of child rejection. They describe it as an inappropriate manner of expressing unpleasant sentiments or demonstrating bad attitudes and actions against oneself. Specifically, they say that it is a mistake to self-blame. That is to say, in the majority of instances, parental rejection is coupled with a lack or seeming lack of warmth and compassion towards the kid (Uncu, 2021).

Children who are subjected to rejection from their parents may grow into adults who lack confidence in themselves and others. It has been shown that young children's minds acquire erroneous ideas and beliefs about themselves and the world (as described in Rohner, 2004). young ideas and beliefs may have a negative impact on the rest of their lives.

2.1.1.4.2 Peer Denial

After their parents, children who are of school age place the most emphasis on their relationships with their classmates. Children are able to cultivate their social skills, learn and try out new adaptive behaviors, get emotional and social support, and stimulate their cognitive and emotional development via the establishment of peer connections, which provide an atmosphere conducive to such growth. When it comes to connections with one's peers, actions that are seen favorably lead to popularity, whereas behaviors that are viewed unfavorably lead to rejection. Children who are subjected to rejection by their peers have feelings of isolation as a direct consequence of this. This circumstance not only prohibits children from forming healthy connections, but it also has a detrimental impact on their overall development (Erwin, 2000).

2.1.1.4.3 Rejection in Romantic Relationships

When seen from the perspective of child development, romantic connections emerge as a central concern, particularly throughout the adolescent years. People who anticipate being rejected are just as uneasy in their relationships with their partners as they are with other people. The anticipation of being rejected might bring to unfavorable circumstances in a relationship. According to Carnelley, Pietromonaco, and Jaffe (1996), it may make relationships challenging not just for those who are sensitive to rejection but also for their spouses.

Some relationships are healthy and thriving, while others are plagued by issues that keep coming to the forefront. When we take into account this circumstance, we can see that the sensitivity to the rejection of a partner is a component that both causes and perpetuates the issue. There is a wide range of ways in which partners may recognize and assess their relationships. Numerous studies have shown that the way one partner's conduct is viewed by the other may have a significant impact on the way the relationship functions. According to Finkel and Campbell (2001), negative attitudes can cause and contribute to the breakdown of partnerships.

People retreat from romantic relationships as a kind of self-protection because they are afraid of being hurt by the prospect of rejection in partnerships that include a certain level of closeness. According to Creasey and Hesson-McInnis's (2001) research, they could have a propensity to give up. It has been found that couples whose members tend to direct their emotions inwards or outwards, as a result of which they are more dissatisfied with their relationships, are comprised of people who view the behavior of their partner as a form of targeted rejection or who believe that their own needs and desires are unimportant to their partner. Both Bradbury and Fincham (1992) as well as Downey and Feldman (1996).

2.1.1.4.4 Social Rejection

People are able to form meaningful and significant relationships with one another, one of which is via the establishment of social interactions. It is possible for a person to have significant difficulties in their life as a result of the degradation of social interactions or an inability to build healthy relationships (Uncu, 2021).

A certain body of research on social skills relates and identifies social rejection with three primary characteristics. According to Irwin (2000), these factors include the amount of time spent engaging with other people, the type of the connection, and the degree of acceptability in society.

Behaviors that are socially acceptable and popular may both learn and find solutions to issues. The capacity to sustain social interactions is analogous to layers of an onion, with each layer representing a different set of experiences that are placed one on top of the other. According to Creasey and Hesson-McInnis (2001), an individual's past experiences with rejection might have a lasting impression on his life and make him more sensitive to the feeling of being rejected.

2.1.2 Fear of Rejection

When going into a new setting or meeting new people, whether it be in business interactions, personal connections, or marriages, there are likely to be a few things that individuals are terrified of. When we constantly ask ourselves questions like "I wonder," "Will they accept me among them?" and "How are the people in the environment?" we set ourselves up for potential feelings of unease. It's possible that someone is afraid of being rejected if they avoid situations

like these, as well as social situations and job interviews, and even if they can't find the words to express themselves.

It is the conviction that they will be shunned and placed in a horrible position in every location and by everyone, as well as the worry that this thought produces. The fear of being rejected. In a childhood that has already experienced or received physical or psychological signals, the fear of being rejected may have a significant effect on the development of the kid.

The fear of being rejected is the worry of behaving in a manner that is unpleasant, embarrassing, or embarrassing in front of other people. For instance, individuals have extreme feelings of embarrassment, humiliation, and anxiety if they are forced to eat in public, make phone calls, write their names, or sign their names in front of other people (Ozturk, 2002).

People who suffer from a fear of rejection are more likely to isolate themselves socially, have poor levels of self-esteem, and avoid interaction until they are certain that they will be accepted (Erozkan, 2009).

When a person reaches maturity, the fear of being rejected may present itself in a variety of ways, including reluctance and worry when entering unfamiliar places, inability to eat, and difficulties communicating. Individuals who have low self-esteem are more likely to suffer anxiety when they are in social settings. Because having a low self-esteem may induce unjustified fears of rejection, anxiety of criticism, and expectations of failure in interpersonal interactions (Baldwin & Sinclair, 1996; Baldwin & Main, 2001; de Jong, 2002); this is because having a low self-esteem can lead to a lack of confidence. However, the avoidance, mistrust, and passive-aggressive conduct of shy persons in their social and emotional connections may be the cause of their fear of being rejected.

People who are anxious about being rejected are obsessed with patterns and schemas linked with their thinking, including emotions of worthlessness, inferiority, uselessness, and incapability, as well as a variety of other experiences.

It was discovered in recent research (Jauk & Kaufman, 2018) that grandiose narcissism was related with a low degree of fear of rejection, but fragile narcissism was connected with a high level of fear of rejection. This was found to be the case when comparing the two types of narcissism.

As a consequence of this, people who are terrified of being rejected may give off the impression that they are grownups who suffer from high levels of anxiety, who experience feelings of being exploited in interpersonal connections, social contexts, romantic partnerships, and marital relationships, who are miserable, and who go through feelings of disappointment and despair.

2.1.3 Rejection Schema Area

The Rejection Schema Area shows out as the schema area that is characterized by the inability to fulfill the need for secure attachment and the deprivation of fundamental needs such as love, respect, and tolerance (Rafaeli, Bernstein, & Young, 2011; Roediger, 2009). The Rejection Schema region stands out as the schema region that is characterized by the inability to meet the need for secure attachment and the deprivation of basic needs. According to Rafaeli, Bernstein, and Young (2011), the majority of the time, the kid has been mistreated or was raised in an atmosphere that was emotionally cold or rejecting.

According to Young, Klosko, and Weishaar (2003), this schema area is broken down into a total of five sub-categories, with the first four of those sub-categories being regarded as the most harmful schemas. The following schemas are specified within this area:

This schema area can be seen in cases where parents are emotionally inconsistent and do not present a reliable relationship pattern, the child is neglected for a really long time (Roediger, 2009), or there is a loss of parent in the family (Rafaeli, Bernstein, & Young, 2011). Abandonment / Instability: This schema area can be seen in cases where parents are emotionally inconsistent and do not present a reliable relationship pattern. The individual is of the opinion that their intimate connection will come to an end in a relatively short period of time. It has been hypothesized that those who have this field may have gone through the ordeal of their parents divorcing or passing away when they were still young. In addition to this, it is beneficial in the development of this schema area in parents who exhibit actions that are discordant with regard to the requirements of their children (Young, 1999).

This schema region is visible when parents do not respect the kid's space and physically, verbally, or sexually abuse it (Young, Klosko, & Weishaar, 2003) or when they often lie (Young & Klosko, 1993). Additionally, this schema area is shown when the child is frequently lied to (Young & Klosko, 1993). (Rafaeli, Bernstein, & Young, 2011) People who have schemas in this area have the belief that they will be mistreated and abused by others despite the fact that there is no evidence

to support this assumption. The fact that individuals have this schema demonstrates, in most cases, that they feel that, if given the chance, other people would utilize them for their own self-serving purposes. They have the impression that other people will make fun of them, injure them, or mislead them. On the other hand, they have a propensity to interpret any kind of risk as being the result of unjust or malicious activity. During their formative years, it has been suggested that these individuals are often subjected to acts of physical or emotional abuse, social exclusion, and exposure to severe punishments or unjust actions on the part of their relatives or peers (Young et al., 2003; Young 1999).

Emotional Deprivation: This schema shows the perception that an individual's fundamental emotional needs, such as care, love, empathy, protection, and significance, cannot be satisfied in a sufficient manner. According to Young and Klosko (2006), this schema region is particularly evident in situations in which the mother is distant or indifferent and struggles to form a connection with her kid. 1993). According to Rafaeli, Bernstein, and Young (2011), individuals who suffer from emotional deprivation schema have an inner sensation of emptiness since their emotional needs are unable to be satisfied in any manner. According to Young, Klosko, and Weishaar (2003), the many types of emotional deprivations may be broken down into three categories: a lack of care, a lack of empathy, and a lack of protection. When there is a lack of care, the individual feels a lack of love, interest, and compassion; when there is a lack of empathy, there is a lack of understanding, listening, and sharing of feelings; and when there is a lack of protection, there is a lack of a power figure and a guiding person (Young & Klosko, 1993). It has been noticed that persons who have this schema usually suffer a lack of attention, empathy, and protection in their infancy, and that their parents bring them up to be cold and apathetic (Young, 1999; Young et al. 2003). In this sense, it may be said that people with this schema have a "schema."

Imperfection and Shame: This schema comprises the idea that the person perceives himself or herself as defective, worthless, undesirable, terrible, or useless and that they will separate themselves from others when this is recognized by other people. Additionally, this schema includes the belief that the individual believes that others regard them as faulty. People have tremendous sentiments of shame because they believe they are defective and inadequate, and this notion drives them. It has been suggested that persons who have this schema have been subjected to sexual, physical, or emotional abuse throughout their childhood, or that they often have parents who are critical, punitive, or unloving (Young, 1999; Young & Klosko 1993). Additionally, it has been suggested that people who have this schema tend to have siblings who also have this schema. According to research conducted by Roediger (2009), parents are the demographic group most

likely to be extremely critical of family profiles and to reject them. (Rafaeli, Bernstein, & Young, 2011) The individual believes that there is a weakness and inadequacy in himself that is not visible by anyone outside, feels that he is worthless, and thinks that no one will love him if his inner world is known by others. Additionally, the individual believes that no one will love him if his inner world is seen by others.

Social Isolation and Alienation: It has been noticed that persons who have this schema think that they are essentially different from other people and have the sensation that they are cut off from the rest of the world. This idea may also contribute to a person's perception that they are not a member of any community or organization. It has been found that this schema is noticed in individuals who are typically subjected to rejection, humiliation, or ridicule in their childhood (Young, 1999; Warburton & McIlwain 2005). This schema has been observed in persons who are generally exposed to rejection, humiliation, or mockery in their childhood. However, it has been said that it is often caused by the humiliation of the person's previous life or the absence of support from the family at the moment when socialization is taking place (Rafaeli, Bernstein, & Young, 2011). According to Young and Klosko (1993), this schema, which is more prevalent among underrepresented groups in society, may also be attributable to the fact that families in these groups have a distinct organizational system compared to that of the general population. In addition, the individual has experienced social exclusion and humiliation throughout their upbringing (Roediger, 2009), has the perception that they are alone and do not belong to any group (Young, Klosko, & Weishaar, 2003), and has been exposed to these things.

It has been generally hypothesized in this field that individuals who hold this schema are unable to form attachments to other individuals that are both safe and fulfilling. They have the misguided belief that their need for a sense of belonging, love, security, care, stability, empathy, emotional sharing, acceptance, and respect would not be satisfied. It has also been hypothesized that these individuals have a propensity to shift away from intimate connections in general and that they have a strong preference to steer clear of unhealthy relationships as they reach maturity. (2009) according to Young, Klosko, and Weishaar.

2.1.4 Parental Acceptance Rejection Theory

Kardiner (1939) and Whiting and Child (1953) are the ones who are credited with laying its groundwork. The goal of the parental acceptance-rejection theory is to provide light on the potential impacts of acceptance or rejection on children, as experienced by their parents.

Acceptance may be characterized by feelings of warmth, closeness, love, and affection, while rejection can be characterized by feelings of neglect, aggressiveness, hostility, and disdain. These impacts might take place in the behavioral, cognitive, or emotional components of a person. The impacts of one's childhood remain with them throughout their whole lives. Rohner and Pettengill published their findings in the year 1986. In addition to this, it offers general explanations for the growth and socialization of a person's relationships with other individuals throughout the course of their life (Rohner, 1986).

The Acceptance and Rejection by Parents idea saw some development in the 2000s. Its remit has been broadened to include other significant interpersonal interactions, such as those with teachers and siblings, amongst others. The viewpoint of the theory has been expanded to include all of humanity, and in accordance with the theory, a "parent or caregiver" is defined as an individual who meets the fundamental requirements of an individual who has been born over an extended period of time. According to the notion, a kid's mother, father, or grandparents; another relative; or a person who has adopted the child may all be considered to be the child's biological parents (Rohner, 2004).

According to Rohner, the feeling of acceptance or rejection that an individual receives from their parents is the primary component that shapes their personality and the way that they behave throughout their life. However, research conducted on this topic all over the globe has shown that whether or not a kid is accepted by their parents has a direct influence on their intellectual, behavioral, and emotional development, as well as their relationships with other people in the future and their own psychological well-being. It has been said that the degree of parental acceptance and rejection that a kid feels they have received from their parents, in the context of the behaviors those parents have shown toward them, is a 26% accurate predictor of the child's psychological adjustment in their later years. It has been found that persons who consider themselves as rejected are more likely to display behavioral difficulties at the point of internalization and externalization, and they show inclinations such as drug usage (Khaleque & Rohner, 2002, Roheque et al. 2005). This is the case because individuals who define themselves as rejected are more likely to believe that they have been rejected by others. According to Aydin and Yamac (2014), and Ulutas (2009), and Turner et al. (2001), the quality of the connection that exists between a kid and his or her parents has a significant bearing on the psychological well-being of the child in adulthood.

The primary foci of research have been on two different aspects of parental conduct. These are the control and autonomy aspects, as well as the acceptance and rejection ones. Control and

autonomy center on the degree to which parents are authoritarian or lax in the way they manage their children's conduct. On the other side, acceptance-rejection examines the question of whether or not a parent's demeanor is friendly or antagonistic (Erkan & Toran, 2004).

Kostic, Nestic, Stankovic, and Zikic (2014) conducted research to evaluate the association between adult persons' perceived parental rejection, family traits, and the individual's behavioral problems. Individuals who had been raised in homes that had gone through a divorce had a greater number of behavioral problems, as shown by the findings, compared to individuals who had been raised in families that were still together. In addition, it was shown that people's experiences of perceived parental rejection were positively connected with their own behavioral illnesses.

Acceptance is a parental conduct that involves being affectionate, loving, caring, and warmly approving towards the kid. Acceptance also includes accepting the child's affectionate behavior. On the other side, we might state that the attitudes and actions of the disapproved parents who demonstrate hostile and negative behaviors towards the kid. In this case, we are referring to parents who act in a hostile and negative manner.

It is a fact that children will experience varying degrees of acceptance and rejection from their parents. However, the expressions of acceptance and rejection, whether they be physical, verbal, behavioral, or symbolic, differ widely from one culture to the next. It is common for the beliefs of individuals and the actions that are witnessed from the outside to produce the same outcome. However, there may also be a lack of incompatibility, as is the case with undifferentiated rejection. The only thing that is important is how a person sees themselves in the world. According to Rohner, Khaleque, and Cournoyer's (2005) research, even if the observer observed parental neglect, the kid may have sensed acceptance.

The relationship of the mother and father with the kid, specifically how the quality of this connection is, that is, how the parents express their sentiments towards their child, is the primary emphasis of the theory (Ozyavru, 2008). The theory also examines how the quality of this interaction is.

According to Rohner (1986), there are four distinct ways in which parents might behave in a "rejecting" manner toward their children. These:

- 1) Cold and Loveless: It is the attitude of the parent that is cold and unloving, withholding warmth, love, and affection from the kid and behaving coldly towards him, which causes the child to interpret the parental conduct of the child as rejecting the child.

2) Hostility and Aggression Hostility is a kind of emotion, and aggression is the reflection of this feeling on the conduct of the parent. Hostility and aggression go hand in hand. To put it another way, when parents behave out of feelings of animosity, wrath, resentment, or hate, the conduct that often results is aggressive behavior. Parents' aggression toward their children can be realized through verbal expressions such as mocking, sarcasm, condescension, rude and cruel words; it can also occur with physical behaviors such as hitting, kicking, shoving, pinching, and scratching. 3) Indifference/Neglect: Similar to hostility and aggression, here too indifference expresses a kind of emotion, while negligence is the reflection of this emotion in behavior. The term "neglect" refers to the situation in which a child's material and physical requirements are not supplied, but at the same time the child's social and emotional needs are not given the necessary amount of attention by the child's parents. The inability of a parent to be physically and/or psychologically accessible to their child is the single most critical symptom of neglect. At this point, psychological inaccessibility refers to the fact that although the parents are physically present, they are indifferent to the demands of the child when they need it and do not give the child the feeling that they are psychologically reachable. Physical inaccessibility, on the other hand, refers to the absence of the parents from the child's life.

4) Undifferentiated Rejection: This kind of rejection occurs when a youngster has the mistaken belief that he is not loved by his parents, despite the fact that the parent does not exhibit any outward signs of hostility, anger, or apathy toward the child. In other words, it is said that subjective sensations of being hated are included in the definition of undifferentiated rejection, despite the fact that there is no objectively detectable evidence of rejection.

In addition, Rohner (2004), in his article titled "Parental Acceptance and Rejection Theory," claims that this overarching theory may be broken down into three distinct sub-theories. There are three different types of theories: personality theory, coping theory, and sociocultural systems theory.

The experience of being rejected by one's parents or primary caregivers might give birth to certain assumptions about one's personality. There have been accounts of individuals suffering from maladaptive personality disorders or psychiatric conditions. According to Rohner et al. (2012), some of these symptoms include hostility, poor self-esteem, feelings of inadequacy, a lack of emotional responsiveness, mood swings, and a pessimistic worldview.

According to Rohner et al. (2012), the coping sub-dimension examines the reasons and methods by which some individuals and children do not develop mental health difficulties as a result of parental rejection.

The behavior and behavior of people in the society, within the context of their general attitudes towards acceptance or rejection by their parents, is a sub-dimension of the sociocultural system. This behavior and behavior are a sub-dimension of the sociocultural system. It focuses on circumstances in which an individual's ideas are influenced (Rohner, 2004).

2.1.4.1 Psychological Symptoms of Parental Rejection

The cognitive, emotional, physiological, and behavioral aspects of an individual's life may all be affected by psychological symptoms, which have an impact on the individual's psychological well-being. According to the DSM-V (2013), it is characterized as a collection of symptoms that may point to underlying psychiatric issues. According to the DSM-V (2013), in order for a person's symptoms to be considered psychological symptoms, the issue that the person is dealing with must be a psychological disorder, the symptoms must have an effect on the functioning of the person, and many of the same symptoms must be common and frequent in life.

According to Rohner and Britner (2002), the rejection of parental approval, which is a component of the events that take place throughout childhood, has an effect on the overall development of the person and leads to psychopathology. In a similar vein, it was proven in another research that parental rejection had an effect on an individual's psychological adjustment (Bouma, Ormel, Verhulst, and Oldehinkel, 2008). This study focused on the association between overall mental health and the acceptance or rejection of children by their parents. In a study conducted in the same vein, Repetti, Taylor, and Seeman (2002) discovered that some families were uncooperative, conflictual, furious, and neglected. They came to the conclusion that these features have an effect on overall childhood development and put children at risk for developing psychiatric problems. Longitudinal research that was carried out by Putnick et al. in 2015 in nine different nations indicated significant levels of parental rejection as well as increasing issues with both internalization and externalization in children. Similarly, a longitudinal study that was conducted in 2009 with 225 women and their children found that parental rejection was connected with sadness in adulthood (Feng et al., 2009). The study was conducted by Chinese researchers. According to the findings of a research conducted by Khaleque and Rohner (2002), psychological adjustment and the sense of being rejected by parents are significantly impacted when children

with conduct disorder, drug use, and addiction are subjected to parental rejection. It has been noted that individuals are more susceptible to disorders such as depression than they used to be. According to research conducted by Hale, Akse, Engels, Raaijmakers, and Meeus (2004), teenage violence is caused by parental rejection, which also predicts sadness (Ince, 2020).

No matter the culture, depression, behavioral disorders, and drug use are all concerns that are linked to parental approval or rejection, as stated by Rohner and Britner (2002). Similarly, Kessler et al. (2010) discovered that unfavorable early life experiences connected to family functions were associated with psychopathology in a study that they carried out on 51,945 individuals from a variety of socioeconomic levels in 21 different countries. This research was done by Kessler et al. (2010). Researchers Quirk, Wier, Martin, and Christian (2015) found that university students who experienced parental rejection in childhood were more likely to engage in self-sabotaging behavior owing to depressive symptoms than controls (Ince, 2020).

It has been shown, on the basis of the research that has been carried out on this topic in our nation, that there is a correlation between feeling rejected by one's parents and exhibiting signs of mental illness. Bayat (2015) and Abac (2018) both state that. In a separate piece of research, Anil and Karl (2010) showed a correlation between feeling rejected by one's parents and feelings of anxiety and despair. It was observed that people were more likely to suffer from depression if they had sentiments of rejection from their parents (Kılıc, 2012). The research was carried out on college students. In a similar vein, research that was carried out by Pektas (2015) identified evident and substantial connections between parental rejection and feelings of anxiety and depression in both male and female participants (Ince, 2020).

Another physiological research shown that persons whose brains are triggered by negative emotions, sensations, and self-evaluations are those who sense that they have been rejected by their parents. According to Slavich, O'Donovan, Epel, and Kemeny (2010), alterations have been seen in the anterior cortex, the posterior cortex, and the cingulate cortex. In other words, it is believed that the thoughts, sentiments, and self-evaluation rejections of the parents that a person recognizes when they are a youngster might have an effect on the individual's brain structure and lead to depression (Ince, 2020).

Looking at parental rejection, psychopathologies in general, OCD (Alonso et al. 2004), anxiety (Cunha & Santo, 2013; Giaouzi & Giovazolias, 2015), eating disorders (Herraiz-Serran et al., 2015), depression and suicide (Robertson & Simons, 1989; Campos, Besser, & Blatt, 2013), delinquency and behavioral problems (Simons, Robertson, & Downs, 1988; Kim et al., 2003), and

substance use (Azevedo, Simões, Marques, Cunha, & Santo, 2013) seems to be related (Ince, 2020).

In conclusion, several research have demonstrated that parental attitudes are connected with psychopathology. This association has been proven to be significant. Growing up in a dysfunctional or apathetic familial environment puts a person at danger by influencing them to develop psychopathological characteristics (Ince, 2020). According to the findings of a research that was conducted by Vulic-Prtoric and Macuka (2006), anxiety was shown to be connected with felt rejection from the father, while depression was found to be best predicted by perceived rejection from both parents. It was found in a study that was carried out in 2011 on children aged 5-6 years in Denizli, our country, that maternal rejection is the determinant of psychological maladjustment in children, whereas paternal rejection is not the only determinant of psychological maladjustment (Gulay & Onder, 2011). In addition, it was found in a study that was carried out in 2012 by Kılıc that the level of parental rejection positively predicted the level of depression in children, but the According to the findings of a research by Near and Gencoz (2011), the feeling of being rejected by one's parents is connected with having anxiety symptoms. According to Azevedo et al. (2013), on the other hand, the degree to which an adolescent's father rejects them leads to an increase in that adolescent's level of anxiety. According to the findings of the same research project, another element that contributes to increased anxiety is defensive factors rather than parental rejection (Ince, 2020).

2.1.4.2 Temperature Dimension of Parenthood

It is essential that all individuals, regardless of who raised them, provide their offspring with attention, affection, and warmth. In most cases, parents are the individuals who are responsible for their children and who shower them with love and attention. Praise, both verbal and physical, supporting facial expressions, singing songs, and telling tales are all wonderful ways for parents to demonstrate their affection for their children. In addition, actions like as providing for one's children and demonstrating compassion are manifestations of a parent's acceptance of his or her child(ren), according to Armagan (2019).

According to Candan (2006), the quality of warmth in parenting is tied to the bond between the parent and kid as well as the manner in which parents communicate their emotions to their offspring. In the dimension of warmth, it is important to note that, in addition to the behavioral components that take place between the kid and the caregiver, it represents the child's mental goal

for this relationship as it takes place. To put it another way, it is essential that the kid has the impression that he or she is loved and welcomed. One way to think about the temperature dimension is as having two different sides. On the one hand, there is love, attention, affection, and closeness offered to the kid; this is an example of "acceptance." On the other hand, there is "rejection," in which these sentiments are lost and even the feelings they exhibit are harmed (Armagan, 2019). "Acceptance" and "rejection" both have good and negative aspects.

According to Rohner (1986), parents could also have unfavorable feelings toward their offspring. There are four distinct ways in which this rejection might be expressed. (1) Sometimes parents treat their children in a manner that is unloving, uncaring, and emotionless. (2) They are unrepentant in their actions and may be cruel, confrontational, and violent toward others. (3) Could treat youngsters with indifference and a lack of consideration. And lastly, number four, they could think that they are unloved ("undifferentiated rejection"), even if there does not seem to be any carelessness or anger toward them.

In the event of undifferentiated rejection, children may feel that their parents do not love or care about them, even if there are no evident symptoms of aggressiveness, hostility, neglect, or indifference on the side of the parent (Armagan, 2019). These children may believe that their parents do not love or care for them even though there are no visible indicators of these things.

In his view, Rohner distinguishes between four different dimensions of conduct and emotion. He began by examining the connection between a hostile attitude and aggressive behavior, as well as apathy and neglect. On the one hand, sentiments of hostility might result in violent conduct, while on the other, they can lead to feelings of apathy. On the other hand, anger and aggressive behavior are linked to the connection between carelessness and apathy. According to Pektas (2015), this is due to the fact that indifference on the part of parents is only one of the numerous factors that may lead to their children being ignored.

It's possible for parents to be indifferent, insensitive, unfriendly, or furious with their children due to the way they behave. Because of their violent actions, people often experience feelings of wrath, resentment, and hate. On the other side, there are those parents who are unable

to tolerate their children, who are apathetic about them, or who are unaware of them. Indifference is shown in a person's actions when they neglect something. One example of how to handle this circumstance would be to ignore the kid or to ignore the child in order to cope with the anger that has been directed against the youngster. No matter how they seem on the outside, children who engage in any of these activities run the risk of feeling unloved and unwanted. Even if the parent did not disapprove of it, the kid may have a different viewpoint on the matter. This is a kind of undifferentiated rejection in which the parent does not love the kid, but the child is aware that the parent does not love, care for, or pay attention to him; hence, the child does not feel loved by the parent. (1986, Lorner).

2.1.4.3 Control Dimension of Parenting

The influence that a parent has on the growth and development of their kid is highly significant. Control exercised by parents is one example of this kind of influence, and the effects of this control on children as they approach puberty and adulthood are especially important. According to Rohner (1985), the concept of parental control was an extension of two facets of his theory. These two extremes may be summarized as extremely permissive views on the one hand, and rigid parenting on the other. The term "control" refers to the amount of influence that a parent has over the actions and behaviors of their kid; more specifically, control refers to the degree to which a parent may limit or restrict these behaviors. According to Gultekin (2011), the primary concerns of parents include potty training, instilling moral values, teaching domestic responsibilities, maintaining order, compliance, and conduct, and controlling aggressive tendencies.

Control is a dualistic concept in the parental acceptance and rejection theory; on the one side, there is control, and on the other, there is autonomy. A tolerant attitude and limited influence on the child's behavior are indicated by a low degree of control over the situation. When high levels of control are exercised, it is the attitudes of the parents toward their children that determine how they behave. On one extreme of this dimension, the amount of control is minimal, if not nonexistent. There are several factors that may affect the general well-being or safety of children, however there is a deficiency in the regulations that need to be developed. In cases when instruction is necessary, the kid alone is responsible for making the choice.

Parents that are too controlling often place restrictions on their children and need them to adjust to a wide range of environments and activities. They take on the attitude of making direct

choices, of setting an excessive number of rules and insisting that children follow them, and of limiting themselves in a variety of locations and circumstances. This is done rather than assisting children in making the appropriate decisions. These methods also play an invasive role in the kid acquiring specific abilities, making his own choices, developing his own norms, and growing his autonomy while the child is not in the company of his or her parents (Armagan, 2019).

2.1.5 The Effect of Rejection on Interpersonal and Close Relationships

Freud and the other psychoanalytic theorists who followed in his footsteps are credited with initiating the first theoretical advancements in interpersonal interactions. These thinkers believed that interpersonal connections were an essential component in the development of personality as well as the emergence of psychopathology. Freud focused his attention on the interpersonal dynamics that led to the internalization of relationships and the loss of objects as contributing factors in the development of depression. Baldwin (1992), on page 462: "Other theorists stated that it is a determining factor in the development of personality and in the formation of psychopathology."

When two individuals begin the process of developing a romantic connection with one another, it is inevitable that their behaviors will have an effect on one another. The exchange that takes place between these two individuals involves emotions, actions, and beliefs on both sides. In spite of the fact that the interactions within this relationship of reliance and solidarity may sometimes have a good impact, the parties' lack of awareness of one another can have a detrimental effect on those relationships and lead to the parties' distancing themselves from one another. The significance of being alert and attentive cannot be overstated in this context. To put it another way, the purpose of this activity is to learn more about one another. According to MYERS (1990), this time period provides the chance to expose the common aspects that need to be taught in comparison to each other.

It hurts a person more when they are rejected by those to whom they are emotionally attached and closely connected than it does when they are rejected by other people. This results in the development of ideas, attitudes, and actions that are inconsistent with one another in regard to the persons in question. When it comes to romantic connections and interpersonal interactions, a person might behave cautiously on the first encounter, and they may start to think about themselves in a way that the other party will not accept or enjoy, or they may avoid it. This can cause tension in the relationship. In addition to being rejected, one may also experience indirect types of rage,

such as extreme direct anger or words that are full of sarcasm. According to Romero-Canyas et al. (2010), individuals who have experienced childhood sexual abuse are more likely to shun romantic and interpersonal connections in adulthood. In addition, those who are very sensitive to the feeling of rejection may respond to it in a variety of ways, including avoiding intimate connections, under-engaging in the relationship, responding carefully and making great attempts to sustain the relationship, investing more, and investing more heavily. In a different strategy, there is a propensity to resort to violence in order to maintain control over one's partner and remove any element of uncertainty. (Ozen and Guneri, 2018). "(Ozen and Guneri, 2018)."

According to DeWall et al. (2009), children who participate in violent conduct are shunned by their peers, while adults who engage in aggressive behavior are imprisoned and secluded from society. According to DeWall et al. (2009), individuals who are excluded from their communities and live in isolation are more likely to have cognitions and perceptions that are hostile and negative toward their surroundings. This creates the conditions for aggressive behavior. A heightened sensitivity to being rejected results in dysfunctional interpersonal relationships. In addition, it is believed that interpersonal interactions and social rejection may both be related with aggressiveness and can mutually impact each other (DeWall et al., 2009; Leary et al., 2003). Specifically, it is believed that social rejection might increase the likelihood of an individual engaging in aggressive behavior.

Sensitivity to rejection acts as a kind of protective drive, which has a variety of effects on both the functioning of an individual's behavior and their psychology. People who are sensitive to rejection seem to have two different responses, in a sense, to the anticipation that they would be rejected. Those who attribute the reason for rejection to the other person have angry rejection sensitivity and give outward-type reactions (such as aggression, anger, and anger) in the event of rejection (Ayduk et al. 2001). Those who attribute the reason for rejection to themselves have anxious rejection sensitivity, and in the event of rejection, they give internalizing type reactions (such as anxiety, withdrawal, depression).

Because of this, we are able to claim that the intensity of rejection from the outside world is high in romantic relationships, interpersonal connections, and many other types of interactions. This includes the individual's emotional and physical reaction to both himself and his surroundings.

2.1.6 Rejection and Its Basis

Some individuals have a tendency to exaggerate the degree to which they are optimistic and moderate in their interpersonal behaviors, leading them to misinterpret the insensitivity of others as an indication that they are being rejected. In point of fact, when we take a look at the outcomes that they acquired from the experiences that they have had in the past, it becomes immediately apparent that these responses are founded on their connections with their parents. Because these individuals have a predisposition to be worried and anticipate to be rejected from a young age, it is simpler for them to be ready to detect rejection in their lives and to have severe emotions to being rejected.

According to Bowlby's theory of attachment, the explanation of psychological processes that demonstrates a connection between interpersonal functioning and rejection is called "rejection theory." Bowlby suggests that children build their own mental models and forms, which will have an effect on the interactions they have later in life. Bowlby contends that children develop a heightened sensitivity to rejection when the needs they communicate to their parents are met with opposition from those parents. In other words, when they seek help, the anticipation that they would be rejected by others is realized, and they place a high value on avoiding this form of rejection. Additionally, they construct a high value in avoiding rejection in general. They start to feel anxious as a result of expressing their needs to other people or letting other people know when they are wounded or unhappy. Because of this, they become extremely cautious. They interpret it as an intentional rejection even if the indications of rejection in their interpersonal connections are ambiguous or ineffectual. As a result, they experience acute feelings of rejection. This apparent rejection might be the result of emotional and behavioral overreactions, such as wrath, hostility, despair, a lack of support, jealousy, aggressiveness, fury, and excessive control that are not suitable for the conduct. This leads to the individual's failure in relationships and their inability to keep the connection going.

When it comes to satisfying the needs of young children, the attitudes of their parents are a significant impact. When parents fail to recognize and satisfy their children's needs, the youngsters will wonder, "Will I be accepted and supported by others?" This will result in an uneasy functioning, which will give rise to questions and worries. They will approach each of the connections in their life with a sense of uncertainty and a problem orientation if they have insecure functioning models. According to West and Keller (1994), faulty parental attitudes are a contributing factor in the reinforcing of insecure attachment as well as negative mental representations of "me and others." The strength of an individual's connection throughout

childhood increases, both in terms of its ability to structure relationships during subsequent phases of life and the harmony of negative mental images.

The findings of Dodge (1991) revealed that children that were rejected had a number of features in common. It was discovered that these children were more hostile, withdrawn, timid, and did not communicate (related to play) with the other children in this group in comparison to the children in their other buddy groups. It has been shown in earlier research that children who have been rejected have a unique perspective on some aspects of social life (the intentions, personalities, connections, and efforts of others), and they place less value on interacting with other people. In point of fact, in a certain sense, it was discovered that their social senses were not as developed as those of other youngsters. In addition, it has been shown that these youngsters have a bad self-perception, are introverted, shy, melancholy, suspicious, and lack initiative. They also exhibit socially undesirable behaviors such as being withdrawn, introverted, timid, insensitive, shallow, and cowardly.

It has been seen that the capacity of the youngsters who were sent away to find solutions to their difficulties is poor as well. To put it another way, those who have had experiences of rejection often have heightened sensitivity to subsequent rejection, which leaves a psychological legacy in terms of perception. According to CREASEY-McINNIS (2001), it sheds light on the possible significance of rejection sensitivity in later adolescent, adulthood, and maturity-stage relationships.

As a consequence of this, the data demonstrated that the degree to which parents accepted or rejected their children predicted their level of psychological adjustment. In romantic relationships, interpersonal relationships, social interactions, skills and capacities, and rejection in relationships associated to divorce and interpersonal violence, it seems that familial factors have a major role beginning in infancy. In addition, it has been shown that those who are involved in romantic relationships have a much-increased chance of experiencing stress and violence. In this scenario, children acquire certain behavioral patterns from their parents by watching and mimicking the patterns that they notice.

2.1.6.1 Developmental Process of Rejection Sensitivity

A great number of authorities have offered their opinions on how an individual's sensitivity to rejection grows throughout time. It is generally agreed upon that this degree of sensitivity and

dedication go hand in hand with one another. It is vital to analyze the process of attachment formation before delving into the topic of the link between rejection and attachment (Uncu, 2021).

In order for a newborn to have any chance of surviving, they need the care of an adult. This concept is referred to as "attachment" in the research that has been done. The primary caregiver is initially solely responsible for the care of the infant; but, as time progresses, the primary caregiver's duty starts to shift toward teaching the kid the skills essential for survival and serving as a companion who may assist the primary caregiver when necessary. The importance of developing a close connection with the kid that is being cared for cannot be overstated. Caregivers are able to protect the safety of children if they correctly understand the signs that children are giving them, react to the children's needs in a timely way, safeguard the children's safety, and keep regular physical touch with the children. You start to become aware of your surroundings and the wider world, and you form favorable opinions about both as a result. The formation of what is known as a secure connection may be achieved via the technique described below. On the other hand, circumstances that contribute to insecure attachment include conflicts between children and their parents as well as frequent shifts in the primary caregivers (Bowlby, 1969; Bowlby, 2012).

The early mental models that children build about themselves and their parents involve particular expectations, according to the attachment theory. These early mental models are formed while children are very young. The expectations of people who have a significant place in your life are included here. Patterns of dread and anxiety are developed in the kid when the parents often respond adversely to the child's demands and expectations, regardless of whether the child's needs are fulfilled and their aspirations are granted or not. According to Hazan and Tiras (1994), children who are put in this position display extreme feelings of emotional perplexity and uneasiness.

According to Bowlby's research from 1980, children develop a sensitivity to rejection when their parents ignore or disapprove of their desires and requirements. The symptoms of this condition don't appear until later in life, and they might give you the impression that your loved ones would turn their backs on you if you seek for help. Therefore, if they are in a position where they need to communicate their wants, desires, or emotions, they do so with fear. This dread is caused by the anticipation of being rejected, which leaves people open to being hurt by a variety of different types of rejection signals (Uncu, 2021). They focus their attention on these indicators of rejection, even if they are not immediately apparent, and this leads to the emergence of unfavorable feelings. This shift in perspective might bring on negative feelings such as pessimism, resentment, and envy. This may also have an effect on their conduct, leading to an exaggerated

response. For instance, it may take an incredible amount of effort to attempt to regulate the conduct of other people. According to Erozkan (2004c), all of these habits have a detrimental impact on one's ability to maintain healthy interpersonal relationships. Children who are not accepted as they grow up may have poor self-esteem and feel as if they have no value. They might be under the impression that they have no power over the events occurring around them and are only witnesses to such happenings. It's possible that they'll come to feel that they have no say in anything and that the outside world is hostile and unforgiving. Children tend to become more self-assured as they become older. They have a greater capacity to bounce back from setbacks and adverse circumstances. Others, namely the individuals they care about, are essential to their well-being. They learn self-confidence, self-respect, and self-acceptance, and they grow into a more realistic version of themselves when they are welcomed by those individuals (Savage, 2006).

Downey and Feldman (1996) assert that anxious anticipation of future rejection is the foundation upon which rejection perception is built. Conflict in relationships, namely the anticipation of being rejected, is presumably the source of this foundation's motivation. According to Erozkan (2004b), people who are sensitive to rejection cause difficulties in their relationships owing to factors such as a lack of trust, fear of rejection, restricted communication, and avoidance of confrontation.

According to the findings of study conducted by Ayduk (1999), people' levels of rejection sensitivity vary depending on how they understand the reasons for being rejected. To put it another way, those who have a low sensitivity to rejection and those who have a high sensitivity to rejection interpret the information they get from others in quite different ways. Interpersonal connections that are assumed to have their roots in childhood may be severely damaged when they are rejected. Children who experience rejection from their parents are more likely to experience rejection in their adult relationships. People who are easily hurt have poor self-esteem, low self-esteem, and are susceptible. People who are sensitive to rejection have low self-esteem. They run the risk of becoming dependant on their interactions with other people. People who are hypersensitive to being rejected are also more likely to have troubles in their romantic relationships. According to Uncu 2021, it is an issue for others as well, and it causes everyone involved in a relationship to feel dissatisfied.

People who have a high rejection sensitivity find it difficult to form connections with others, and this difficulty is made worse by feelings of dread and uncertainty. These worries and concerns are connected to the desire to have a place to call home. It has a one-to-one correlation to one's level of social acceptance. When it comes to interpersonal interactions, they are more

combative and antagonistic. It brings the quality down, making them as well as the other people dissatisfied. Because of this, they are more likely to suffer from mental health conditions such as depression and social anxiety (Ayduk, Mendoza-Denton, Mischel, Downey, Peake, & Rodriguez, 2000).

People who are very sensitive to rejection struggle to form intimate, healthy relationships owing to a variety of maladaptive behaviors, which makes it difficult for them to do so. Any recognition or rejection signal that is ready to capture might be shaped by the anticipation of being rejected. According to Ayduk, Mendoza-Denton, Mischel, Downey, Peake, and Rodriguez (2000), the impression that develops in this manner also serves to strengthen the anticipation of being rejected.

Those who are vulnerable to being rejected steer clear of unpleasant emotions. To put it another way, they do not risk being rejected by entering into connections with others who may or may not accept them. This is true not just in romantic but also in professional and other kinds of relationships, such as friendships and business partnerships. These individuals could have trouble approaching the ladies or men they admire, which can cause them to retreat from social situations. For instance, when a guy approaches a woman, he has feelings for, the woman can get the impression that he doesn't truly desire her since he doesn't gently decline her advances. Or, it's possible that they believe women are superior in this respect (Horney, 1997).

People who are sensitive to rejection are very sensitive to any kind of rejection, even verbal rejection. People who think like this interpret everyday occurrences like missed appointments, unfilled requests, and extended wait times as personal slights. According to Horney (2007), being rejected may result in outbursts of fury, as well as apathy and carelessness in certain cases.

People who are very sensitive to rejection often have unrealistic expectations of being rejected and have had negative life experiences as a result. It is important to recognize that this may occasionally result in the breakup of a relationship. A number of research have shown that there is evidence to support this association. Nevertheless, even while people who have rejection sensitivity are comparable, they do not have the same relationship issues and are not as severely impacted by this sensitivity as one another. According to the findings of the study, one of the probable explanations for these variations is the individual's capacity to exert control over themselves. According to the findings of these research, even those who are very vulnerable to being rejected seem to adopt tactics that require self-control in order to create connections. They will be less likely to overreact to potentially disastrous relationships as a result of this. In this

context, self-regulation also includes behaviors that include delaying the pleasure that is necessary for the process. To put it another way, an individual's capacity to self-regulate improves in direct proportion to the length of time they are able to go without satisfying a need. According to Ayduk, Mendoza-Denton, Mischel, Downey, Peake, and Rodriguez (2000), those who have greater self-regulation, also known as a higher self or better self-concept, do not have substantially damaged interpersonal interactions as a result of their heightened sensitivity to rejection.

In a similar vein, a deployed defensive plan places an emphasis on regulating compliance avoidance. This idea is outlined in the regulatory foci theory, and some research shows that it may be one of the forms of self-defense that individuals who are prone to rejection adopt. Two distinct foci are said to be responsible for regulating motivational orientations in accordance with this notion. These are: the orienting regulatory attention, the avoiding regulatory focus, and the combination of the two.

The aim of the orientational regulatory system is on achieving the objective while simultaneously maximizing profits. The goal of the avoidant regulatory approach is to cause the least amount of damage possible while simultaneously avoiding unfavorable outcomes (Higgins, 1997).

"Hiding negative emotions and avoidant regulatory focus in individuals who are sensitive to rejection" is a theory that has been supported by Ayduk, May, Downey, and Higgins (2003). As a result, these people rely on their avoidant regulatory concentration to keep themselves from displaying their bad feelings to the others around them. People who are like this often overreact to the actions of others in real life. By exercising extreme caution, their goal is to prevent making strategic relationship blunders. In this path, rather than expressing unpleasant sentiments and ideas, they choose to be aloof, to keep mute in conversations, and to be cold and distant. This shows that they are moving in the right route. People come up with a variety of techniques to combat rejection in order to shield oneself from the potential damage that might result from being rejected. On the other hand, the techniques that they use might, in the long term, be detrimental to relationships (Uncu, 2021).

Rejection sensitivity leads individuals to behave in two different ways due to the fact that it is both a motivational and protective mechanism. The response known as "anxiety rejection sensitivity" is one of these responses. To put it another way, the individual attributes the cause for the rejection to himself. In a way, it attributes the cause for the rejection to itself and accepts full responsibility for the situation. In most cases, individuals that fit this description would rather steer

clear of committed partnerships. They are more likely to experience feelings of loneliness, social anxiety, and despair as a result of their tendency to turn their emotions within. The term "anger rejection sensitivity" refers to yet another form of reaction. In this scenario, the individual channels the angry and destructive feelings that arise as a direct consequence of the rejection he has experienced and shifts the blame for the rejection onto the other party. When seen from this angle, the role is that of the one who has been treated unfairly. As a direct consequence, rage, animosity, and aggressiveness are produced. According to Ayduk, Downey, and Kim (2001), feelings that are directed at another person have the potential to escalate into verbal or physical hostility.

There are a number of psychopathologies that are linked to being too sensitive to rejection. When social avoidance, social phobia, and avoidant personality disorders are examined in terms of social inclusion, it is presumed that there are diseases such as dependent personality disorder and borderline personality disorder, including rejection sensitivity (Feldman & Downey, 1994). This assumption is based on the fact that social avoidance, social phobia, and avoidant personality disorders all have negative effects on social inclusion. People who suffer from dependent personality disorder have a greater perception that their parents did not accept them as children, in comparison to those who suffer from social phobia. In addition, those who suffer from dependent personality disorders and social phobias reported having more frequent instances of parental rejection than healthy people (Blatt & Zuroff, 1992; Parker, Roy, Hadzi-Pavlovic, & Pedic, 1992). These findings were published in two separate studies. Avoidant and borderline personality disorders reported that they had maladaptive reactions to situations where rejection sensitivity is high and therefore interpersonal stress factors are high, and they experience problems in relationships (Gadassi, Snir, Berenson, Downey, & Rafaeli, 2014; Berenson, Downey, Rafaeli, Coifman, & Paquin, 2011; Staebler, Helbing, Rosenbach, & Renneberg, 2011; Berenson, Gregory, Glaser, Romirowsky, Rafaeli, Yang, & Downey, 2016). In instance, borderline personality disorder is a kind of personality disorder that is characterized by an extraordinary amount of impulsivity. In addition to this characteristic, there are studies that reveal a strong sensitivity to rejection and a predisposition toward improper conduct (Berenson, Downey, Rafaeli, Coifman, & Paquin, 2011; Berenson, Downey, Rafaeli, & Coifman, 2012). It is also believed that early experiences of rejection are absorbed by the person, and the effects of those events manifest themselves in later stages of development. There are scientific studies showing that this may lead to psychopathologies such as depression, social anxiety, substance use, and borderline personality disorder in the future (Maccoby & Martin, 1983; Campo & Rohner, 1992; Ayduk, Downey & Kim, 2001; Ayduk, Gyurak & Luerssen, 2008).; Downey, Bonica, and Rincon, 1999; Downey, Lebolt, Rincón, and Freitas, 1996; Downey, Freitas, Michaelis, & Khouri, 1998).

2.1.6.2 Studies on Rejection Sensitivity in the Literature

Research conducted by Butler, Doherty, and Potter on college students indicated a correlation between being teased as a kid and being more sensitive to being rejected in adulthood. According to the findings of the same research, there is an inverse connection between rejection sensitivity and peer acceptability. According to Butler et al. (2007), this work may be significant in the effort to understand the origin of rejection sensitivity.

among research that was conducted by Luterek et al., it was discovered that rejection sensitivity was connected with a variety of psychiatric symptoms among university students who had been the victims of sexual abuse as children. According to the findings of the research, a trait known as rejection sensitivity acts as a go-between when childhood sexual abuse and depressive symptoms are concerned. According to the findings of Luterek et al. (2004), it has been shown to have a function as a partial mediator between childhood sexual abuse and repressed rage.

In research that was carried out by Bungert et al. (2015) for patients who were diagnosed with borderline personality disorder, healthy persons were chosen from the borderline personality disorder rejection sensitivity assessment, and it was discovered that they scored higher than the group overall. Low self-esteem was shown to be positively linked with borderline personality disorder and rejection sensitivity, and it was found to have a mediating role in the interaction between these two variables (Ozdemir, 2017). The same research also indicated that low self-esteem was positively connected with borderline personality disorder.

Romeo-Canyas and Downey (2013) conducted research in which participants were given video footage of individuals visiting online dating sites and examining the profiles of other users of the sites. After being instructed to do so, participants were then shown the profile of a person in the movie and asked to make an educated assessment as to how that individual was feeling. The participant in the film was then informed that they had watched the profile of another individual, and they were asked to speculate as to how the other person was feeling after seeing the video. After then, the researchers looked at how each individuals' responses stacked up against each other. It is anticipated that those who have a low sensitivity to rejection have more happy feelings when they are encouraged to look at profiles, but individuals who are told to look at the profiles of other individuals experience fewer positive emotions. They observed that low rejection sensitivity was

connected with interpersonal positivity and optimism, and that this permitted social engagement. This was the conclusion reached as a consequence of this research. It has been hypothesized that this trait is connected with a positive accepting tendency in persons who are less sensitive to the negative effects of rejection (Ozdemir, 2017).

Several research have been carried out to investigate the degree to which an individual's sensitivity to rejection is mirrored in their perspectives towards romantic and interpersonal relationships. Women who are sensitive to rejection reacted with anger and heightened hostility to rejection when they were rejected in a relationship, according to research conducted by Ayduk et al. in 1999. The study focused on women. It was shown in another research by Ayduk et al. that men who are more dedicated to their relationships and who are more sensitive to rejection behave more aggressively toward their partners who are more likely to be rejected than men who are less sensitive to rejection (Downey et al., 2000). This finding contradicts the findings of a previous study by Downey et al., which indicated that men who are less sensitive to rejection act more aggressively toward their partners who are more likely to be rejected.

among a separate piece of research, Downey et al. (1998) identified a conflict process as a factor that leads to the breakdown of relationships among women who are very sensitive to being rejected. It was shown that guys who had a strong sensitivity to rejection did not exhibit this pattern of behavior. It has been shown that the partners of women who have a high rejection sensitivity as a result of relationship conflict exhibit a greater level of disgust than the partners of women who have a low rejection sensitivity. This is because of the fact that these women are more likely to feel rejected. The findings of this research indicate that women who are sensitive to rejection are more likely to provide negative responses in romantic relationships, which adds to an increased likelihood of the relationship coming to an end. This was shown to be the case by preparing the atmosphere for future rejection. According to the findings of a research conducted by Downey and Feldman (1996), individuals who have anxious expectancies about being rejected are more likely to interpret their partner's insensitive or nervous behavior in a romantic relationship as an act of purposeful rejection. When this occurs, both parties are left feeling dissatisfied with the relationship. On the one hand, it has been proposed that discontent in this relationship might be due to male jealousy, which is sensitive to rejection. On the other hand, it could be due to unfriendly views towards women's relationships and a low level of social support.

Brown, James, and Taylor (2010) conducted research on the association between rejection sensitivity and self-protection inclinations in males who have high levels of violent tendencies. According to the findings of this research, the rejection-violence cycle model hypothesizes that males who have been rejected in prior relationships are more likely to turn to violence in their present relationships because they are more susceptible to being rejected again in these relationships. According to the findings of the research, aggressive males have heightened perceptions of threats, more need for self-protection, more violent impulses, and increased sensitivity to being rejected.

Researchers Ayduk, Downey, and Kim (2001) conducted research that followed university students for a period of six months and found that female students are more likely to be rejected. It was shown that those who wished to leave a spouse but already had a separation partner or made the choice to leave exhibited greater levels of depression symptoms. On the other hand, when they were applied jointly, depressed symptoms were less common.

Finally, Saricam (2011) performed a third study on university students to investigate rejection sensitivity. This time, she used a variety of factors to conduct her research. According to the findings of the study, there is a correlation between having a higher propensity to be rejected and having a lower level of self-esteem.

CHAPTER 3

THE EFFECT OF REJECTION ON PERSONALITY

3.1 Perceived Parenthood

The significance of an early connection to a caregiver is emphasized in a number of different ideas. Beginning in the very early days of a person's existence, there is an immediate and pressing need to create a social connection. According to Baumeister and Leary (1995), the desire to belong to a group and to have that group accept one has significant impacts on a person's psychological growth and well-being. This need exists in addition to the need for physical care and protection. Nevertheless, issues in the parent-child connection might have an impact on the

schema and lead to psychological challenges throughout the process of personality development. Interpersonal theory (Sullivan, 1953) is one of the several theories that have been proposed to explain human behavior. This theory places an emphasis on interpersonal contact as a means of doing so. Because one's first romantic partnership is often with a person to whom they make a lifetime commitment, the dynamics of this particular connection are also of the utmost significance. According to Bowlby (1973), attachment theory is one of the most influential theories that has ever been developed in the field of interpersonal psychology and focuses on the development of deep personal bonds. According to attachment theory, humans are born with a fundamental need for close personal relationships. According to Bowlby (1982), the purpose of this system is to provide support and protection so that the user may have a sense of safety. Attachment systems continue to function throughout a person's life (Bowlby, 1988), despite the fact that individuals develop internal representations of external attachment pictures throughout time. Bowlby makes an effort to understand the influence that one's first love experiences have on subsequent romantic relationships. Bowlby (1977) contends that individuals construct their expectations for new relationships based on the experiences they have had in the past. People have a propensity to act in certain ways as a direct result of the schemas that were created in the course of their prior relationships. For instance, individuals who have been in supportive relationships in the past tend to anticipate that they will continue to be in supportive relationships in the future. On the other hand, if the individual in the new relationship has a history of being harassed or cheated on in past relationships, they are more likely to believe that their current relationship would also deteriorate (Sarisoy, 2017).

The effects of parental acceptance and rejection on a child's short-term and long-term development were investigated by Rohner. Two parts of parenting, according to Rohner (1986), are providing parental warmth and maintaining parental authority. Signs of rejection include warmth, love, and a lack of attention, whereas signs of warmth include your presence, care, approbation, nursing, kissing, embracing, smiling, and supporting your child's needs. It is characterized by anger and aggressiveness (Rohner, 1986). It is defined by a chilly, uncaring, and unloving manner; it is physically or mentally unavailable. Previous rejection experiences have a substantial influence on an individual's psychological adjustment, worldview, self-perception, and mental health, as stated by the parental acceptance and rejection hypothesis. According to research conducted by Rohner, Khaleque, and Cournoyer (2007), individuals who have been rejected in the past are more likely to sense rejection and hostility even in circumstances that are not hostile. They claimed that these individuals were predisposed, that they had a limited ability for coping, and that they were emotionally unstable.

Research in psychology has often focused on determining the reasons for mental health issues throughout history and into the current day. These studies demonstrate that the early events of one's life are of a psychological character. It adds to the body of information about the consequences that it has on one's health. The findings are associated with perceived parenting styles and depression (Richter, Richter, Eisemann, Seering, et al. Bartsch, 1995), personality pathology (Thimm, 2010), psychological problems such as internalization and externalization (Roelofs, Meesters, ter Huurne, Bamelis et al. Muris, 2006), obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) (Alonso et al., 2004; Yo It has been shown by Turkuler, Aka, and Gencoz (2014) that there are substantial correlations between

The findings of the most recent studies are all over the place when it comes to examining the connection between perceived parenting style and personality. These discoveries may have something to do with the use of a variety of instruments or with the intricate character of personality disorders. Over-intervention and inadequate attention to children were found to be prevalent motifs in individuals with borderline personality disorder, according to Links and Monroe-Blum (1990), who conducted a review of 10 papers on the topic of borderline personality disorder. Additionally, borderline personality disorder is linked to parenting styles that are both inconsistent and persistent. In the body of research that has been done (Paris, 1996; Reich and Zanarini, 2001), there is evidence that this connection exists. In addition, Timmerman and Emmelkamp (2005) showed that signs of cluster B personality disorder were connected with a perception of insufficient care and attention from family members as well as a perception of overprotection and control. This was discovered via research conducted on inmates. Inadequate maternal care was shown to be connected with signs of cluster A personality disorder, according to the findings of the research. According to the findings of a research conducted by Thimm (2010), an increase in cluster A and cluster B personality disorder symptoms was linked to a lack of appropriate maternal emotional warmth as well as rejection from both the mother and the father. It has been suggested that those who suffer from C personality disorder also experience rejection from their fathers. After going over the available research, it has become clear that they are deemed to be parents. According to Sarisoy (2017), there is a need for research to better understand the influence that parenting styles have on personality disorders.

3.1.1. Recognition of parental rejection and psychopathology

According to Rohner, Khaleque, and Cournoyer's (2005) research, those who believe that they have been rejected by their parents are more likely to develop mental health issues than individuals who feel that they are accepted by their parents. Anxiety (Giaotsa, Kyriazos, & Mitrogiorgou, 2018), depression (Sart, Borkan, Erkman, & Free, 2016), eating disorders (Dominy, Johnson, & Koch, 2000), and obsessive-compulsive symptoms (Dominy, Johnson, & Koch, 2000) were found to be associated with parental rejection when previous research was examined (Giaotsa, et al. (Haciomeroglu, 2008), somatization (Naz, 2012), and suicide (Sobrinho, Campos, & Holden, 2016). [Citations needed] [Haciomeroglu, 2008], [Naz, 2012]. In addition, according to Rohner and Rohner (1980), children who are rejected by their parents are more likely to develop a variety of psychopathological conditions, including depression, eating disorders, behavioral issues, and borderline personality disorder.

3.1.2. The Role of Parental Rejection in the Development of Depression

According to the parental acceptance and rejection hypothesis, individuals have a tendency to display particular emotional and behavioral reactions when they do not have a fundamental emotional need, which is the need to be accepted, satisfied by their parents. This desire for acceptance during infancy and childhood may be satisfied by a parent or another significant attachment object; however, non-parent attachment objects may also arise throughout adolescence and adulthood. This need for acceptance during infancy and childhood may be met by a parent or another significant attachment object. (Rohner, 2004). a. On the other hand, according to the conceptual framework of the part that parental rejection plays in the maturation of a person, it is generally accepted that individuals who go through the trauma of being rejected by their parents as children have a propensity to interpret and/or view the people in their life as being hostile, deceptive, and dangerous. In other words, these individuals live in a pessimistic environment, and the content of their thoughts reflects a pessimistic self-perception as well as the potential for the development of a pessimistic sense of self-efficacy (Rohner & Rohner, 1980; Rohner, 2004). In other words, according to the PAR personality subtheory, people who perceive themselves to be rejected are: (1) hostile and aggressive; (2) dependent or defensively independent; (3) negative self-esteem; (4) negative self-efficacy; (5) emotionally unstable; They have a tendency to develop (6) emotional unresponsiveness; and (7) a negative worldview (Khaleque & Rohner, 2004).

According to this hypothesis, parental rejection has a long-lasting and detrimental effect on the psychological adjustment and behavior of children and people all over the globe (Rohner & Rohner, 1980; Rohner, Khaleque, & Cournoyer, 2005). This idea was developed by Rohner and Rohner. Children who experienced rejection from their parents were more likely to acquire pathologies such as behavioral disorders, depression, and drug misuse, as shown by Khaleque and Rohner (2002), who discovered a negative association between parental rejection and psychological adjustment. These researchers also showed that children who felt rejection from their parents were more likely to develop pathologies. Rohner and Britner (2002) suggested that there is a directly associated pathology and that there is a linkage between depression, behavioral difficulties, and drug misuse, regardless of culture, and that there is a relationship between the two. The findings of a meta-analysis that was carried out by Khaleque (2014a; 2014b) indicate that the feeling of being rejected by one's parents is experienced along the sub-dimensions of indifference or ignorance and hostility or violence. It has a significant impact on children's general psychological adjustment regardless of factors such as race, culture, gender, or geographic location. At this moment, while looking at the research in the field, it is indicated that all of the individual items on the Parental Acceptance-Rejection Scale (PARQ) developed by Yildiz and Dag (2017) are connected with the severity of depressive symptoms as well as the attitudes of acceptance or rejection of depression that are predictive. According to a number of studies (Feng et al., 2009; Nolan et al., 2003; Pektas, 2015; Salahur, 2010), when children and adolescents are disowned by their parents, they are more likely to display signs of clinical depression. The acceptance or rejection of fathers' perceptions affects many people, not just children and adults, and their psychological well-being is affected by psychopathology, including depression (Magaro & Weisz, 2006). The effect of parental rejection perception on depression symptoms is more important than the perception of control. (Magaro & Weisz, 2006) Furthermore, the acceptance or rejection of fathers' perceptions affects many people. Rohner and Veneziano's research was published in 2001. discovered that a feeling of rejection by one's parents was a factor in the development of depression, and that views of parental rejection were more prevalent in males than in females. (Vulic-Prtoric & Macuka, 2006) "(Vulic-Prtoric & Macuka, 2006)"

3.1.3. Recognition of Parental Denial and Risky Eating Habits

According to research by Deas, Power, Collin, Yellowlees, and Grierson (2011), negative beliefs held by parents play a significant part in the development of eating disorders. Because a person's connection with food may extend to his relationships with others he cares about (Elgin

and Pritchard, 2006; Ward, Ramsay, Turnbull, Benedettini, and Treasure, 2000). [Citations needed] Elgin and Pritchard (2006); Ward, Ramsay, Turnbull, Benedettini, and Treasure (2000). In accordance with this, it was shown in a research of female college students that those participants whose moms gave them unfavorable verbal signals about eating and drinking had more poor eating habits. Gross and Nelson's research was published in the year 2000. Another research found that bulimic women were more likely to be rejected by their dads compared to women in the control group (Dominy, Johnson, and Koch, 2000). In addition, it has been shown that the rejection and neglect that individuals go through as children contribute to the formation of negative self-perceptions and encourage people to adopt behaviors such as dieting and trying not to gain weight (Cooper, Wells, & Todd, 2004). These findings were established in a study conducted by Cooper, Wells, and Todd. Yurtsever and Sutcu (2017) discovered that the majority of individuals engage in unhealthy eating practices. They demonstrated that college students who consumed hazardous diets had a more unfavorable perception of the parenting practices of their moms and dads than students who did not consume risky diets. Another research found that individuals in the risk group felt parental rejection more strongly than their own parents did when it came to eating behaviors (Hoppe-Rooney, 2004). This finding was similar to what was found in the first study.

3.1.4. Emotional Regulation and Difficulty Regulating Emotions

According to research conducted by Marchica, Mills, Keough, Montreuil, and Derevensky (2019) and Zimmermann and Ivansky (2014), one of the characteristics that seems to have a role in the development of depressive symptoms in young people is the individual's ability to regulate their emotions. According to Rohner's research from 1986, people who were rejected when they were children likely to develop particular emotional tendencies. According to Cole and Deater-Deckard (2009) and Crow, Cross, Powers, and Bradley (2014), acknowledging the experience of being rejected as a kid may also play a part in the development of psychopathology via the mechanisms of emotion regulation. The capacity of individuals in early infancy to receive, analyze, and interpret emotional signals is distinct from the interactions that they have with their parents and the other people in their social context. According to Zeman and colleagues' (2006) research, this trait is associated with the capacity to control one's emotions. This ability may produce issues with emotional regulation (Cole, Michel, & Teti, 1994), and emotional dysregulation can lead to symptoms of depression (Mennin, Holaway, Fresco, Moore, & Heimberg, 2007). Either an excess or a lack of this capacity can cause problems with emotional regulation.

It is possible that the idea of emotional control, which refers to either the control of emotions or the self-regulation of emotions, seems to be confusing on its own. Gross and Thompson's research was published in 2007. From this vantage point, the first thing that comes to mind when we are asked to discuss emotion regulation is that, at its core, it can be boiled down to the efforts that a person makes to control his or her feelings. According to Cole et al. (1994), emotion management is the capacity to react to a wide variety of emotions that arise in the course of everyday life and to demonstrate or postpone the expression of intentional emotional responses when appropriate. According to Thompson (1994), emotional responses are the key problem at hand in this scenario. There are procedures both within and outside of the company that are responsible for monitoring, assessing, and coordinating the time of its occurrences. To put it another way, emotional regulation is a process that involves both the efforts of a person to self-regulate and the effects that come from the surrounding environment.

According to Gross and Thompson (2007), a person's capacity to manage their emotions is dependent upon how they feel emotions, what emotions they experience, and how they express those emotions. It is possible that it will not operate in the way that it should (Koole, 2009; Werner & Gross, 2010). Having trouble keeping one's emotions in check may have negative effects on one's behavior, physiology, and physique. It is possible for it to be shown in both thoughts and feelings (Koole, 2009), and according to Cole, Martin, and Dennis (2004), emotional dysregulation is a component of the process of emotional regulation. Approaches that investigate topics like emotion control, emotion control techniques, emotion dysregulation, and the inability to exert control over one's feelings may be found in published works, and you could come across some of them.

According to Gross and Thompson (2007), there are three fundamental components that make up emotion regulation. The first method is to exert one's will on another person by modulating the amount of happy or negative feelings they experience. Second, the action of controlling one's emotions takes place mainly at the conscious level and, on a scale that ranges from conscious emotion regulation to automatic regulation, moves progressively farther down the scale. Third, the process of emotion regulation may take different forms depending on the circumstances, which can either improve or worsen the situation.

Emotion regulation was investigated by Garnefski, Kraaij, and Spinhoven (2001) within the framework of emotion control techniques. These strategies may be divided into two categories: functional and dysfunctional. There are two distinct methods for retaining emotional control. The five functional strategies are acceptance, planning, active rearrangement, perspective, and active

reevaluation. Acceptance is the first functional strategy. The following are examples of dysfunctional coping strategies: (1) blaming oneself; (2) blaming others; (3) brooding; and (4) catastrophizing.

In their discussion of emotional dysregulation, Mennin, Holaway, Fresco, Moore, and Heimberg (2007) identify four distinct aspects of the condition. These include (1) an elevated level of emotional intensity and (2) an insufficient awareness of one's own feelings. According to the authors, issues with these problems are related with diseases such as depression. These difficulties include responding adversely to a person's emotional state (for example, dread of emotional repercussions), and exhibiting maladaptive reactions to the management of one's emotions.

Gratz and Roemer (2004) investigated the issue of challenges in emotional control via their research. According to the authors, the capacity to perceive emotions, analyze emotional data and reactions, accept feelings, employ situational emotion management tactics, and regulate negative emotions and impulsive conduct are all components of the emotional step. If any or all of these processes are skipped, it suggests that you have difficulties managing your emotions.

It is well known that problems with emotional regulation may have a negative impact on an individual's quality of life as well as their ability to operate (Gross & Munoz, 1995; Koole, 2009). However, these challenges are often suggested as underlying causes or reoccurring elements in a variety of kinds of psychopathology (Cole et al., 1994; Gross and Munoz, 1995; Joormann and D'Avanzato, 2010; Mennin et al., 2007; Kring and Verner, 2004).

3.1.5. The Connection Between Difficulties in Emotional Regulation and the Rejection of Children by Their Parents

It is common practice to address emotional control in conjunction with parental views. Attachment theory proposes that infants learn how to regulate their emotions as they search for answers to the questions they have about the world from their parents and other caregivers (Bowlby, 1988). In a similar vein, the development of more constructive emotion control abilities in children is dependent on parental acceptance and supportive reactions, as stated in the research conducted by Eisenberg et al. (1998). When viewed from this perspective and taking into consideration the role that these factors play in explaining depressive symptoms, it is possible to assert that the importance of parental attitudes in the process of development is taken into account. Emotional regulation is something that develops after neglect or trauma in infancy. According to the findings of Weissman et al.'s (2019) study, psychopathological issues have been demonstrated to be connected with the development of generalized psychopathology. The link between these

two significant factors has been the subject of investigation in a number of research that have been published in Turkish and international literature. (Chang, Schwartz, and Dodge, 2003; Pektaş, 2015; Sarıtas and Gençöz, 2011; Vandewalle, Moens, Beyers, and Braet, 2016).

3.2. The Theory of Personality

People who have experienced rejection have reported that it has seven distinct effects on their personalities, despite the fact that they come from a variety of ethnic, religious, and social backgrounds. These are ambivalent, ranging from favorable to negative aspects. It was shown that persons were more likely to exhibit the unfavorable side of these seven qualities if they felt that they had been rejected. According to the personality theory of interpersonal connections theory, however, the acceptance and rejection of a kid by his or her parents has a significant influence on the child's personality development throughout his or her whole life (Khaleque & Rohner, 2002).

3.2.1. Substance Abuse or the Struggle to Maintain Independence

Dependency is one facet of this characteristic, whereas independence is another facet to consider. The disadvantage of the feature is represented by the dependent side. On the dependent side, there exist challenges such as the need for approval, difficulty in making choices on one's own, and difficulties in attaining autonomy. On the independent side, on the other hand, people are able to make their own decisions and have no trouble dealing with the challenges they face. When people who have dependent personality traits experience rejection from their parents when they are children, they try to focus their attention on themselves. When these people are separated from their parents, they may experience situations in which they are anxious, reluctant, do not feel safe, and may feel the need for closeness.

In addition, in order for them to feel at ease, youngsters need to see feelings of being loved, cared for, and given attention by the attachment objects in their environment. The fact that they insist on having such sentiments demonstrates their dedication. Children who demonstrate an unhealthy attachment to their parents by acting out in ways such as whining and sobbing when their parents leave the room or seeking an unhealthy amount of attention as soon as they see their parents are reliant on their parents even though they seem independent. At later ages, children may exhibit behaviors such as seeking refuge from their parents, expecting support from their parents,

and asking them to stand behind them in times of hardship (Rohner, 2005). These behaviors might be signs of attachment disorders.

People that have personalities that lend themselves to independence do not have the same difficulties when they are separated from one another, and they are better able to adjust to their surroundings. One might reasonably anticipate that the amount of addiction in children who get a sense of acceptance from their parents will be at a level that is not troubling. When a person feels that they have been rejected, they will try many different things until they get the emotion that they are looking for, and this process will cause the person to become dependent. While this process is ongoing, the one who views it as being rejected will decrease the amount of effort he puts in to observe the anticipated response after an unspecified amount of time has passed. After experiencing something like this, the kid may give off the impression that they are self-reliant, but in reality, this independence will not be what it should be; rather, it will be a defensive independence, which is a type of independence that the child has taken against himself and uses as a protective shield.

Children who are raised with such a high level of autonomy are more likely to emotionally separate themselves from their parents, seek their company less often, and struggle less effectively with feelings of rage. According to this hypothesis, the end consequence is that children's perceptions of acceptance or rejection creates a difference in addiction. This difference might present itself in persons who are thought to be rejected as a craving for emotional support and ongoing approval (Rohner, 2005). The term of "immature addiction" is another subject that is brought up in this article. This kind of dependence manifests itself when the parents become too controlling of their children, which leads to an increase in reliance. Additionally, these parents do not provide their children the opportunity to test the limits of what they are capable of doing. This particular kind of addiction was described by Rohner as "suffocating love" (Rohner, 2005).

3.2.2. Unresponsiveness to Emotional Cues

Children, in general, learn not from the words of the parents they model in the family but rather from the attitudes the parents exhibit for them. Children who are rejected by their parents are unable to learn how to accept and offer love since they are not shown affection by their parents. Children who have been rejected may have a propensity to retreat emotionally, make few efforts, and cover up their emotions in order to protect themselves emotionally because they are emotionally spent. This tendency may be caused by emotional exhaustion. In a nutshell, they have

a propensity to give up trying. These youngsters often have a strong need to be loved. These youngsters who have been rejected have difficulties in relationships that are straightforward, friendly, open, emotionally distant, and freely intimate. They also struggle with restrictions in attachment, as well as difficulties related to defensiveness. Indifference and the flattening of emotions are symptoms that may point to a more severe disease.

According to Rohner (1984), people who have been rejected by their parents tend to withdraw from other people and bury their sentiments in order to save themselves from the agonizing sensation of anguish that comes along with being rejected. As a result, they develop into persons who are emotionally unresponsive. However, they often experience toxic feelings such as hatred, wrath, and resentment, which may be very unpleasant owing to their emotional inability to respond appropriately to situations.

It is a sign of emotional sensitivity to be able to openly communicate one's sentiments and emotions in one's relationships, without having any difficulties with trusting the other person and without having any concerns about oneself. These individuals are able to form connections with ease and have no trouble expressing who they are as individuals. People who are emotionally insensitive, on the other hand, may have trouble establishing and sustaining connections, and they may avoid forming emotional ties within the context of their interactions (Khaleque & Rohner, 2002).

Those who suffer from emotional unresponsiveness are emotionally isolated from other individuals as a result of this condition. Their interactions with other people are quite restricted, and when they do interact with other people, they often exhibit a protective tendency. Although such individuals may give off the impression of being warm-hearted and sociable, their capacity for developing meaningful connections is relatively limited. According to Rohner (2005), their connection is often one that is more guarded and fake.

3.2.3. Aggression based on hostility and aggression based on passivity

Hostile and aggressive attitudes, which are successful in the actions of parents that cause their children to be regarded as rejected, may drive children to express their behaviors as being more furious and angrier. This can lead to the children feeling rejected themselves. These same tendencies continue throughout adulthood as well. And children who have difficulty expressing their feelings may experience worry or adopt a passive-aggressive stance when they are angry

(Rohner, 1990; referenced in Yetkin, 2016). Children who have difficulty expressing their feelings may also be more likely to act in a passive-aggressive manner.

The term "passive aggression" describes the conduct of persons who are angry toward others but do not directly attack them. These actions are non-aggressive yet irritable. These behaviors may include assaulting the other person, placing barriers in their path, acting defiantly, and purposefully delaying work (Rohner, 2005). Other behaviors that may be included in this category include purposely delaying activities.

3.2.4. Having a Poor Opinion of Oneself

"Self-esteem" and "self-efficacy" are the two titles that are used to convey self-assessment in the PAR theory. The term "self-evaluation" refers to an individual's view, both good and negative, of the sum total of their feelings, perspectives, and attitudes. On the other hand, self-esteem may be defined as an individual's broad emotional evaluation of how they see themselves. On the other side, having a negative picture of oneself, disapproving of himself, blaming himself, and perceiving himself as inferior and worthless in comparison to others are all signs of having poor self-esteem (Rohner, 2000).

Negative self-esteem is a characteristic that may be seen in people who have a high sensitivity to being rejected as a result of their social interactions. In addition, this condition is referred to as low self-esteem when it is unfavorable and harmful. A self-evaluation that is characterized negatively by one's emotions is called low self-esteem. However, he is a person who has a feeling of worthlessness, hates and disapproves of themselves, views themselves as having no value, views themselves as guilty, thinks themselves to be lower than other people, and deserves to be condemned for their actions.

In addition to this, those who are anxiously attached have a tendency to focus more on the negative aspects of themselves (Mikulincer, 1995).

A person's views about themselves are often included in the definition of low self-esteem. When a person has healthy self-esteem, it indicates that they accept themselves as they are, love and respect themselves, and seldom have negative sentiments about themselves. Negative self-esteem, on the other hand, describes a person who has unfavorable thoughts about himself, reduces the significance he places on himself, demeans oneself, and considers others to be more significant than themselves. (Rohner, 1990; quoted in Yetkin, 2016) A youngster who believes that he is being

rejected by his parents may think, "They don't care about me, so I'm someone who doesn't deserve to be cared for." In this scenario, one's self-esteem may grow toward the negative end of the spectrum.

3.2.5. Self-efficacy that is not positive

A person is said to have negative self-efficacy when they do not believe they are capable of achieving their objectives, making progress toward those goals, or overcoming challenges. The individual's level of self-confidence and belief in themselves drops when this characteristic shifts from being positive to being negative. The more he thinks about it, the more anxious he becomes. The level of a person's self-sufficiency and confidence in themselves is largely influenced by the perspective of their parents in this area. The notion that the person will not be successful, that he will not be able to face challenging circumstances and be self-sufficient when they arise is formed in the mind of the kid when the child believes that the individual is rejected by his parents. (Rohner, 1986; Tezcan, 2015, referenced in).

A person's level of self-efficacy may be measured by their level of self-confidence, their ability to develop clear and clear comfortable relationships in social contacts, and their belief that they will be successful in the task that they will undertake. According to Orun (2010), the term "self-efficacy" refers to a person's belief that they are unable to fulfill their own demands in the midst of the rush and bustle of everyday life, that they lack the power to fight, and that they are unable to deal with issues.

Because of this, a youngster who believes that he is being rejected by his parents may lose his life commitment, become unable to feed on his ambitions, and experience a decline in drive to achieve these goals while maintaining a feeling of self-efficacy. A person's mental health suffers when they are unable to fully understand who they are as an individual.

3.2.6. Inconsistency in Emotional State

People who are described as having "emotional consistency" according to the PAR theory are those who do not go through frequent shifts in their mood, who are able to maintain their composure despite the hectic pace of everyday life, who are resilient in the face of adversity, and who respond to situations with composure and sensitivity rather than becoming anxious or

irrational. These individuals, who do not experience many changes in their overall mood, do not have difficulties returning to their usual routines and adjusting, even if they endure tensions and stressful circumstances (Rohner, 1986). This is because they do not experience as many swings in their general mood. On the other side, it has been observed that persons who suffer emotional inconsistency are those who get irritated and upset when their "daily routines" are broken, as well as if the events they go through do not proceed as they had intended. According to Rohner & Rohner (1986), people who experience major depression are capable of displaying an instantaneous hostile and furious attitude while they are in a pleasant attitude.

This attribute of personality is connected, in a way, to the stability that is shown by parents in the manner in which they interact with their offspring. Emotional constancy may be defined as the harmony that a person displays in the environment in which he lives, in the difficulties that are not too significant, and in the challenging circumstances that he is presented with. Inconsistency may be defined as the individual's incapacity to adjust to new circumstances, to stretch and strain themselves. According to Rohner (1986), who was mentioned in Tezcan (2015), this trait was more prevalent in persons who had been disapproved of by their parents.

According to the parental acceptance/rejection theory, in light of this information and based on this information, parental acceptance/rejection predicts psychological adjustment, and the implicit variable of psychological adjustment is hostility, addiction, negative self-esteem, negative self-efficacy, emotional unresponsiveness, and emotional inconsistency. as well as unfavorable aspects of the worldview.

3.2.7. Negative Perspective on the World

The person's birth, existence, life, and the significance of the environment in which he lives are all seen in a negative light, giving rise to the concept that this phenomenon might be classified as. In this instance, the individual has bad thoughts towards trusting friendship relationships, having expectations, and having friendship interactions. According to Rohner (1986), as described in Tezcan (2015), a person with a positive outlook is the kind of person that does not fear for their safety, has no trouble establishing new acquaintances, and has optimistic aspirations and objectives for their life.

According to Rohner (1986), an individual who has a pessimistic outlook on the world views his life and the world around him as a place filled with uncertain, risky, potentially harmful, and even life-threatening circumstances.

Both the interpersonal acceptance-rejection theory and the personality theory have traditionally centered their attention on two overarching concerns. To begin, are children's impressions of being accepted or rejected by their parents and other related persons the same across various sociocultural systems, racial or ethnic groupings, genders, and other categories of individuals, and are their responses to this acceptance and rejection the same as well? The second question is: What are the impacts and extensions of being accepted or rejected beginning in childhood? (2016) (Rohner)

In conclusion, in light of all of this knowledge, the following is the best way to describe it. According to Rohner (2015), feeling rejected by one's parents may lead to a variety of personality issues in addition to addiction. These characteristics include an inability to respond emotionally, anger and aggressiveness, self-confidence, self-perception, self-esteem, negative self-esteem, negative self-efficacy, emotional inconsistency, and a pessimistic outlook on the world.

CHAPTER 4

THE SYNDROME OF REJECTION

4.1. The Scars Left Behind by Criticism in Our Lives

It opens up a lot of scars that were generated by the notion being rejected when they were young. These factors contribute to the maturation of at least one negative feeling, including emotional numbness, the avoidance of love, hate, violence, apathy, and neglect.

According to Rohner (2014), having a sense of being rejected in childhood might lead to an uneasy and insecure connection. According to Rohner and Khaleque (2010), children who have anxious and insecure attachments are more likely to create dependent connections with their parents in order to increase their chances of being loved. These children also have higher expectations about favorable approach and acceptance from their caregivers. According to Rohner and Khaleque (2010), this scenario may be perceived in both adolescents and adults as a persistent yearning for the approval of the people they esteem and an emotional anticipation on their part. It is possible for one to experience anger, violence, passive aggression, difficulty in impulse regulation, grudges, a lack of empathy, emotional coldness, a negative worldview, poor self-

esteem, low sense of competence, and emotional swings as a consequence of seeing that they have been rejected. According to Rohner and Khaleque (2010), some children may exhibit dependent behaviors, emotional inconsistencies, low levels of self-esteem and self-efficacy, as well as a negative worldview in their interpersonal connections.

In addition, it has been suggested that having one's feelings of rejection validated during childhood may lead to disruptions in one's mental schemas at the level of social cognition (expectations and beliefs regarding oneself and others that one values, regarding their interpersonal relationships, and regarding their life), which in turn may have a negative impact on one's sensitivity to rejection as an adult (Downey & Feldman, 1996).

As a consequence of this, we may argue that the physical and emotional scars created by the perceived rejection in infancy have a detrimental impact on the individual's expectations and beliefs, relationships and actions in adulthood, and that they may have a pessimistic outlook on the world.

4.1.1. Failure

According to Rafaeli et al. (2018), this schema is connected to the idea that the individual is now unsuccessful or will be unsuccessful in the future and that he is insufficient in comparison to his peers in areas that need achievement such as education, sports, and employment. This individual believes that everyone will do a better job at his work than he will, and that he will never be able to accomplish it himself (Roediger, 2015). According to Young et al. (2013), it involves holding thoughts such as being unsuccessful, inept, uneducated, and unable.

These individuals may have suffered from a learning disorder, attention deficit disorder, or coordination disorder when they were younger. Furthermore, they may not have been taught the necessary discipline to learn how to read, were given the labels of "lazy" and "incompetent" and stopped trying as a result. Additionally, their performance may have been criticized by their parents and negatively impacted their relationship with their siblings. may have felt that he would not be able to live up to the expectations set by his extremely successful parents; as a result, he gave up attempting to compete with them (Young & Klosko, 2018). He may have assumed that he would not be able to attain the standards that his parents had set for themselves. In a way, the thought that he cannot achieve in all of his relationships and activities may have been labeled by him as something that is negative and unsuccessful.

A stable bond, independence, a feeling of success and identity, realistic limits, spontaneity, and play are some of the fundamental psychological requirements that need to be provided by parents throughout childhood, according to the schema therapy approach. If these demands are not addressed, it may lead to the development of rigid schemas that are difficult to alter. The failure schema is the antithesis of the success schema. This framework consists of the fundamental concepts that determine the patterns of interpersonal relationships. In this context, there are 18 early maladaptive schemas, which include failure, vulnerability to illness and harm, dependency/inability, intimacy/underdeveloped self, abandonment, submissiveness, negativity/pessimism, vindictiveness, inadequate self-control, approval-seeking, high standards, punitiveness, and self-sacrifice (Young et al., 2009). According to Louis et al. (2018), each of these schema domains correlates to fundamental childhood emotional needs that are either not supplied by parent-caregivers or are addressed to an excessive degree. For instance, a kid who develops a failure schema in this manner gives birth to the idea that he will always be rejected in interpersonal connections, in person-to-be-married relationships, in friend group surroundings, and in corporate life, and that he will fail as a consequence of these interactions. Another example would be that a child who develops a failure schema in this manner gives rise to the belief that he would always fail. According to the parental rejection hypothesis, the formation of this schema region may be caused by the parents' high expectations for abilities that are inappropriate for the child's age, overprotective attitudes, or inability to encourage the child's accomplishment.

They react with animosity, jealousy, or restricted conduct in response to what they perceive to be a rejection or threat of rejection on the part of the person with whom they are speaking. According to Creasey-McInnis (2001), page 89, people with these kinds of qualities are also thought to suffer from social anxiety, which may help explain why they are unable to form deep connections. These failures demonstrate that there are discoveries in the scientific literature that are connected to their failures in the process of the development of social anxiety. According to the DSM-IV diagnostic classification system, social anxiety is defined as avoidance or distress in situations where an action has taken place, which disrupts the person's normal daily activities, occupational or educational functionality, social activities, or interpersonal relationships (First, Frances, Pincus, 1999, p. 167). This definition was developed by researchers First, Frances, and Pincus. For instance, individuals have extreme feelings of shame, embarrassment, and anxiety if they are forced to dine in public locations, make phone calls, use public restrooms, write their names or sign in front of other people (Ozturk, 2002, p.355). We may argue that as a consequence of such activities, he develops the conviction that he has failed, and he experiences avoidance or anxiety as a result of this view.

In addition, it has been shown that people who suffer from social anxiety are very sensitive to the pain and rejection they experience in their interpersonal connections. One of these parallels is that people who suffer from social anxiety have a considerable fear of making errors in settings that involve social interaction and performance, and even the tiniest mistake is seen as inadequacy or failure. Another similarity is that those who suffer from generalized anxiety disorder also have these commonalities. However, it was shown that persons who avoided relationship commitment and those who avoided avoidant attachment due to the fear of being rejected had a high rate of relationship failure. Both of these factors contributed to relationship failure.

In conclusion, the development of a failure schema in a kid is caused by the family's rejection of the child as an individual. The target of this con is led to feel that he lacks essential qualities, that he is not complete, that he has failed in the past, and that he will continue to fail at whatever job he does in the future. According to Young, Klosko, and Weishaar (2003), when a person compares themselves to the individuals in their immediate environment, they experience feelings of incompetence in their task and feelings of humiliation over their shortcomings. However, it is conceivable for this schema to emerge in households in which the parents have very high expectations for their children and regularly criticize them or draw comparisons between their children and other children in the family (Young & Klosko, 1993).

It is speculated that a person's upbringing may have a role in the development of avoidant personality disorder (APD). Being continually ridiculed and rejected by his family, siblings, or friends causes him to have an exceptionally high desire for the things they want to accomplish; nevertheless, he pulls back or does not want to attain it at all because he is afraid that he will not be successful (Zorlu, 2013).

People with a fixed mentality who fall in love and who are rejected suffer the unpleasant impacts of rejection for a longer period of time, according to the findings of a number of research conducted by Carol Dweck and Lauren Howe of Stanford University. (<https://listelist.com/rejection-fear>) Participants who felt that individuals would not change saw rejection as a failure due to their own personal inadequacies, rather than believing that rejection may be a chance for good development or progress.

It originates in maladaptive schemas such as retreat, not continuing education, not taking chances, perfectionism, and underestimating the success of others. Failure is the belief that the rejection schema provides, accepting simpler jobs than you can perform, and surrendering to your fate.

4.1.2. Insecurity

People who were brought up by parents who rejected them as children have a heightened feeling of loneliness and uncertainty. People who were brought up by parents who rejected them throughout their infancy develop a feeling of isolation and insecurity as adults. Later in adulthood, they continue their lives as persons who are easily harmed by the negatives that they encounter in relationships and feel depression as a result of this vulnerability.

According to Roediger (2015), insecurity is connected to the feeling of being unable to fulfill a desire for connection. The concept that one's demands for security, constancy, care, empathy, sharing of emotions, acceptance, and respect would not be satisfied, in a manner, promotes the sensation that one is unsafe and unprotected.

On the other hand, when seen from the perspective of the rejecting parents, an insecure schema region is generated. According to Roediger (2015), this schema involves the belief that other people are harmful and will cause the individual to be injured. The individual is under the impression that he would be mistreated by other people, including being injured, humiliated, lied to, and tricked. According to Rafaeli et al. (2018), these individuals feel that the majority of the damage they have sustained was either perpetrated on purpose or was the result of negligent behavior. According to Erkan and Toran (2004), parents who reject their children lead to the development of qualities in their offspring that have a detrimental impact on their lives, such as insecurity and abstention.

It is well known that insecure attachment patterns in infancy are linked to lower levels of life satisfaction as well as increased rates of social (for example, loneliness) and psychiatric issues (Akdogan, 2017; Levy and Johnson, 2019; Mathes et al., 2020; Mikulincer and Nachshon 1991; Wei et al., 2005). Because their early caregivers responded to physical symptoms rather than emotional symptoms, adults who have an insecure attachment style and poor emotional regulation (Kawamoto, 2020) cause somatic symptoms (self., attachment anxiety) such as fibromyalgia, which describes the experience of chronic pain in adulthood with no medical cause. This is because these adults learned that their early caregivers prioritized physical symptoms over emotional symptoms. (Lin and colleagues, 2020; Williams (2017)).

People who are sensitive to rejection are often persons who have a poor opinion of themselves and approval-seeking schema as a result of their insecurity. This makes them more likely to feel hurt when they are rejected. The notion that he does not belong to a group that he considers to be distinct from the others is reflected in his use of the mistrust schema. We may state

that this schema refers to a negative perspective of others and that individuals who have these schemas perceive others as rejecting since it involves the concept that other people will not accept the person as he is. People who subscribe to the mistrust schema have the mindset that they are unique from other people and do not, as a result, belong to a group or community. (Clark & Wells, 1995: 69-93; Rapee & Heimberg, 1997: 741-754). They assume that these persons regard themselves as more inadequate than others and worry that they will not be accepted by others because of their inadequacies.

According to Bowlby's theory of attachment, the mental models that children form about themselves and their relationships are the expectations that they have about whether or not other people would reject them. When an individual who cares for themselves gives a negative answer to these expectations, the individual creates a model based on insecurity and anxiety in response to the situation. According to Downey and Feldman (1996), as a result of this circumstance, the individuals involved will have tremendous emotional upheaval in their future relationships and will exhibit distrustful attitudes.

According to research conducted by Purdie and Downey (2000), high levels of rejection sensitivity are linked to increased degrees of both insecurity and aggression in romantic relationships. People who are very sensitive to being rejected struggle with trust issues. According to Creasey and Melnnis (2001), people who have a high rejection sensitivity are more likely to mistrust their relationships because they see a definite and unmistakable rejection in the conduct of their partners, even if the behavior is ambiguous.

This schema region is evident in situations in which parents do not respect the child's space and abuse it physically, verbally, or sexually (Young, Klosko, & Weishaar, 2003) or in situations in which they often lie (Young & Klosko, 1993). (Rafaeli, Bernstein, & Young, 2011) People who have schemas in this area have the belief that they will be mistreated and abused by others despite the fact that there is no evidence to support this assumption.

People who are highly sensitive to the rejection of others, to whom they attribute meaning, see a definite and clear rejection in the behavior of their partner, even if it is vague. Because of the negative and negative thought system that comes with insecurity, these people respond to rejection threats with hostility, decreased support, controlling, and controlled behaviors. (Creasey and Melnis, 2001). [Creasey and Melnis, 2001].

According to research conducted by Purdie and Downey (2000), high levels of rejection sensitivity are linked to increased degrees of both insecurity and aggression in romantic relationships.

As a consequence of this, Erikson (1998) said that there would be a sense of uneasiness when the fundamental requirements of the infant are not satisfied. However, children whose parents display a pattern of rejection throughout their upbringing will develop attachment patterns that are insecure, will be hypersensitive to being rejected, and will carry this insecurity into their adult relationships. If the person providing care for themselves gives a negative reaction, then that person will construct a model that is built on insecurity and worry. In addition, those who suffer from anxious attachment are said to have an overwhelming desire to develop closeness, to see the proximity of their partner as inadequate, and to mistrust him (Hazan & Shaver, 1987).

4.1.3. Belief that One Is Not Worthy

Experiences of rejection and feelings of worthlessness may produce unpleasant thoughts that affect a person's well-being (Romero - Canyas, Downey, Berenson, Ayduk, & Kang, 2010; Saricam et al., 2012; Staebler, Helbing, Rosenbach, & Renneberg, 2011; Romero - Canyas, et al., 2012).

A person will unconsciously assign an existing belief a name, such as "the belief that I am worthless," and call it by that name. A unique interpretation of beliefs emerges from this. The subconscious has repercussions for daily living that are influenced by a wide variety of ideas and worldviews. The individual's subconscious has an expectation that they will carry out their behaviors in the belief dimension of their life. The way one feels is a reflection of their beliefs. The individual comes to the conscious realization by feeling that he is useless (Uran, 2018).

Our beliefs serve as the fundamental building blocks of our subconscious. The concepts and propositions that are accepted unconsciously as being true are referred to as beliefs. Uran presents the idea that there is no value to anything as a basic principle. According to him, these beliefs are what produce the myriad of sub beliefs that are tied to him.

"If I have no value, then I am a coward,"

"If I have no value, then I am a coward,"

"Because no one appreciates me, I'm not worth anything."

There are a great number of beliefs like this. According to Uran (2018), this might result in the creation of new behavioral models and the enhancement of existing ones.

The development of people' abilities to conceal their own worthlessness takes place outside of their conscious awareness. Concealment and secrecy are the goals of a variety of behavior patterns that seem very distinct to the naked eye. According to Uran, the fundamental mechanism is of the idea that any verbal and behavioral attitude, which is recognized at the subconscious level of behavior, cognition, and emotion, may establish a perception of worthlessness in a person. This belief can then be perpetuated by the individual. However, according to Butler and Matthews (1983), persons who are raised in homes where there is a lot of conflict and conflict resolution are more likely to see ambiguity as dangerous. According to Rohner (2004), a youngster who has the perception that they are being rejected by their parents will have skewed images of themselves. According to Rohner et al.'s research from 2005, people have a tendency to seek out settings or experiences that correspond to their mental representations and to avoid situations that do not correspond to their mental representations.

In this context, the distinction between sensation and belief is not an insignificant one. A sensation is a bodily experience that may be felt in our bodies. To put it another way, it is the physical manifestation of a shift in one's mental state. Faith is a state that cannot be altered. The fact that feelings and beliefs may both be altered is the characteristic that most clearly differentiates the two. To put it another way, feelings might change while beliefs remain constant (Uran, 2018).

As a consequence of this, when we are rejected or excluded, this desire is thwarted, and our enjoyment is hindered since we experience feelings of isolation. This person has a terrible feeling about themselves as a result of the rejecting conduct. The conclusion that he is not appreciated and that he is excluded may be reached as a result of his conduct that rejects others. In this state of mind, the sense of dread is activated in the subconscious mind, which causes it to be experienced as an unpleasant sensation throughout the body. The presence of this uncomfortable sensation in the body indicates that a danger is being perceived. This, in turn, may lead the individual to believe that they are worthless, which is regarded as rejection. This, in turn, may cause the individual to become introverted and to be alone from the social environment. This, in turn, may diminish the likelihood of socialization within their relationships. This may also cause intrafamilial, bilateral, and interpersonal relationships to worsen. When seen from this angle, we may state that the ambiguities that arise when rejection, ignorance, or psychological exclusion are understood as behavioral or discursive may cause us to conclude that we have no value since it is possible for us to be led to this conclusion.

4.1.4. Being Ignored or Excluded Completely

According to Williams (2007) and Aydin (2008), in ostracism, it is common for there to be no link between the person who is being excluded and the individual or group that is engaging in the excluding behavior. The group or the individual in question is unaware of the person they have chosen to exclude. Because of this, it is completely out of the question for the group to respond badly to the person who has been excluded from the group or to publicly state that they do not wish to include this person in the group.

Therefore, when seen from this angle, ostracism is often unclear to the one who is the target of verbally or behaviorally hostile treatment. In many cases, the person who is being excluded does not know if this is the case or why. Psychological exclusion, which may be witnessed in a variety of ways such as avoiding eye contact with the excluded person or not answering vocally, generates a sensation of being neglected, disregarded, or distant from oneself (Williams, Govan, Croker, Tyanan, Cruickshank, & Lam, 2002). Psychological exclusion can be noticed in a variety of ways such as avoiding eye contact with the excluded individual or not replying orally.

Excluded persons may have the thought that their present condition will not improve or that they are unable to form new connections within the context of their current relationship status if they are subject to psychological exclusion, which occurs when individuals are neglected and virtually ignored. Because of this, individuals may have the impression that they are unable to develop meaningful relationships with other people. According to Molden, Lucas, Gardner, Dean, and Knowles (2009), people who experience psychological exclusion feel pain because they are unable to get unambiguous positive feedback from the people around them in their interactions.

According to Leary (2005), ostracism is a kind of rejection that entails isolating the individual who is being excluded from the group that is engaging in the exclusionary behavior. When someone is subjected to psychological exclusion, they are treated as if they do not exist.

When viewed from this perspective, it's possible that psychological exclusion could be one of the reasons why an individual is completely rejected or not preferred, withdraws or closes himself off in their relationships in later adulthood, stays away, is embarrassed or cannot make eye contact, the coldness in male-female relations, and the distance between parents. In this particular setting, I believe that it would be useful to have a particular emphasis on psychological marginalization.

Ostracism poses a greater risk to an individual's ability to maintain a healthy sense of self-worth, according to a number of studies. Ostracism is a kind of social exclusion that conveys the message that the target individual is so unimportant that it is pointless to respond to their actions.

The psychological exclusion model that was created by Williams proposes that different forms of exclusion may be categorized using certain criteria. The terms "visibility," "motivation," "quantity," and "clarity" are used to describe these characteristics. There are three aspects of exclusion that are taken into consideration when discussing visibility: physical, social, and virtual. Through concrete and visible forms of behavior such as physical exclusion, expulsion, and exile; through more ambiguous forms of behavior such as not making eye contact with the target person, and not speaking; and through behaviors on virtual communication tools such as not responding to phones, messages, and e-mails. Exclusion can take place in any of these ways.

The model developed by Williams classified the reasons individuals exclude others into one of three categories. The first factor is the traits of the object of the exclusion that are considered to be socially unacceptable. The second factor is the qualities of the source of the exclusion, such as unstable connection, which contribute to an increased propensity to exclude other people. Third, there are occasions in which social variables do not allow for any other sort of conduct (for instance, a person who is upset with their spouse in public may want to exclude him since they cannot fight in public), but there are also situations in which social factors do allow for any other form of behavior.

In addition, Williams (2001; 2009) cites four fundamental wants that are negatively affected by the experience of being excluded: (1) the need to belong is defined as the desire to be accepted into groups and relationships, which is universally present in all individuals, and it is fairly understandably injured by the experience of being excluded. (2) the need for autonomy is described as the need to have control over one's environment and one's life. (2) The need for a healthy sense of self-esteem is badly impacted when a person is excluded from their social group because it leads them to point the finger at themselves for the reasons they are not accepted by others. (3) The need of people to see their social environment as being manageable and predictable is the root cause of the demand for control that they have. The individual feels as if he has lost control of the situation when they are excluded, and the uncertainty over whether or not they will be allowed back into the social context develops a feeling of danger in them. (4) The inclination of humans to ascribe a meaning, worth, and significance to their own life is what gives birth to the demand for meaningful existence; nevertheless, positive evaluations of a person's existence may be harmed when that individual is excluded from certain social situations. These four fundamental

needs are influenced to varying degrees by the various sorts of exclusion, and distinct reactions come about on the behavioral, emotional, and cognitive levels depending on which need is seen as being more in jeopardy. There have been numerous reports showing the fear of exclusion has a detrimental impact on these four requirements of participants (for example, Abrams et al., 2011; Chernyak & Zayas, 2010; Kaya, 2012; Williams et al., 2002; Zadro, Boland, & Richardson, 2006; Zadro, Williams and Richardson, 2004). These findings have been found in a variety of research.

4.1.5. Concept of Belonging (One of Exclusion)

A person's sense of belonging to a society, a community, a group, etc., in order to form a positive view of their identity, is an aspect that falls within the "belonging" category and is one of the steps in Maslow's hierarchy of needs. Belonging may also be described as adoption, a sense of belonging, or integration. This happens through identifying it with an event or phenomena such as Belonging can also be defined as adoption, a feeling of belonging, or integration.

According to Altekin (2001:28), an individual's feeling of belonging may be traced back to their infancy and is linked to the relationship that a newborn has with its mother during this time.

Many social psychologists are of the belief that in order for a person to feel more a part of a community, it is beneficial for that individual to involve himself in an existing group.

When a person has strong indirect or direct relationships with the social environment that surrounds them, they are more likely to have a strong sense of belonging to that community. On the one hand, a person's direct feeling of belonging in themselves is created by the social context in which they were born; on the other hand, this sense of belonging is contingent upon the fully aware decisions made by the individual as a social being. ethnicity, religion, place of origin, and other such things. There is a dimension of belonging that can be updated and variably shaped by the conscious preferences of the individual in the form of education, politics, economic environments, or social groups included in certain age categories (Alptekin; 20-21: 2011). While the individual's belonging is formed spontaneously with some innate characteristics such as, there is also a dimension of belonging that can be formed spontaneously with some innate characteristics such as.

Not being accepted as a word, being looked down upon, being relegated to the background, not being liked, and not being included in a setting or a group are all examples of what it means to be excluded. According to Gordon (1999: 150), the phrase "exclusion" is a term that refers to the

process by which people or families are deprived of either resources or social relationships with the greater community or society. In other words, exclusion is a term that relates to the term "exclude." In addition, the idea of social exclusion encompasses biases and stigmatizations that are ascribed to individuals (Semerci, 2011: 4). This structure is what affects a person's feeling of belonging and membership in a group, and it is dependent on a person's ideas of what it means to be included in a society and what it means to be excluded from a society (Bolukbasi, 2008: 12).

The state of an individual's sense of belonging to a group is a condition that has an effect on how that person conducts their life. As a result, the urge to belong is something that every person works hard to fulfill. On the other hand, the importance of not being bound to a certain location cannot be overstated. The most complicated feeling that an individual may have been that of belonging to a group. "On the one hand, the human spirit enjoys the feeling of freedom. On the other hand, the human soul searches for a branch to cling to. As long as he can maintain his grip, he has a sense of security" (Gunes, 2018:11).

The urge to feel like one is part of a group is considered by some thinkers to be the most fundamental need of the person. Abraham Maslow and Erik Erikson are two of these thinkers that stand out in particular. According to Maslow, the most significant time in one's life when the feeling of belonging emerges to the forefront is during adolescence. Being a part of a community or a group satisfies the third level of Maslow's hierarchy of needs, which is the need for a feeling of belonging (Yurtdas, 2018). This level comes after the physiological and the safety needs. According to Maslow, a person feels a sense of belonging throughout adolescence.

It is clear that the individual's feeling of belonging plays a significant role in the development processes that occur from childhood into adulthood. If a person does not experience this emotion, it is possible that their inner world will become unsettled, and they will not find satisfaction in the relationships they have with other people.

In France during the 1960s, the term "exclusion" referred to persons who were mentally or physically challenged, criminals, ill or old people who need care, mistreated children, drug addicts, people who were suicidal, single parents, immigrants, novelists, immigrants, families with issues, and families with problems. persons who are marginal and asocial as well as those who are in other social incompatibilities have been placed in the literature as groups who are driven out of society due to differences that are mostly caused by economic considerations (Copuroglu and Mengi, 2014: 609).

According to Baumeister and Leary (1995) and Saricam, Gencdogan and Erozkhan (2012), one of the primary determinants of fulfilling the desire for belonging and love is contributing to the formation of good interpersonal relationships. This is one of the key factors that contributes to the satisfaction of the need for love. Because man is a biopsychosocial entity, it is his responsibility to ensure that he satisfies his fundamental requirements throughout his life in order to maintain a healthy life cycle. According to Baumeister and Leary (1995), Teneva and Lemay (2020), and Uziel, Seemann and Schmidt-Barad (2020), the desire for love and belonging is one of the most essential requirements for meeting these needs. When it comes to sating the fundamental need for love and belonging, it is essential to keep up deep social relationships with people, since these connections impact emotions, ideas, and actions.

However, the majority of the research that has been done on the psychological factors that are supposed to be successful in the backdrop of the difference in feelings of loneliness that occur as a consequence of not satisfying the desire for belonging has been done in the form of bilateral relationships. These studies have been done because it is assumed that these factors are effective in explaining the difference.

uncovered via the examination of. According to the findings of a research conducted by Demir et al. (2005), teenagers in our nation prefer their friends over their families since the former causes them to feel less pressure, while the latter allows them to be more comfortable. It has been shown that teenagers are more able to receive approbation from their peers than they are from their parents (Yorukoglu, 1996). Peer groups help adolescents develop a feeling of belonging, which is an important step in the process of socialization.

Being rejected or excluded from a group may make a person feel as if they do not belong, which can have a significant impact on the individual's way of life. As a consequence, having a feeling of belonging is an absolute need for human existence. Every action that person does in order to directly fulfill his wants is, in essence, a step made in the direction of forming the foundation of social life. is the one to take. We might argue that the circumstance of exclusion, rejection, and the failure to satisfy the requirements of individuals to develop social interactions is the inhibition of belonging. This is because these things prevent people from feeling like they belong anywhere.

4.1.6. Loneliness

In general, the definitions of loneliness that have been produced by researchers emphasize that it is a painful and difficult process. Some often equate feeling lonely with being alone themselves, yet it is also possible for someone to feel lonely even when they are surrounded by other people. According to Bulus (1997), the most fundamental aspect that determines whether a person suffers from loneliness is the insufficiency of the individual's social ties with others and the low level of enjoyment from such relationships.

Williams (1983) described loneliness as the painful awareness that individuals feel as a consequence of wanting to have close relationships with others but not being able to attain these close relationships that they seek. Loneliness may be alleviated by reaching out to others and cultivating meaningful connections with others. To put it another way, loneliness is a process that develops when one's desire for connection is not satisfied and goes unfulfilled.

Pepleu and Perlman (1984) described loneliness as the disparity between the social connections an individual has and the social ties he craves, as well as the unsettling emotion that arises as a consequence of the understanding that this condition makes in the person. Loneliness is a distressing feeling that occurs as a result of the realization that this circumstance creates in the person.

On the other hand, while defining loneliness, Rook (1984) placed an emphasis on the many elements that contribute to it. According to him, an individual is in a painful state of loneliness when he or she is afraid of being misunderstood by other people, when he or she is afraid of being rejected by others, when he or she believes that he or she is excluded or will be excluded, and when he or she is unable to find social partners to relieve his or her loneliness.

According to de Jong Gierveld (1998), the development process of loneliness is a condition that occurs due to the huge gap between the social ties persons have and the social interactions they seek, and it is caused by the individual's sense of inadequacy in creating intimate relationships. Loneliness is a situation that arises owing to the vast difference between the social relations individuals have and the social relations they desire.

It is believed that this deficiency in the individual is the reason why he prefers to be alone, why he is reluctant to meet new people, why he experiences a decrease in his motivation, and why he is unable to find a friend with whom he can share his ideas and feelings. All of these factors are

effective in the development of the feeling of loneliness that the individual experiences (Cakil, 1998; Yaparel 1984).

There are six different types of connections that, in accordance with the idea of emotional and social isolation, contribute significantly to the development of loneliness. According to Michela, Peplau, and Weeks (1982), one of these associations is the fear of being rejected.

Some researchers, particularly those who do not spend a significant amount of time with their families, the death of a parent, or the feeling of being rejected might lead to feelings of loneliness, according to their findings (Celen, 2007).

According to Kaya (2007), it is believed that the roots of loneliness are built in childhood and even in infancy. The urge for closeness mainly arises in infancy, and this circumstance also impacts adulthood. If the kid believes that he will not be able to get assistance when he needs it if he is excluded or rejected, then he may have difficulties in the future coping with the damaging repercussions of sentiments such as helplessness and loneliness (Horney, 1997; as quoted in Saricam, 2011).

Loneliness is supposed to be the outcome of an individual's failure to satisfy their desire for closeness with other people to the fullest extent possible, as proposed by the psychodynamic method. In other words, if he is unable to supply the individual with a sense of connection and sharing, the person may experience feelings of hopelessness and loneliness (Gectan, 2005).

One of the conclusions that can be drawn from the outcomes of the study that was conducted on loneliness in general is that there is a connection between the sensitivity to rejection and the experience of being lonely. According to Gonzaga, Keltner, Londahl, and Smith (2001), rejection is a phenomenon that damages connections and lowers the sense of trust. This causes people to separate themselves from each other, which in turn leads to the deterioration of social interactions and feeds the feeling of loneliness. From this vantage point, it is believed that there may be a connection between being sensitive to being rejected and experiencing feelings of isolation. However, it is also believed that there is a connection between the sensitivity to rejection, loneliness, and the condition known as alexithymia, which is also known as emotional blindness.

In light of their study, Michela, Peplau, and Weeks (1982) also provided a list of the factors that contribute to feelings of isolation. They discovered that there are internal and external, mutable and immutable factors that contribute to feelings of isolation. These:

- Pessimism.
- The dread of being turned down.
- Don't put any effort into it.
- Misfortune.
- Ignorance, which results in a lack of capacity to develop social interactions.
- Shyness.
- An unattractive or unattractive appearance.
- Other connections and groups (while this circumstance arises outside to the individual, it speaks to the views of others toward the person who is suffering loneliness).
- The worries that other people have.
- Circumstances that lack a personal element, such as when an individual interacts with other people in an impersonal way.
- A lack of available opportunities.
- The hesitation of other people.
- Personality that lacks empathy.

This notion, which has a detrimental impact on people's mental health, may be connected to other concepts, given that rejected individuals generate issues in communication and lead the person to remove himself from others and become lonely. Additionally, this thought causes the individual to withdraw from others and become isolated.

According to Rocakch (2004), the following are some of the negative repercussions that being lonely may have on a person (Yilmaz & Karakurt, 2012). These:

- People isolate themselves from other people as a defense mechanism against feeling lonely. This inhibits the development of meaningful interpersonal bonds.

- There is a decline in effectiveness in one's interactions with other people. The bond between them can no longer be maintained. Loneliness, which may lead to destructive feelings

like envy, is harmful to interpersonal connections. If a person is lonely and has a strong need for love, he or she may try too hard to hold on to that love once it is found, which might lead to unfavorable outcomes.

- Loneliness has the potential to divert attention and inhibit the effective use of one's energies. It has the potential to get in the way of creative thinking.

- When the sensation of loneliness is not addressed, the individual's experience of life becomes more dominated by feelings of isolation.

- The experience of loneliness contributes to the development of maladaptive mental patterns in the individual. These ideas might cause the individual to become less functioning by urging him to make rash and unwise choices about his life. In this regard, disordered ideas that may be brought on by feelings of isolation may have a bad impact on an individual's professional life, marital life, social life, and even their sexual life.

- Loneliness may lead a person to become sensitive or inflexible in their thinking.

- It causes emotional scars, and the sense of having them is excruciating.

It has been argued that loneliness is both a cause of and a factor in a variety of other conditions and states. For instance, according to the findings of certain research, people who have poor self-esteem tend to be more introverted and choose the company of themselves above other people when it comes to social or interpersonal connections (Inanc & Yerlikaya, 2008). On the other hand, due to the fact that there are many similarities between loneliness and depression, some experts have regarded the former to be a subtype of the latter.

In conclusion, in light of the facts presented here, it can be said that many of the things that generate feelings of isolation are elements that have an effect on the person. Among them, we may include the idea that the person in question is disregarded, rejected, or excluded. Because it is both a wide term and a complex topic, loneliness consists of a number of different components. It has been argued that these ideas have a detrimental effect on the psychological well-being of humans. When seen from this angle, it is possible to claim that rejection, along with a wide variety of other actions, plays a part in determining the detrimental consequences that individuals have on mental health.

4.1.6.1 A Categorization of Different Types of Loneliness

Some scholars have categorized the experience of loneliness under a variety of categories and subheadings. These:

Complete Isolation

The type of loneliness that comes along with despair is what we mean here. The symptoms of sadness may make loneliness seem much more intense and upsetting than it already does. The intensity of the depression is directly correlated to the level of isolation experienced. Typical symptoms of depression include feelings of helplessness and melancholy, difficulty concentrating, disturbed eating and sleeping patterns, and even thoughts of ending one's own life. Even if it is obvious that some kind of action is required in this scenario, mental assistance has to be sought out as soon as feasible (Yildirim 2002).

Loneliness and One's Social Standing

When you move to a new location or community, you may experience a different sort of loneliness than you were used to. This occurs when people put themselves in unfamiliar settings, such as relocating to a new city or nation, starting at a new school, or switching careers. It is not regarded an issue if someone feels lonely for a short period of time due to their social standing; nevertheless, this feeling should go away once some time has passed. According to Yahyaoglu (2007), individuals experience discomfort when they are permanently and long-term lonely as a result of their social standing.

A State of Emotional Isolation

Loneliness is the emotional state that a person experiences when his or her expectations of life and of themselves are not fulfilled, despite the fact that the individual lives in an environment that is otherwise typical. Major letdown the cause for this letdown is due to the expectations and their values, which were not met. People have good physical and mental health, but when their loneliness persists for an extended period of time, it may wreak havoc on their relationship with the spiritual world (Yahyaoglu, 2007).

The Unspoken Loneliness

One or more traumatic experiences that a person has been through are the root cause of the individual's hidden loneliness. People who have trouble expressing their unpleasant emotions are more likely to struggle with feelings of loneliness. When observed from the outside, it is difficult

to determine whether or not this is the source of the issue. Changing one's outlook on life, on other people, and on oneself may be a helpful step in the process of overcoming loneliness for the person who is currently going through it. However, according to Yahyaoglu (2007), the transition from hidden to profound loneliness may occur when the former turns into a chronic condition and the latter becomes more severe.

Loneliness of the Triad

The emotional upheaval may be attributed to a certain kind of loneliness. In addition to the symptoms of depression, one may also experience unexpected outbursts of rage and feelings of terror. These symptoms, which seem to be a consequence of the individual's sense of isolation, contribute to the individual's continued sensation of isolation. It's almost like a never-ending cycle. It is really difficult to shake this sensation of isolation when you are by yourself. According to Yildirim (2002), psychotherapy and medical assistance are both crucial.

In conclusion, when all of this evidence is taken into consideration, it becomes clear that many of the elements that induce loneliness are causative and influence people. It is possible to say that people are ignored, excluded, and rejected as a result of this. Because feeling lonely is such a big term and such a prevalent problem, it encompasses many different subcategories. It has been discovered that these ideas have a detrimental impact on the mental health of humans. According to this point of view, examining the adverse impacts of various actions, including rejection, which might have an impact on people's mental health is relevant.

4.2. Identifying Past Pains

It is up to us to define our perceptions whether the words, glances, or acts of other people force us to exhibit certain reactionary emotions or to become inwardly distant and lonely. In many cases, it is proportionate to how we react to old hurts that date back to our infancy.

This suffering builds up over the course of time. Rejection from one's parents, neighbors, social circles, or seniors might be one of the scars that can be produced by such traumatic occurrences in childhood.

The previous hurts, emotions of all this rejection, feeling wounded, furious, angry, worthless, helpless, disregarded, and unsupported are sometimes signals that are not quite clear but that we believe we understand despite the fact that they are not.

A kind of psychologically unhealthy conduct is called rejection. Not just the most visible habits may cause damage that lasts a lifetime. There is a message of rejection underneath each of these acts. It is not usually the case that one only experiences rejection, anguish, and disappointment once. It happens again and over again, as one incident flows into the next. Children are impacted, which has long-term repercussions for the conduct of adults. According to Savage (1999), a person's responses to events at this age are determined by the experiences they have had throughout their lives.

How can we become better at recognizing our own lingering aches and pains? Research conducted by Mary Main, a psychologist at the University of California, Berkeley, and Ruh Goldwyn, an anthropologist at the university. In order to conduct their research on commitment, the researchers placed twelve-month-old infants in a laboratory environment where they were momentarily isolated from their mothers. The purpose of this experiment is to see how newborns react when they first see their moms. The vast majority of newborns communicated that they were relieved to see their mother, showed that they wanted to bond, and actively welcomed their mother's return. However, none of the infants shown any signs of contentment upon seeing their mother, and observers noted that they seemed to be distressed. These infants had evaded their moms by avoiding them, turning their backs on them, or ignoring them, and had successfully made their escape.

Why did they decide to run away from the police? The researcher has come to the conclusion that the solution may be found in the extent to which the mother accepts or rejects the commitment that the kid has made to her. The moms of the infants who didn't want their mothers had consistently turned down their offspring's requests for emotional and physical interaction with them. (Savage, 1999) found that when mothers were removed from their children in the laboratory setting, the youngsters seemed to view the loss of their mother as a rejection on the part of their mother.

In his research, Rohner has looked at a large number of acceptances and rejections. According to him, acceptance is "the warmth, love-support, and approval of the parent," while rejection is "the absence or marked avoidance of warmth and love" (Savage, 1999). Savage offers this definition of acceptance and rejection.

For children to have the perception that they are not loved, cared for, or respected, it is not necessary for the acts that cause these emotions to be communicated explicitly. Even if the

behavior or action does not seem to do any damage to the kid, the most important thing to consider is how this message will affect the child in the long run.

Even stating that you let me down is a severe characterization of the situation. Children who hear this description recall being told that they were not wanted and may feel as if they have let someone down. Some of these ideas remain with us even after we become adults. These ideas may not have been passed down from our parents; Savage (1999) suggests that some of them stretch back as least a century.

The paradigm of remembering the experience of exclusion in research has demonstrated that recalling a prior exclusion memory in the memory of people is effective (for example, Maner, DeWall, Baumeister, and Schaller, 2007; Pickett, Gardner, and Knowles, 2004; Sacco et al., 2012). Recalling a past exclusion memory in the memory of individuals is effective (e.g., Maner, DeWall, Baumeister, and Schaller, 2007).

4.2.1. Anger

According to Turk Dil Kurumu Sozlugu (2017), anger is described as "aggression reaction, anger, kinship, rage, wrath in the face of frustration, hurt or intimidation." This definition is only one example of the many different ways that anger has been characterized by several academics. It is said that "anger includes disturbing objective feelings and an awareness of psychological reactions as a quality of all emotions" in the 1988 edition of the Dictionary of General Concepts in Psychology.

It is clear from the research that researchers consider anger to be an emotion that is triggered in response to upsetting circumstances, such as being blocked, being wronged, being criticized, or perceiving a threat (Bilge and Sayin 1994; Genctan, 1999; Kennedy, 1997; Kisac, 1999; Koknel 1999; Nazik, 2003; Torestad 1990; Ustun and Yavuzarslan 1995).

Anger is regarded to be connected to the influence that attitudes shown in the family, where the individual's socialization process starts, have on the kid, the sense of the child's acceptance or rejection by the family, and the schemas that are created by family members (Yanik, 2019).

Anger is a stimulating emotion that can also be utilized constructively to create and establish suitable boundaries with individuals who are considered emotionally insecure and who are the major source(s) of rejection in your life (Rising & Rohner, 2020). Anger can be used to set

and build proper boundaries with people who are emotionally insecure and who are the primary source(s) of rejection in your life. It is common for rejected children and adults to have feelings of anger, other unpleasant emotions, a diminished sense of their own ability to cope well with stressful situations, and other negative repercussions of rejection. Because of this, many individuals who are rejected have a tendency to have less emotional stability than those who are accepted. This is especially true when compared to those who are accepted. According to Rohner and Rising (2019), persons who are widely accepted are able to deal with stressful events while maintaining better emotional equilibrium. This might be difficult for them.

According to Khaleque and Rohner (2012), children and adults who suffer considerable rejection or who sense that they have been rejected may feel heightened anger, resentment, and other harmful emotions. Because of the high likelihood of experiencing rage in their personal relationships and throughout their life as a result of persistent rejection, the majority of people who are rejected learn to numb their emotions at the risk of shielding themselves from more hurt.

According to Baltas (2013), individuals experience great rage as a result of the sensation of being rejected, whether by society, family, or friends.

People who endure rejection throughout their youth and into adulthood may have elevated feelings of anger and resentment, which may surface as overtly violent behaviors such as physical or verbal violence, or more covertly hostile behaviors such as pouting, stubbornness, and purposeful procrastination. It's possible that people in this situation struggle to control their feelings. However, the anger that comes from a sense of being rejected may manifest itself in a variety of different ways. (Rising and Rohner, 2020).

According to a study that was compiled by the United States Surgeon General in the year 2001, social exclusion poses a larger threat to young people than do drugs, poverty, or involvement in gangs. Numerous studies have demonstrated that individuals become more aggressive after experiencing even minor rejection, and those who have been rejected have a tendency to try to take the sting out of the experience by inflicting it on 'innocent' people. Shootings in schools, violence against women, and excessive aggressiveness on the part of terminated employees are all on the rise. There is a clear correlation between being rejected and acting aggressively towards others. On the other hand, a significant portion of the anger that results from being rejected is inwardly focused (Some facts about rejection - Earthlings (dunyalilar.org)).

When we become aware of a possible indication of rejection, we are only able to concentrate our attention on other indicators that will strengthen our suspicion of rejection. When

this suspicion of rejection becomes greater, we are more likely to respond angrily to the people and events in our immediate environment (What is Rejection Sensitivity? - Close Relationships (yakiniliskiler.com)).

It's possible that seeking justice for a previous rejection won't be detrimental to one's emotional health or lead to a life of being enslaved by bitterness and resentment.

Many individuals are unaware that they have unresolved anger stemming from experiences of rejection that they had in the past. An individual's mental health might be negatively affected by their history of refusing to pursue justice, which can then lead to persistent anger. According to Rising and Rohner's research from 2020, one of the most important components of effectively managing anger resulting from previous rejections is identifying the erroneous ideas that are a direct result of those rejections and then replacing them with more accurate beliefs.

According to Khaleque and Rohner (2012), children and adults who have suffered considerable rejection beyond a certain point may feel heightened anger, resentment, and other harmful emotions. In other words, we may say that individuals who suffer from excessive rejection lock off many of their emotions in attempt to protect themselves, and the sense of rejection diminishes their ability to deal with rage. This is because excessive rejection causes people to feel that they have no one to turn to for support.

Children and adults who suffer considerable rejection may feel greater anger and resentment, which may emerge as either physical and verbal violence or more passive-aggressively as sulking, stubbornness, and purposeful procrastination. This anger and resentment may lead to aggressive behavior such as physical and verbal aggression or more passive-aggressively as sulking and stubbornness. These kinds of people could also have trouble controlling their hostile sentiments because they worry too much about other people's hostile dreams, fantasies, or imagined behavior toward them. According to Rising and Rohner (2020), defensive independence is connected to both sentiments and acts of rage, which might ultimately result in the rejection of one another.

In point of fact, as a consequence of this, we are able to state that the individual's experience of being rejected is a component that contributes to a reduction in their ability to properly manage with other unpleasant emotions such as rage. Problems with anger control may also originate from inclinations such as the perception of rejection, the rejection of parents or romantic partners during childhood, or the rejection of romantic partners as an adult. When a person believes that they have been rejected, rage may sometimes lead to a cycle of violence as well as other relationship

difficulties. On the other hand, anger is often linked to the experience of feeling rejected, which may result in difficulties such as animosity, resentment, and aggressiveness. Children who have been rejected by their parents may openly express their anger or allow it to build up to the point where it creates an explosion of rage, as they have a tendency to become upset with them as a result of their behavior. Because of this, people get hostile and aggressive, lose their calm, and find that they are unable to achieve their expectations, which causes them to feel stressed and angry.

4.2.2. Dependence

According to Roediger (2009), those who have not been able to totally separate from their families and have not been able to safeguard their own space are more likely to have a damaged autonomy schema region. To put it another way, it has difficulties functioning as an independent person in the traditional sense. According to Rafaeli, Bernstein, and Young (2011), this is often the result of the family either being overprotective of the kid, deficient in their support of the child's independence, or fitting the description of a family that makes choices for the child. This results in the formation of a dependency schema area.

It is observed in circumstances where the parents execute daily duties instead of the kid, present an excessively dictatorial and critical attitude at the points when the child is responsible, do not allow independence (Rafaeli, Bernstein, & Young, 2011), or have no feeling of bonding (Young & Klosko, 1993). Additionally, it is found in cases where the parents do not have a sense of connecting with the child (Young & Klosko, 1993). The individual who has a schema in this area has the notion that he cannot deal with everyday life events and fulfill his own tasks without the support of others, and he has difficulties making his own choices and accepting responsibility (Young, Klosko, & Weishaar, 2003). This causes the individual to have difficulty taking on responsibilities and making decisions for themselves.

It has been hypothesized that children and adults, as well as people, develop personality disorders when they are rejected by their parents. Depending on the type, frequency, and degree of rejection, it may be either dependency or a fragile independence (Khaleque & Rohner, 2002). These include hostility, violence, passive aggression, or issues with anger management.

Dependence; In order for them to feel secure, youngsters look on attachment objects to demonstrate feelings such as being loved and cared for, as well as receiving attention. The fact that they insist on having these sensations proves their dedication. It is clear that young children are

reliant on their parents by the excessive connection they have to their parents, their behaviors (such as whining and sobbing when they go somewhere, and anticipating excessive attention as soon as they see them), and their excessive attachment to their parents. At higher ages, it is exhibited by actions such as taking refuge from their parents, expecting support from their parents, and asking them to stand behind them in times of sorrow, according to Rohner (2005).

According to Rusbult, Martz, and Agnew (1998), the term "addiction" refers to the degree to which an individual requires the presence of the other person with whom he or she is in a relationship or to the extent to which the individual uniquely trusts this specific connection for their future processes.

In this schema area, which is characterized by an excessive attachment to a family member and difficulty in gaining an independent character, research findings indicate that the level of alexithymia is high in individuals who were unable to socialize in the family when they were young and who were incomplete in social environments and interaction (Solmaz, Sayar, Ozer, Ozturk et al. Acar, 2000). This schema area is also characterized by difficulty in gaining an independent character. It has been seen that the insecure attachment types in attachment theory are quite similar to the addiction schema domain.

The experience of being rejected demonstrates that this situation may, in a way, generate a variety of difficulties in people, including issues with the attachment processes. On the other hand, it may be seen that people build dependence schemas of rejection, but autonomy schema regions do not mature. In addition, research conducted by Amato (1994), Dominy (1997), and Heller (1996) has indicated that the perception of parental rejection is linked to the development of psychopathologies such as clinical depression, disorders of drug use and addiction, as well as eating disorders.

According to John Bowlby's (2012) attachment theory, a newborn stress the need to relax by building a connection with the person he or she is near to when he or she is fearful or requires it. This relationship is formed when the child is in need of it. According to attachment theory, for this process to be able to be seen, it is necessary for a danger or an unfavorable condition to first exist. Attachment theory operates on the presumption that a newborn would perish in a setting in which it is not shielded or cared for by an adult. This is the central tenet of the theory.

According to Bowlby (1980), children acquire a sensitivity to rejection when their desires and needs as youngsters are denied by their parents. This circumstance will manifest itself later on in their life, leading them to believe that they will be disapproved of by significant individuals in

circumstances in which they need assistance. Therefore, if they are forced to articulate their requirements, preferences, or emotions, they start to suffer anxiety about doing so. Although this anxiety is brought on by the anticipation of being rejected, it renders the person very sensitive to any and all potential indications regarding rejection. They begin to experience unpleasant feelings because they interpret these rejection indications as signs of purposeful rejection even if the clues are not immediately apparent. Feelings such as pessimism, hatred, and envy are some of the unpleasant emotions that might arise as a result of this shift in perspective.

According to Rohner, Khaleque, and Cournoyer (2005), those who fall into the addiction dimension also have a strong need for continuous acceptance, trust, and support. These individuals are the ones who perceive rejection. (Rohner, Khaleque, & Cournoyer, 2005) Individuals who have experienced rejection are said to have a tendency to be excessively reliant until they have the support they desire, since they can't acquire the help, they want. This idea was developed by Rohner et al. These people, who have been rejected, produce strong anger, aggressiveness, and hostility with addiction, and it also causes drug usage, eating disorders, and addiction disorders. These people are the source of great anger, aggression, and hostility with addiction. In the event that a person's requirements are not satisfied in a timely way, the need for a secure attachment will not be satisfied.

Because of this, people who are very sensitive to rejection tend to exhibit a lot of similar characteristics in their personalities. This might be what we refer to as dependency or defensive independence, depending on the kind and level of rejection that was encountered. According to Feldman and Downey's (1994) research, it is hypothesized that some personality disorders, such as borderline personality disorder and dependent personality disorder, include a component of sensitivity to rejection.

4.2.3. Instability of Emotional State

When we are rejected, we feel physically and emotionally worthless, and we are unable to have a sensible conversation with ourselves as a result. This causes us anguish. Because reason, logic, and common sense, despite their best efforts, are unable to alleviate the anguish that comes from being rejected, the experience is very distressing.

The experience of being rejected has a negative impact on our capacity to utilize reasoning and think in new ways. In one of the experiments, participants were instructed to think back on

reoccurring experiences of being rejected. When their intelligence, short-term memory, reasoning, and decision-making abilities were tested, it was found that these individuals had low performance (Winch, 2015).

The emotional instability that many of us experience as a result of certain rejections, feelings of despair, grief, or helplessness shocks us by rendering us unable to think about anything and rendering us speechless. According to Winch (2015), being rejected in a relationship, particularly one that is romantic, is one of the most efficient ways to confuse our thinking and disturb our positive perceptions.

When one is going through a period of emotional instability, it is not simple to recognize this experience. Also, emotional instability, rage, bad self-feelings, negative self-efficacy, and other negative repercussions of rejection may lead to a decline in the rejected child's or adult's capability to deal with stress. This can be true for both children and adults. Because of this, many individuals who are rejected have a tendency to have a lower level of emotional stability than those who are accepted. According to Rising and Rohner's research from 2020, those who are often exposed to stressful events are more likely to experience feelings of being overwhelmed.

The majority of individuals who are rejected have a tendency to have a lower level of emotional stability than those who are accepted. According to Rohner and Rising (2019), persons who are widely accepted are able to deal with stressful events while maintaining better emotional equilibrium. This might be difficult for them. According to Rohner and Rising (2019), persons who struggle with emotional instability often have a history of major interpersonal rejection and do not have stable connections that can assist them in learning how to learn how to manage their emotions.

Many individuals are unaware of the connection that exists between emotional instability and previous and current experiences of what they believe to be rejection. It is impossible to modify bad beliefs or heal from the suffering connected with emotional instability if one does not have awareness. According to Rohner and Rising (2019), many individuals are ignorant of the ways in which emotional instability hinders not just their own capacity to create safe and healthy connections with other people but also their own capacity to maintain their own emotional well-being. Emotional instability may contribute, in part, to the feelings of rage and pain that are associated with rejection experiences.

Emotional instability can be understood by considering the following six components: 1) frequent changes in emotion; 2) high emotional intensity; 3) rapid rise time at the onset of emotion;

4) slow rate of return to emotional starting point; 5) excessive reactivity to negative psychosocial cues (for example, critical comments from others); and 6) random, chaotic, or rapid cyclical fluctuation of emotion (personal communication, December 2, 2019; RP Rohner).

Emotional instability may be a symptom of a variety of different mental and physical health conditions, including attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, bipolar illness, thyroid diseases, and others (Quinn, 2007).

However, when teenagers' emotional instability (Yilmaz, 2009), risk-taking behaviors connected to social status (Ucan, 2013), continual anger and stress levels (Kucukkose, 2015), aggressiveness (Gundogan, 2016), and school burnout (Akpinar, 2016) grow, there is a correlation between the two. The levels of well-being have decreased.

In addition, according to Eysenck, those who are nearer to the emotional instability end of the spectrum also tend to gravitate to criminal activity when extraversion is present. People who are on the verge of emotional instability have a rapid response to stress and need a significant amount of time to return to a calm state.

In conclusion, emotional instability occurs when our feelings display certain symptoms as a result of being rejected, although we are often unaware of this fact. We are able to claim that these functional responses adversely influence both our emotional well-being and our capacity to form secure and healthy connections with other people. Nevertheless, our sexual relationships and other interpersonal interactions may be negatively impacted by emotional instability. In general, we can assume that persons who battle with emotional instability have had at least one instance in their life in which they were rejected.

4.2.4. Respect for oneself

Self-esteem may be defined as an individual's overall evaluation of what they provide to the world. 2009 according to Hewitt. According to contemporary psychological theory, there are four components that make up one's self-esteem: (I) acceptance; (II) appraisal; (III) comparison; and (IV) impact. The acceptance of the kid in early life, obtaining good evaluations from near people, favorable comparisons, and the ability for effective action are the factors that contribute to the development of healthy self-esteem (Hewitt, 2002).

According to Harris (2021), an individual's views about himself should be seen as opinions rather than as a reflection of a reality.

a lack of confidence; clinical depression (Brown, Bifulco, Veiel, & Andrews, 1990); anxiety disorders (Sowislo & Orth, 2013); personality disorders (Lynum, Wilberg & Karterud, 2008); obsessive-compulsive disorder (Ehnholt, Salkovskis & Rimes, 1999); eating disorders (Gual, Pérez-Gaspar, Martnez-Gonzá To put it another way, it may be said that a feeling of self-esteem is observed to be associated with one another. Love, hope, curiosity, and taste were shown to be the most important characteristics for one's sense of self-esteem in the research carried out by Peterson and colleagues.

According to the research conducted by Rosenberg et al., the general component of self-esteem is associated with emotional and overall well-being, while the particular dimension of self-esteem is judgemental, evaluative, and more cognitive in nature, and it is associated with behavioral and behavioral outcomes.

According to the findings of the study conducted by Orth, Robins, and Widaman (2012), self-esteem improves from youth through middle age, reaches its highest position around the age of 50, and then begins to drop after reaching this point.

Peer victimization is a significant contributor to both poor self-esteem and social anxiety, according to research conducted on the origins of low self-esteem. In addition, a number of research have shown that the idea that is most strongly linked with happiness is self-esteem. However, low self-esteem is correlated with increased levels of fragile narcissism.

Sullivan, who contends that his research on interpersonal processes show that the experiences of the individual and his connection with others create the self and psychopathology, underlined that these interactions are driven by two need areas named security and self-esteem. Sullivan's findings on interpersonal processes were published in the journal *Personality and Individual Differences*. Based on the Theory of Interpersonal Personality, Leary (1957) presented the notion of "affiliation" as an alternative to the concept of "security" as one of the fundamental motives and requirements of interpersonal actions. He also proposed the concept of "dominance" as an alternative to the concept of "self-esteem."

Formal (2000) investigated the connection between the assertiveness and self-esteem of kids in the eighth grade of primary schools and the attitudes of their parents. They discovered that there was a considerable gap in the levels of self-esteem that were associated with the different

parents' perspectives. It was shown that kids who perceived their parents to be democratic had a better level of self-esteem than students who perceived their parents to be authoritarian or overprotective.

When someone is rejected, excluded, or neglected by other people, it may have a negative impact on a person's self-esteem and their ability to live a meaningful life, according to Case and Williams (2004). To put it another way, if someone is very sensitive to being rejected, we might say that their self-esteem is in jeopardy.

One of the requirements that is put at risk by psychological isolation is one's sense of self-worth. People who have low self-esteem are more likely to take expensive risks in adverse situations, such as being rejected or failing an endeavor, compared to people who have a healthy level of self-esteem. According to Zeigler-Hill (2013), the explanation for this is because people who have low self-esteem lack the evaluative resources required to defend themselves from potentially dangerous events involving themselves. In this particular instance, the person who has poor self-esteem displays avoidance behavior in order to prevent themselves from experiencing feelings of inadequacy, worthlessness, and deficiency.

There have been several research done on how being rejected might affect an individual's sense of self-worth. The participants in a study that is being carried out get feedback from a humanoid robot at the conclusion of a game in which they participated with the robot. When the participant is in the acceptance condition, the robot will inform them that it would want to meet again, but when they are in the rejection condition, the robot will say that it does not want to meet again. According to the findings of Nash et al. (2018), the level of self-esteem shown by the individuals who were exposed to the rejection condition was statistically substantially lower compared to those who were in the acceptance or control circumstances. To put it another way, we may argue that the connection between feeling rejected and having low self-esteem is an essential one.

According to Sirvanli Ozen and Guneri (2018), rejection sensitivity might be seen as an early warning system for potential dangers to the individual. A lack of respect for oneself, on the other hand, makes a person more vulnerable to being turned down. According to Watson and Nesdale (2012), there is a correlation that can be found to be both negative and substantial between the trait of rejection sensitivity and one's level of self-esteem.

We might claim that an individual's lack of self-esteem can make them more vulnerable to being rejected. Cognitive fusion may occur in a person who has been sensitive to rejection,

particularly if the individual has poor self-esteem and is preoccupied with ideas about rejection. Berenson and Downey (2006) provided an explanation of the workings of this mechanism that was quite comparable to what we have here. As a result, the concurrent development of rejection sensitivity and self-esteem may be traced back to the misconception that having high self-esteem and being accepted by others are inextricably linked.

According to Haliloglu (2008), the underlying reasons of loneliness include low self-esteem, deficiencies in social skills, poor social contacts, unrealistic appraisals, difficulties in bonding, and other contextual issues.

Iwaniec (2003), on the other hand, defines emotional neglect as a kind of parental action that lowers the degree of a child's sense of well-being and causes harm to the child's sense of self-worth.

People who struggle with low self-esteem are more likely to look for positive social feedback as a result. According to him, individuals who have poor self-esteem would reject good feedback because they know themselves and will be rejected by the person (Kagiticibasi, 2014). He thinks that this happens because people with low self-esteem know themselves. According to Baumeister, Hutton, and Tice (1989), people who have low self-esteem are different from those who have high self-esteem due to the fact that they desire to shield themselves from making errors, feeling embarrassed, being rejected, and experiencing various types of setbacks.

(Salmela-Aro & Nurmi, 2007) Research has shown that those who have poor levels of self-esteem make less money, are more likely to get addicted to drugs, and have much higher levels of depression.

However, research has shown that people's perceptions of themselves are strongly influenced by the approval, acceptance, or exclusion and rejection of others (for example, Leary, Tarnbor, Terdal, and Downs, 1995; Baurneister, 2000). This is because people tend to see themselves more favorably when they feel that others view them favorably.

A lack of respect for oneself is another significant component that contributes to the development of depression. According to Sireli (2012), a kid's self-esteem may be badly impacted when the youngster is rejected by others, particularly by perfectionist parents who have high standards for their children.

Low self-esteem has been linked to a variety of negative outcomes, including eating disorders, anxiety, depression, aggressive behavior, drug use, failure, and loneliness (Mann, Hosman, Schaalma, & Devries, 2004; Donnellan, Trzesniewski, Robins, & Moffitt, 2005). According to Sanford and Donovan (1984), the degree of a person's self-esteem has a significant impact on almost every aspect of that person's life.

Many children and people who have experienced rejection have a tendency to view themselves in the same way that they believe their parents and other attachment figures see them. Therefore, as long as children and adults have the impression that their attachment figures do not like them, they will continue to have the impression that they are unwanted and maybe even undeserving of being loved. Because of the harm done to their sense of self-worth, individuals may have an overwhelming sense of helplessness in the face of overt or implicit criticism (Rohner & Rising, 2014).

It is stated that experiences of rejection, either in the past or in the present, are associated to damaged self-esteem. There are a lot of individuals who are ignorant of the connection between previous or current experiences of perceived rejection and impaired self-esteem. It is difficult to modify the negative beliefs that drive damaged self-esteem if one does not have knowledge of the problem. In addition, a lot of individuals have the misconception that these twisted beliefs are true, and they are oblivious of the fact that this misconception may weaken their desire for love and acceptance and have them ready for even more rejection (Rohner & Khaleque, 2005).

On the other hand, negative thinking patterns (also known as negative self-talk) emerge over time as a means of making sense of one's encounters with rejection. For instance, children who don't receive enough quality time from a parent may try to make sense of this by convincing themselves that they aren't "good enough." This is particularly likely to happen if the child notices that the parent is spending more time with a sibling whom the child views as being more deserving of affection. (For instance, being physically handsome, cognitively talented, or athletically gifted). In certain cultures, young men are seen as having more potential than young women. This might occasionally cause young women to come to the incorrect notion that they are not as important as their brothers. According to Rohner and Khaleque (2005), this might result in a decline in one's sense of self-worth.

As a consequence of this, there may be swings in mood along with poor levels of self-esteem brought on by the perception of being rejected. Some youngsters who are trying to deal with this may display behaviors such as avoiding it or becoming defensive. Research has also

shown that persons who feel lonely tend to have lower levels of self-esteem, which is another one of the characteristics of lonely people. People who struggle with poor self-esteem and mood problems are more likely to be rejected by others. In addition, while taking into consideration the connection between the idea of self-esteem and psychiatric symptoms, one may assert that a person who has a high sensitivity to rejection is in the risk group in this respect. This is because of the interaction between the two concepts. It has been shown that being rejected might lower one's self-esteem. According to the findings of many studies, those who are very sensitive to rejection also tend to have poor levels of self-esteem.

4.2.5 The Need for Command and Control

People try to dominate or control their surroundings in order to produce good results and prevent undesirable outcomes. This is done in the hopes of achieving the former and avoiding the latter. According to Case and Williams (2004), it is essential for individuals to satisfy their need to dominate their surroundings in order to successfully adapt to those surroundings. According to the findings of the research that was carried out by Williams, Cheung, and Choi (2000), the participants in the study reported feeling poorer and having less control, despite the fact that they experienced a minor amount of psychological exclusion. Individuals could feel the need to reclaim the power that was taken away from them as a result of being excluded, according to Warburton, Williams, and Cairns (2006). According to Warburton, Williams, and Cairns's (2006) research, a violent reaction to being excluded may be attributed to the danger that people face while trying to fulfill their desire for control. Taking into consideration the connection between control and aggressive behavior, it is important to note that the degree to which an individual is exposed to aggressive behavior is partly affected by the amount of personal control that they feel they have after being excluded (Warburton, Williams, & Cairns, 2006).

We may argue that the need for control occurs in order for a person to avoid feeling awful for themselves when they are rejected, neglected, or excluded in order to adapt, and the degree to which an individual needs control is decided by the individual themselves.

4.3 Paradigms Used in Studies of Exclusion and Rejection

To be ignored is one interpretation of the term "psychological exclusion." In both research and study, this practice is fairly frequent. The phrases "life alone" (living Alone Prognosis),

"meeting" (Get Acquainted), "ball-toss," and "virtual ball" (Cyberball) are examples of phrases that are used often. It has been argued that these definitions describe behaviors as voluntary acts intended at helping or benefitting another person or people, and as conscious actions targeted at damaging or causing a disadvantage for another person or individuals (Williams, 2007). Similarly, it has been stated that these definitions explain behaviors as conscious actions aimed at helping or benefitting another person or persons. In addition, Williams (2007) employed face-to-face talks, role-playing, picturing or experiencing the event of rejection, as well as scenario descriptions of rejection and exclusion.

4.3.1 The Model for the Prediction of a Sole Life

Participants that react to a personality test under this paradigm are provided with one of three distinct forms of feedback, depending on the condition to which the participants were randomly allocated, in addition to receiving accurate feedback on their level of introversion or extraversion. This feedback is provided after the participants have completed the exam. The first of these three distinct types of feedback are referred to as the acceptance / high belonging condition. In this condition, the participants were told that they have the type of personality that allows them to have satisfying relationships throughout their lives, that people with this type of personality have long and happy marriages, and that they have long-lasting friendships with people who care about them. In the second condition, which is known as the rejection/low belonging condition, the researchers told the participants that they have the type of personality to live alone and end their lives alone, that although they now have friends and relationships, they have had no one around since their mid-20s, and they have had many marriages that did not last for a long time. In addition, the researchers told the participants that they have had many marriages that did not last for a long time. given. (Williams, Forgas, & Hippel, 2005; Williams, 2007) In the final negative feedback control condition, the participants are informed that they are clumsy and that as a result, they would have a variety of accidents and injuries during the course of their life.

In point of fact, its foundation was laid by the participants' responses to a personality test and the subsequent feedback they received on those answers. On the other hand, members of the inclusion group are informed that they will have a lifetime relationship, a stable lengthy marriage, and that their friends will always look out for them, while members of the exclusion group are told that they will be single for the rest of their lives, that their present relationship and friendship will end in their mid-twenties, and that they will always be taken care of by their friends. Negative

feedback is provided to the people in the control group, and they are informed that they will be hurt and will often have accidents because they are prone to accidents (Baumeister, Twenge, & Nuss, 2002; DeWall et al., 2009; Twenge et al., 2001) (Baumeister, Twenge, & Nuss, 2002; DeWall et al., 2009; Twenge et al. According to Twenge and colleagues' (2001) research, it was discovered that when the individuals were shunned by the Living Alone Paradigm, they demonstrated more violent behaviors. When individuals were excluded from the study, it was found that their performance on cognitive tests suffered a considerable drop (Baumeister, Twenge, and Nuss, 2002). In other words, we can state that the Alone Life Paradigm is a highly successful strategy in the provision of psychological exclusion as a result of the information presented here since it is consistent with that knowledge.

4.3.2 A New Approach to Dating

This paradigm may be accomplished if the participants choose particular themes, discuss about those issues inside the group they are in, and get to know one another. They are given some themes to speak about, such as their favorite movies or their areas of study at the university, and they are requested to take turns talking about these topics in the group in order to facilitate the participants in these groups getting to know each other more readily. This is done in order to facilitate the members in these groups getting to know each other more easily. At the conclusion of these discussions, the participants were given the task of deciding with which among the other members of the group they would most enjoy continuing to collaborate. It is communicated to the participant whether or not the other people in the group wish to collaborate with him (the acceptance condition) or whether or not they do not (the exclusion condition) (Leary et al., 1995; Nezlek et al., 1997). When this paradigm is used, it is noticed that there is a decline in the degree of self-esteem, particularly among the participants who believe that they are excluded due to personal reasons (Leary et al., 1995). This is particularly true of the participants who believe that they are excluded owing to personal reasons. In addition, it has been shown that the participants' reaction to not wanting to cooperate with other members of the group is higher if they have a poor self-esteem (Nezlek et al., 1997).

As a consequence of this, he does not want to collaborate with them if he has a poor sense of self-worth and views it as a kind of exclusion for personal reasons. In addition, we may argue that those who have the belief that they are being excluded have a poor sense of their own self-worth.

4.3.3 The Concept of Throwing as a Model

The Throwing Paradigm, which Williams and Sommer (1997) devised, was the first paradigm used in research on psychological exclusion. During their time spent sitting in the waiting area, the subjects were subjected to a method known as psychological exclusion. The participants who were involved in the game till the very end were considered to be part of the control group. The change that began with the other contracted participants in the waiting room tossing the ball to each other in the room was part of the experiment. Because there is no ball for the last five minutes of play, only the players who are members of the exclusion group are eliminated from the competition. Williams and Sommer (1997) discovered that participants who were excluded from the study were more disturbed and furious than individuals who were included. In different research that Warburton, Williams, and Cairns (2006) carried out, it was shown that individuals who were subjected to psychological ostracism had a tendency to engage in more violent behaviors than those who were not subjected to the same treatment. These research, namely the ones using the Ball Throwing Paradigm, were stopped before they could be completed (Williams & Jarvis, 2006). This was due to the observation of the severe psychological impacts of social exclusion on the subjects. As a result, a method known as the Virtual Ball Paradigm has been devised (Williams, Cheung, and Choi, 2000: 748-762) This method involves providing psychological isolation via the medium of a computer game.

4.3.4 The Hypothesis of the Virtual Ball

Williams, Cheung, and Choi (2000) conceived up the Virtual Ball Paradigm with the intended intent of ostracizing users inside a virtual setting using its capabilities. For the purpose of making the throwing paradigm more reasonable and less painful, a virtual equivalent has been devised. Participants engage in a game of ball with two other players who are linked to them via the computer in this form of the activity referred to as the Virtual Ball Game (Williams & Jarvis, 2006). This game begins with the participant clicking on one of the symbols on the screen that represents one of the other players. After that, the computer takes over and controls all of the other players. On the other hand, the information about the players that is maintained by the computer is kept hidden from the participants at all times. The participants were told at the beginning of the game that they were taking part in a study where the performance of mental imagery was being researched, and that the study would be conducted throughout the game. In order to make this

cover story more believable, we asked the participants to describe the atmosphere that was conjured up in their heads while they were playing the Virtual Ball Game. The participants in the psychological exclusion group only received the ball at the beginning of the game (Williams, 2007; Williams & Jarvis, 2006). This was in contrast to the people in the inclusion group, who received an equal number of balls with the other players until the finish of the game (Williams, 2007; Williams & Jarvis, 2006). It has been discovered that the people's emotional states shift as a result of playing this computer game, despite the fact that they are only subjected to a little amount of psychological exclusion. According to Williams, Cheung, and Choi's (2000) research, those who are excluded report experiencing more negative emotions than those who are included. Virtual Ball Paradigm; attachment (Frias & Shaver, 2014), depression (Niu et al., 2018), social anxiety (Wang et al., 2019), prosocial behavior (Riem et al., 2013), the need to belong and being aware (Aydin & al. et al., 2013), early maladaptive schemas (Komurcu & Soygut Pekak, 2017), accessibility of thoughts about uncertainty (Yavuz Guzel & Sahin, 2018), fear of death (Yaakobi, 2018), mortality salience (Wadian, 2009) worked with. In his study examining the impacts of ostracism, personal uncertainty, and mortality, Yavuz Guzel (2012) applied this paradigm in Turkey. His research was published in 2012. When participants are able to accomplish psychological exclusion via the use of Virtual Ball Game, the outcomes of the associated research show that their ideas regarding uncertainty become more prevalent (Yavuz Guzel, 2012). There are some researches that look at the accessibility of death thought by completing the Word Completion Test after psychological exclusion is offered using the Virtual Ball Paradigm (Steele, Kidd, & Castano, 2015; Yaakobi, 2018). When the literature is investigated, there are some studies that look at the accessibility of death thought.

According to the findings of the study conducted by Steele, Kidd, and Castano (2015), the ease with which persons who suffer psychological exclusion are able to entertain thoughts of death rises.

When it is taken into consideration that people are subjected to psychological exclusion via actions and discourses, there are studies that show individuals suffer feelings of uncertainty, mortality, and changes in their emotional states.

CHAPTER 5

PSYCHOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF REJECTION

1. *Changed Words*
2. *Structural Changes*
3. *Longest Unchanged Words*
4. *born with the ability to live independently of their mothers.*

A youngster who is conditioned to believe that he would be disapproved of by his parents may be hypervigilant for indications of disapproval while he is interacting with his playmates. As a result, such a child may be more prone to misinterpret benign critiques as being hostile (Goleman, 2006).

Given this information, we are able to draw the conclusion that the amount of acceptance or rejection shown by the parents is directly proportional to the good or negative contribution made to the cognitive and social development of preschool-aged children.

5.1.1. Trauma

Trauma is another word for harm. They suffer trauma as a direct consequence of being exposed to trying circumstances in their lives, which leads to stress. According to Arkonac (1999), p. 436, the development of posttraumatic stress disorder or posttraumatic stress disorder takes place when stress is not eliminated.

Post-traumatic stress disorder may cause physiological symptoms such as weariness, exhaustion, hyperarousal, somatic complaints, hunger and sleep difficulties; psychological and cognitive responses such as time, body, visual and auditory distortions (Akbaba, 2014). Post-traumatic stress disorder can also cause symptoms such as irritability and anger.

According to Akbaba (2014), "child abuse" refers to behaviors such as neglect, physical abuse, emotional abuse, sexual abuse, domestic violence, and intimidation. All of these behaviors may create trauma in children.

One of the things that might contribute to trauma is being verbally or emotionally abused. According to Akbaba (2014), the characteristics of emotionally abusive relationships include rejection, humiliation, disrespect, intimidation, and destitution.

After experiencing a traumatic incident, one might respond in one of two ways. Avoidance is the one that doesn't serve any purpose. According to Akbaba (2014), one of the effects of trauma is a loss of hope and powerlessness.

A single traumatic experience, such as being rejected, may shape us to have intense reactions across several domains, including physical, emotional, and cognitive, perhaps for the rest of our lives.

A conclusion reached as a consequence of the many investigations conducted by James Pennebaker (1990, 1997; Petrie et al., 1998). Pennebaker's research has shown that it may be detrimental to one's mental and physical health to repress the thoughts and sensations that are related with personal tragedies, failures, and sentiments of guilt or shame.

Ruppert (2011) Traumas, in the spiritual and emotional area; If processes such as seeing, feeling, thinking, remembering, or dreaming are affected for particular periods of time or over the long term and their functions are not operating regularly, then a mental injury is described. Attachment trauma is another term that he uses to describe what happened when the kid was rejected by his mother.

However, for the kid who is rejected, the emotional tension caused by his mother's lack of affection is intolerable, and this causes the youngster to resist this rejection in each and every manner imaginable. According to Ruppert (2011), types of sexual abuse often occur with mother's rejection of a kid and emotional neglect of the child, both of which are associated to attachment trauma.

A traumatic event is an unpleasant experience that occurs in our life at a time and place that is not within our control. This occurrence or circumstance takes place when we are unable to make a choice, regardless of what is taking place to us (Solmus, 2015).

People who have poor self-efficacy believe that their shortcomings are the cause of their problems, which causes them to have lower levels of self-confidence and performance, as well as feelings of hopelessness and pessimism (Solmus, 2015).

In point of fact, the good and bad processes that take place when we are not bonded to our mothers throughout the initial years of our existence effect all aspects of life, across an individual's whole life span. When a person is forming a connection with the outside world, the role that a person performs as a mother plays a significant part in the development of that connection.

It is experienced when the mother is unable to create fundamental closeness with the newborn, which results in the infant having the sense that they have been rejected. As a consequence of this, the infant develops fears of being left alone and being rejected, and as a consequence of this attitude, the infant exhibits protest responses. When this mindset, that is, anxiety, is unable to be decreased, distance between the mother and the child starts to develop. This attitude drives him to retreat into his shell, grow lonely, worry about being abandoned and rejected, and move away from social contacts. It also causes him to move away from social relationships. According to Solmus (2015), this life orientation is consistent throughout a person's whole life, beginning when they are infants.

According to research conducted, the emotional harm caused by paternal rejection is larger and more long-lasting than that caused by mother rejection.

Children experience trauma when either of their parents rejects them; yet, it is often more difficult for children to deal with the rejection of their dads since men typically have more status and prestige in society.

According to Kohut (1971), if a kid's needs are not met by their parents, the youngster will go through painful disappointments and will have pauses in the progression of their development. If a traumatic letdown is experienced along the line of "idealized parental imago," then in the years that follow, the person will wander between the notion of "defensive grandiose self" and the quest for "the source of strength to be fused" while they are experiencing anxious periods.

People are capable of reacting to previous traumas that occurred throughout their upbringing. They might respond based on previous experiences in addition to how they feel about the present circumstance. Some of these events may be painful, and children who have been through them may feel tricked or rejected, leading them to the conclusion that the world is not a safe place to live (Savage, 1999).

According to Glasberg and Aboud (1982), children who encounter extreme trauma and whose life is endangered are left with no alternative but to believe that the events never occurred in order to deal with the emotional emotions they feel. This is because they have no other choice.

(Downey, Khouri, & Feldman, 1997) found that it is feasible for individuals who are exposed to wrong parental attitudes throughout childhood and whose requests and needs are ignored to transmit the fearful rejection expectancies of interpersonal trauma to their future lives. This is the case for persons who have had their preferences and needs disregarded.

According to research published by Mulkens and Bogels (1999), Kimbrel (2008), and Stemberger, Turner, Beidel, and Calhoun (1995), traumatic events that a person has personally experienced or observed in the past are a significant factor in the development of anxiety. According to Hudson and Rapee (2000) and Gazelle and Ladd (2003), the majority of these experiences consist of being humiliated and mocked by other individuals.

Rejections that have severe emotional repercussions or that are endured for an extended period of time may have substantial psychological implications or even be traumatic. It has been stated that some persons suffer from a persistent dread of being rejected, which is often brought on by "multiple traumatic experiences" of being rejected at an impressionable age. For instance, a child who is made to feel rejected on a regular basis by his parents may struggle in school and in his relationships with his classmates. If the child is unable to rectify the situation, he may continue to experience difficulties in his personal and/or professional relationships as an adult (<https://www.yasantipsychology.com/kisisel-gelisim/reddildilme-why-pains>). (Source: <https://www.yasantipsychology>).

People who have a high rejection sensitivity have been shown to be more likely to suffer from a variety of psychological issues, including social anxiety, obsessive compulsive disorder, and post-traumatic stress disorder (<https://psikohelp.com/reddedilme-duyarliligi>).

As a consequence of this, we may argue that children who are subjected to inappropriate parental attitudes while they are still young are likely to have severe psychological repercussions or even trauma. In addition, it was said that until this circumstance is resolved, there is a possibility that there would be difficulties in all adult relationships. In other words, the attitudes of one's parents that are modeled for them throughout infancy are carried into adulthood. The circumstance in which children are subjected to emotional abuse or psychological injury as a result of the attitudes and actions they are exposed to is categorized as one of the sorts of abuse that may occur. The majority of the time, adults in the immediate vicinity of children and teenagers are the ones

that engage in behaviors that might be interpreted as emotional abuse. According to Tutar's article on criminology.com from 2002, the root of these behaviors is feeling rejected. In addition, Kernberg (1989) puts forward the theory that traumatic events have a role in the formation of borderline personality disorder.

However, studies call attention to the fact that disconnection and rejection, both of which are schema areas of traumatic childhood experiences, are simultaneously prevalent in both the mother and the kid. The majority of people who have a field of Disconnection and Rejection have recollections of painful events from their childhood. As a consequence of the findings of this research, we are able to assert that the domain in which Young et al. experienced the most traumatic events was that of disconnection and rejection.

It has been claimed that the impacts of small traumas are just as significant as the effects of large traumas in terms of mental health, and this statement has been based on major traumas in the research that have been completed in general. According to Orucular (2016), traumatic events in childhood expose victimizing relationships again in adulthood via the intermediate role of a sensitivity to rejection and abandonment.

5.1.2. Depression

Hippocrates first used the word melancholia, which literally translates to "black bile," in the fourth century BC when he was attempting to define sadness. This condition was first referred to as "folie circulaire" by French psychiatrists in the year 1854 (Karamustafalioglu, 2011).

People's typical response to unfavorable occurrences is one that includes feelings of misery. If this circumstance continues for an extended period of time, the individual may be experiencing an uncontrollable symptom related with a low mood. According to Karamustafalioglu (2011), depressed mood may develop concurrently with both physical ailments and psychological conditions.

The basic symptoms of depression include a depressed mood, decreased energy, and a lack of interest or pleasure in formerly pleasurable activities. A lack of attention, low self-esteem, feelings of guilt, pessimism, thoughts of self-harm or suicide, disturbance in normal sleep patterns, changes in appetite, and a diminished libido are other prevalent symptoms. According to Karamustafalioglu's (2011) research, the DSM-IV-TR classified the intensity of depression into three categories: mild, moderate, and severe.

Depression is one of the most prevalent forms of mental illness that may be seen in adolescents. Depression is an individual's emotions, beliefs, and actions; it has a substantial impact on the individual's self-perception, interpersonal connections, physical functioning, biological processes, productivity, and overall life satisfaction (Sireli & Soykan, 2015).

According to behaviorists, depression is caused when a person's life is lacking in positive support in some way. On the other hand, humanistic personality theorists believe that respect for oneself is the key to understanding depression. According to him, those who suffer from depression on a regular basis are those who are not aware of the principles that they hold dear. According to cognitive personality psychologists, whether or not an individual will develop depression relies on how they view their capacity to influence the events in their lives (Burger, 2006).

Studies have shown that the risk of depression is higher in teenagers who have contentious relationships with their parents and who regard their parents as lacking in warmth and as rejecting them. This perception also increases the risk of depression. Family dynamics and the degree to which a family is functioning are also key contributors to the development of depressive symptoms in adolescents. According to the findings of Sireli and Soykan (2015), there is a statistically significant correlation between the severity of depression and both the amount of felt rejection and the decline in family functioning.

Children who have the impression that they are being rejected are more likely to display irritation, pessimism, and sadness. This implies that they continue their lives as persons who are easily injured and feel sadness within the context of the challenges that they face in social or interpersonal interactions (Sireli and Soykan, 2015).

The fact that the desire to belong is not addressed in studies and studies (Baumeister et al. 2005; Verhagen et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2017) has shown that psychological exclusion becomes permanent, and social exclusion may lead to depression and suicide (Kavakli, 2020). Studies and studies have shown that psychological exclusion becomes permanent, and social exclusion can lead to depression and suicide. According to Peters et al. (2016), one of the distinguishing characteristics of many pathological features and behaviors is an extreme sensitivity to rejection signals. This trait is also associated with borderline personality disorders, avoidant personality disorders, depression, and social anxiety.

"Social depression" is a term that has been used by professionals to describe the state of being unhappy brought on by poor or damaged relationships and the unfulfilled demand for

connection. According to Goleman (2007), social exclusion, or the fear of being excluded from social activities, is one of the most prominent causes of anxiety in people.

Studies of moms with clinical depression and their children demonstrate that depressed mothers usually behave colder than other mothers, divert their eyes from their babies more often than other mothers, feel furious more frequently than other mothers, and are more intrusive when their kids need time to settle down (Goleman, 2007). This conduct, which the kid observes in his mother, may, in a way, lead the youngster to grow sensitive to the feeling of rejection and to behave in a melancholy and angry manner.

It has been hypothesized that a person's response to being rejected is in some way influenced by the way in which they attempt to make sense of the incident. People who believe that they are to blame for the situation are susceptible to unpleasant feelings of rejection; yet, their responses are inwardly focused. Anxiety, withdrawal, and despair were found to be the responses to these observations. On the other hand, research that was carried out on women who are particularly sensitive to rejection discovered that the manner in which a romantic connection comes to an end is significant for the mental condition of the individual after the relationship has ended. It has been suggested that depression is associated with situations in which a person's partner is the one who ends a romantic connection. If this is the case, the individual will have an increased sense of rejection as a result of the breakup. (Ayduk and colleagues, 2001).

According to the research that pertains to this topic, it has been discovered that when extraverted persons experience rejection, they act belligerently and adopt the tactic of hurting oneself as a coping mechanism. On the other hand, it is said that introverted people react to the possibility of rejection with worry and isolate themselves from other people in order to protect themselves from any potential dangers that may arise. According to Ayduk et al. (2001), being in this scenario might lead to feelings of isolation, despair, and anxiety in social situations.

Persons who spend a lot of time alone are more likely to be introverted, apprehensive, and open to being rejected (Russell et al., 1980). Additionally, lonely persons are more likely to suffer from depression (Joiner, Catanzaro, Rudd, & Rajab, 1999; Koenig, Isaacs, & Schwartz, 1994).

It has been established that the effect of the father may be more crucial in the development of depression (Erozkan, 2004; Rohner & Britner, 2002). The perception of parental rejection in the early period predicts the development of depressive symptoms in adolescence and adulthood. It has been demonstrated that individuals who suffer from rejection anxiety and who have also been rejected in the past have a greater likelihood of developing depressive symptoms in the foreseeable

future. This is in comparison to individuals who suffer from rejection anxiety but have not been rejected in the past as well as individuals who do not suffer from rejection anxiety but have been rejected. Negative thoughts might arise as a result of an anxious expectation of being rejected. According to the findings of Normansell and Wisco (2017), there is a correlation between the anxious anticipation of being rejected and depressive symptoms in both a cross-sectional and a longitudinal fashion. The likelihood of recovery from depression may be affected by the existence of rejection sensitivity. During a depressive episode, a person's way of understanding both himself and their surroundings changes, and the individual finds that negative intermediate beliefs dominate their day-to-day existence. According to Weinstein et al. (2016), the inclusion of rejection sensitivity to the picture in persons who suffer from major depression is likely to have the predicted consequence of predicting more frequent, more severe, and longer-lasting depressive Chapters. The existence of rejection sensitivity was shown to be connected with higher depressive chapters in patients with bipolar mood disorder. However, no association was identified between rejection sensitivity and manic chapters. In patients suffering from bipolar or unipolar depression, there is a correlation between rejection sensitivity and somatic discomfort. (Weinstein and colleagues, 2016).

It has been observed that the majority of persons who suffer from depression acquire a profoundly pessimistic schema or worldview as a result of formative events they had as children or teenagers. According to Furnham (2009), this may occur for a variety of reasons, including parental sadness, being chastised or rejected by parents or peers, or the loss of a parent via death or divorce.

Only those teenagers who did not have any supportive connections were discovered to have a link between anxious expectancies of rejection and symptoms of depression in the course of the research that was carried out with young people. According to the findings of McDonald, Bowker, Rubin, Laursen, and Duchene (2010), there is a connection between the anticipation of receiving an angry rejection and the development of depression symptoms in adolescents who do not have supportive connections with either their parents or their friends. In addition, there is a connection between rejection sensitivity and borderline personality features, borderline personality disorder (Ayduk et al., 2008; Berenson et al., 2016; Staebler, Helbing, Rosenbach, & Renneberg, 2011), as well as depression (Ayduk, Downey, & Kim, 2001; Beeson, Brittain). in addition to Vaillancourt, 2020; Harper, Dickson, & Welsh, 2006; Kraines & Wells, 2017; Mellin, 2008; Normansell & Wisco, 2017; Zimmer-Gembeck, Nesdale, Webb, Khatibi, & Downey, 2016). According to research that was conducted by Salahur (2010), the sub-dimensions of adult attachment traits

known as anxiety and avoidance have a mediation role in the association between perceived parental acceptance or rejection level and the number of depressive symptoms that an individual experiences. Accordingly, it has been determined in many parts of the world that children or adults who believe they are rejected by their parents are significantly more likely to experience clinical or non-clinical depression or depressive affect-affect than people who believe they are accepted (Rohner & Britner, 2002). This is the case in contrast to people who believe they are accepted by their parents.

People who have a pattern of being rejected are more likely to have low self-esteem. According to Joiner (1995), adolescents and teenagers who have low levels of self-esteem are more likely to suffer high levels of despair, anxiety, and a feeling of being powerless.

Individuals who were brought up by parents who rejected them throughout their infancy are said to develop a feeling of loneliness and insecurity as adults, as stated by the research of Karen Horney (1945). Individuals as a result will suffer feelings of depression. After then, they continue their lives as persons who suffer depression in every difficulty that they have in the latter stages of life due to the difficulties that they have in their interactions with other people.

According to Persons-Miranda's research from 1992, however, we can state that people who are rejected by love partners and close friends produce more dependent negatively dependent life events and increase despair.

The emotional trauma caused by being rejected almost invariably results in overgeneralization. According to Burns (2016), one of the 10 types of cognitive distortions that make up the foundation of depression is overgeneralization. In addition, a person who is sad may entertain the concept that others do not accept him because he is imperfect or abandoned.

There are many different kinds of refusals to accept anything. The phenomenon known as "adolescent rejection" is the one that may be seen most often and most obviously. The second kind of "angry rejection" is one that is characterized by arrogance and self-centeredness. "Manipulative rejection" is the third sort of rejection that may occur. To put it another way, the other person attempts to exert their will on you by using the implicit or explicit threat of deprivation or rejection (Burns, 2016). The emotional harm caused by rejection and disapproval is caused by our own ideas, and the feelings of grief and anger that result from these actions may put a person at risk of developing depression.

Parents who have suffered emotional trauma often unintentionally transmit their unresolved anxieties and depressions to their offspring. However, in order to alleviate their anxieties, parents become too attached to their own children, but at the same time, they turn their backs on their children because of the insensitivity they feel (Ruppert, 2014). When children are emotionally rejected by their parents, they are far more likely to suffer from anxiety and despair throughout their whole lives. However, being rejected by one's parents may lead to feelings of isolation in childhood, which can manifest as both anxiety and sadness (Gibson, 2017).

According to Harb et al.'s research (2002, page 963), there are correlations between being sensitive to rejection in interpersonal relationships and having depression. Social anxiety is often accompanied with depression as a general comorbid condition. On the other hand, interpersonal rejection sensitivity manifests itself in connection to social anxiety in addition to sadness. In addition, Rapee (1997) highlights the fact that being rejected by one's parents is related with a wide variety of psychological issues such as anxiety and despair. A study that was done by Ayduk et al. (2000) found that those who anticipate being rejected are more likely to experience despair in their romantic relationships.

Having an anxious anticipation of rejection is connected with negative affect such as tension and anger, and in this instance, effects such as hostility, social withdrawal, loneliness, and depression may develop (Ayduk et al., 2001; Romero-Canyas and Downey, 2005). These findings come from empirical investigations that have been conducted. According to Gao et al.'s (2017) research, having a high sensitivity to rejection was also substantially and modestly related with depression, other anxiety disorders, loneliness, and body dysmorphic disorder. According to Ayduk and Gyurak (2008), those who have a high rejection sensitivity are more likely to incorrectly perceive and distort the acts of others, which might cause them to experience emotions of sadness.

Negative reactions, which are seen as being rejected by other people, being excluded from the group, or being excluded, cause people to experience negative emotions such as uneasiness, tension, disappointment, and anger, and in the long run, it can result in feelings of helplessness, worthlessness, alienation, depression with social isolation, and even suicidal thoughts (Blackhart, Nelson, Knowles, and Baumeister, 2009; Ford and Collins, 2010). In addition, it seems that parental rejection and other kinds of interpersonal rejection are the primary predictors of practically all sorts of behavior disorders (including depression, depressed affect, delinquency, alcohol and drug misuse, and so on). (Al-Falaij, 1991; Chen, Rubin, & Li, 1997; Crockenberg & Leerkes, 2003; Ge, Best, Conger, & Simon, 1996; Glavak, Kuterovac and Sakomon, 2003; Hill and Bush, 2001; Jakupčević, KK and Ajduković, M., 2011; Loeber and Stouthamer-Loeber, 1986;

Maughan, Pickles, and Quinton, 1995; Pedersen, 1994; Rothbaum and Weis, 1994; Salama, 1990; Simons, Robertson and Downs, 1989; Whitbeck, Hoyt, and Ackley, 1997; Act. Yener, 2005).

Studies that were carried out in Turkey looked at the relationship between a person's perception of acceptance or rejection from their parents and their psychological well-being (Isik, 2010; Saritas, 2007; Near, 2011). Saritas (2007) revealed that psychological distress, depression, eating disorders, anger, and anxiety symptoms were linked with perceived mother acceptance or rejection in a sample of Turkish adolescents (Walsh et al, 2017). According to the findings of the research carried out by Near (2011), the perception of parental rejection was shown to be a predictor of feelings of anxiety, anger, and sadness.

However, Parker (2002) advocated for a shift in the definition of atypical depression as the most frequent symptom of atypical depression. This is due to the fact that rejection sensitivity as a permanent personality type is shown to be high in atypical depression (Derecho, Wetzler, McGinn, Sanderson, & Asnis, 1996). In this context, rejection sensitivity is the most common symptom of atypical depression. Individuals who were diagnosed with atypical depression and had a high rejection sensitivity responded differently to antidepressants than those who had a low rejection sensitivity, according to the findings of Joyce and colleagues (2004).

In a study that was carried out in 1995 by Lesnik-Oberstein, Koers, and Cohen with women who neglected their children and behaved aggressively against one another, the researchers discovered that these moms had low levels of self-confidence, as well as low levels of despair and anxiety, when it came to resolving issues within their marriages.

Similarly, research that was done longitudinally with 225 children and mothers in 2009 by Feng et al. found a connection between parental acceptance-rejection and depression in adulthood. According to the research conducted by Khaleque and Rohner (2002), it was shown that there is a negative association between parental rejection and psychological adjustment. Furthermore, it was found that perceived rejection from both parents tends to lead to problems in children such as behavior disorders, drug misuse, and depression. These findings may be found in Khaleque and Rohner's research.

In their analysis of research conducted on adults, Rohner and Britner (2002) found that issues such as depression, behavior difficulties, and drug addiction are linked to the acceptance or rejection of children by their parents. This was true independent of the culture.

According to the findings of another research carried out by Anli and Karli (2010), there is a connection between the feeling of being rejected by one's parents and increased levels of both anxiety and sadness. According to the findings of a research that was carried out with college students, the perception of parental rejection was proven to be a predictor of sadness in persons (Kilic, 2012). In other words, it was assumed that the experience of rejection by one's parents throughout infancy had an effect on the structural makeup of people's brains and contributes to the development of depressive symptoms by way of affect, emotion, and self-evaluation.

According to the findings of research conducted by Vulic-Prtoric and Macuka (2006), felt rejection from one's father was shown to be connected with feelings of anxiety, whilst experienced rejection from both parents was discovered to be the strongest predictor of feelings of sadness. On the other hand, Magios, Downey, and Shoda (2000) said that an individual's susceptibility to clinical depression is increased when they have a high rejection sensitivity.

According to Burns (2016), the act of being rejected by another person causes the most emotional anguish, even more so than the harm done to our bodies or the loss of our possessions. One of these strategies is termed depression, and it consists of the individual turning their sentiments of wrath inward on themselves. One of the most significant characteristics of depression is the presence of pessimism with the emotion of mourning. This is in contrast to the sentiments of sadness and pain that are experienced by the normal individual. A person who is prone to depression has a persistent belief that he would never be able to free himself of unfavorable thoughts and feelings. For instance, if someone is ignoring you, the first ideas that pop into your head are ones that are rooted in pessimism, such as "that means I will be rejected." These thoughts come to mind automatically. Burns (2016) and Gectan (1994). It was shown in research conducted on depressed individuals by Clark and Teasdale in 1982 that sad memories were simpler to retrieve than happy ones. Rejection sensitivity has been linked to a variety of mental health and behavioral issues, including depression and self-mutilation (for example, Goncu & Sumer, 2011; Harper, Dickson & Welsh, 2006). Furthermore, rejection sensitivity has been shown to accurately predict unfavorable outcomes in romantic relationships.

As a consequence of this, it was discovered that it played a mediating function in the association between the perception of maternal rejection and the feeling of despair, as well as in the relationship between the impression of maternal rejection and the feeling of anxiety. It is possible to say that self-mutilation strategy is a method that both men and women who have rejection sensitivity generally use as a method when it comes to their romantic relationships (Harper et al. 2006). There is a significant relationship between rejection sensitivity and

depression, and there is also a significant relationship between rejection sensitivity and self-silencing behavior. Those who suffer from anxiety rejection sensitivity tend to blame themselves for being rejected, engage in behaviors that signal avoidance, and channel their emotions within. As a consequence, these individuals are more likely to encounter circumstances such as social withdrawal, feelings of loneliness, and despair. On the other hand, those who are very sensitive to rejection are more likely to experience despair.

In addition, many studies (Gilbert et al. 2006, Harper et al. 2006, Mellin, 2008) have shown that there is a considerable connection between depressive symptoms and an individual's sensitivity to being rejected. According to Brown et al. (2007), other types of abuse are less efficient in causing persistent sadness than the rejection and lack of sympathy shown by a mother toward her child. In other words, evidence-based research on depression has demonstrated that sensitivity to rejection, in addition to experiencing rejection oneself, is connected with depression (Rosenbach, 2013). Depression has been shown to coincide with the attachment type that develops as a result of parental rejection, as has been seen.

Studies on whether or not children are accepted or rejected by their parents have been carried out in a number of different countries throughout the globe. It has been shown that feelings of rejection from one's parents are linked to clinical depression, problematic behaviors, attachment disorders, difficulties in psychological adjustment, psychosomatic responses, as well as alcohol and drug misuse.

5.1.3. Angle

According to Bourbeau (2017), pain is the development of emotional agony that has been formed and created in the minds of individuals who feel undesired, excluded, have lost their sense of belonging, and are dissatisfied after being rejected by "others."

the psychoanalytic approach to psychotherapy, which derives from its predecessors, focuses on reliving the painful experiences of one's upbringing. Freud gave this concept the label "again compulsion" (E. Young & S. Klosko, 2019).

According to Rook (1984), loneliness is the unpleasant condition that a person experiences or feels when he or she worries about being misunderstood by other people, has rejection anxiety, is excluded or believes he or she will be rejected, and is unable to locate a social partner to ease his or her loneliness (Uncu, 2021).

The schema has a lot of trouble surviving on its own. We are being put under a significant amount of pressure to keep this continuing. This uniformity is an essential component of human drive. This ruse is familiar to us. Even though it hurts, it's so familiar that it seems cozy and comfy. According to E. Young and S. Klosko (2019), one of these strategies involves the rejection of children by their parents. It is made up of your memories, feelings, perceptions, and the physiological sensations you experience (Tuncer, 2019).

The act of surrender involves engaging in all of the damaging patterns that we keep on repeating. These are the ways that we live out our childhoods over and over again. We are still innocent youngsters that go through the same suffering. Rejection is a part of childhood that follows us into adulthood. As a result, humans often experience anxiety when faced with change. It fills us with hopelessness. According to E. Young and S. Klosko (2019), everything that we are aware of is the pattern from which we are unable to break free.

An essential aspect in the development and maintenance of psychological diseases is experiential avoidance, which may be seen as a reluctance to expose uncomfortable thoughts and emotions (Hayes & Smith, 2021). This reluctance plays a role in the development and maintenance of psychological disorders. According to Chawla and Ostafin (2007), it is regarded as a significant element. According to Hayes et al. (2004), there is a connection between the act of avoiding experiences and a variety of psychiatric problems, including trauma, anxiety, fear, and depression. According to Williams (2009), people experience emotional distress when they are rejected, ostracized, or neglected by other people. According to the Social Pain Theory proposed by MacDonald and Leary (2005), human beings experience both physical and social pain via identical physiological pathways. It has been shown that the experience of rejection and physical pain share a same neurocognitive infrastructure (Eisenberger et al. 2006; Fris and Shaver, 2014). In this instance, the dACC area of the brain is engaged (Chester, DeWall, & Pond, 2016) (Eisenberger, Lieberman, & Williams, 2003).

People are equipped with an early warning system that can identify social isolation and the accompanying emotional suffering very rapidly. Being rejected or neglected by other people is, in a way, an experience that is on par with the anguish of dying. To put it another way, being rejected

is the equivalent of dying socially in the eyes of persons. Perhaps this is the reason why they have a greater fear of dying. Despite this, research has shown a statistically significant positive correlation between the experience of pain and an individual's susceptibility to rejection (Gurbuz, 2022).

The individual is under the impression that other people would bully them, injure them, humiliate them, lie to them, and mislead them. According to Rafaeli et al. (2018), these individuals think that the majority of the damage they have sustained was caused either intentionally or negligently. It encompasses feelings such as rage, pain, and terror, and it may be an indication of unexpected mood shifts or that the individual may walk away from their surroundings. According to Young and Klosko (2018), the individual is always on high alert and cannot even put their faith in their family members.

Basic needs of children include touching, trusting, caring for the child's health, feeding and dressing the child, protecting the child from danger, guiding the child, setting an example for the child, determining the limits of what the child can and cannot do, being consistent, recognizing the child's feelings, allocating time for him, building a bridge between the child and the outside world, to see, to enter the child's world, and to experience and warn different events and s. Basic needs of children include touching, Emotional neglect may be seen as the failure to satisfy these fundamental requirements. According to Benice (2013), emotional neglect is characterized as scaring, threatening, humiliating, and rejecting the kid as a result of not addressing the child's fundamental needs (OZSERT, F., KAZAK, M., OZDEMIR, EA, & Figen, C. OK, 2022).

According to the findings of certain research (Baumeister, Brewer, Tice, & Twenge, 2007), after experiencing the social pain that results from being excluded and rejected, the emotional system becomes incapacitated for a period of time, which leads to numbness. On the other hand, Eisenberger, Liberman, and Williams (2003) put forward the hypothesis that social pain and physical pain share neuroanatomical underpinnings. Accordingly, the findings of DeWall and Baumeister's (2006) study shown that the experience of social exclusion both heightens one's tolerance to physical pain and decreases their sensitivity to it.

In addition, feelings such as social sorrow, grief, and rage brought on by social exclusion might drive people to fear and direct their attention on the process of social exclusion (Solak & Tek Ozel, 2019). Accordingly, the existence of obvious negative feedback is the primary driver of the painful experience of rejection. According to Molden et al. (2009), under this scenario, persons are more likely to lose existing social ties than they are to gain new ones since either their present

standing in the relationship or their prospects of forming new relationships are diminished. In addition, people experience discomfort and anguish if they are made to feel threatened in the context of their interpersonal interactions. On the other hand, Williams and Zadro (2005) contend that being oblivious of one's rejection would lead to the same outcomes as being unaware of the agony that one must experience when their hand touches fire.

In addition, the study participants who were mentally excluded during the virtual ball toss exhibited higher activity in the anterior cingulate cortex of the brain. This is the same region of the brain that shows increased activity when a person is experiencing physical pain. According to this, the neurocognitive function of social pain seems to be comparable to that of physical pain. At this point, it is stated that the psychological responses of individuals who endure physical pain are comparable to those of those who are socially rejected. According to Soylu (2010), the agony of being rejected may often result in negative feelings such as rage and grief, both of which might promote violent responses. On the other side, a negative reaction that is perceived to be rejected by others or excluded from the group leads persons who are excluded to experience pain, agitation, stress, and delusions. It has been shown by the findings of the study that it is capable of producing emotions, including negative ones such as irritation and wrath (Williams, 2007).

In point of fact, being rejected results in a kind of mental suffering that is analogous to physical pain and instant responses that are accompanied by various unpleasant emotions; these sentiments represent a true condition of being excluded from a group. According to the findings of the research conducted (Soylu, 2010), the second-stage short-term responses that were noticed following the choice remain.

Horney believes that people's first encounter with rejection and other people's disapproval of any conduct, regardless of how inconsequential it may be, is the root cause of their fear about being mistreated by others. He believes that this leaves him open to the possibility of being rejected (COLAK, GV, KOC, AE, & HOCAOGLU, C. 2021).

The agony of being rejected by those to whom you feel a deep connection and closeness is greater than the anguish of being rejected by other people. In addition, the first personal rejection experiences seem to be a component that also influences the success of a person's subsequent social interactions (Ozen & Guneri, 2018). This suggests that the sensation of being rejected is not merely an unpleasant occurrence that occurs during this experience.

According to Yanik (2019), a significant number of individuals who have experienced rejection emotionally close themselves off, claiming that they "do not need anyone" to shield them from the anguish and grief caused by rejection.

Rejected;

They have a decreased sensitivity to their own feelings. According to Rohner (1984), those who were rejected by their parents turn to others as a means of shielding themselves from the agonizing sensations that they are experiencing. They don't speak out and they keep their emotions a secret. As a result, they develop into people who are emotionless.

- They often experience uncomfortable negative emotions, such as rage, resentment, hostility, and others, which may constantly be a source of discomfort (Yanik, 2019).

One is able to determine at a young age whether or not the behaviors of a mother are genuine by seeing how she behaves. According to Genctan (2002), at this point in their development, youngsters begin to carry traumatic experiences into their subconscious.

In a nutshell, this feeling of rejection, which manifests itself in infancy and continues to manifest itself in subsequent encounters, is what causes the individual to suffer from psychological agony. Everyone makes it a point to do everything they can to avoid going through this suffering (Bowlby, 1980). The refusal to acknowledge one's formative experiences is a component of this distinction in perspective. He holds the belief that a person does not only experience a fleeting sorrow but rather that it permeates all aspects of his life and hinders his capacity for successful social connection (Varli, 2022). We can say that damaged borders create a maladaptive schema and that this perception is painful, and this pain is accompanied by psychological pain and some negative emotions in some social interactions later in life. In light of this information, individuals who are hurt by rejection have a tendency to hurt the rejected person in return, emotionally. Rejection maladaptive schemas between childhood and parental rejection. This, too, produces an unpleasant experience for many people and might expose knowledge that is unsettling and challenging to understand (Varli, 2022).

To put it another way, one might say that the anguish of being ignored or disregarded by other people is comparable to that of dying.

5.1.4. Anxiety, also known as the anxiety disorder

Anxiety: The feeling that something is wrong but you aren't sure what it is anxiety disorder fear. These are the kinds of circumstances that might show themselves in a variety of different ways, such as stress and impatience. Anxiety is often brought on by both the external world and the internal expectations that people have. (Koc, M., Yavuzer, Y., Demir, Z., and Caliskan, M. 2001) Some of these misconceptions include the belief that a parent does not love them enough or that they will be punished or abandoned for poor conduct.

Anxiety is a significant emotional reaction that leads a person to grimace, haste, move rapidly, react angrily, and play with their fingers. Anxious people also tend to shake their fingers. Body numbness, tingling, redness, shaking limbs, inability to relax, fear of something serious happening, dizziness, heart palpitations, feeling unsteady, nervousness, choking, choking, difficulty breathing, fear of death, indigestion or nervousness, fainting Extreme symptoms that are not related to heat, such as flushing or sweating, indicate that the person is experiencing anxiety. In certain contexts, the term "anxiety" is used interchangeably with "anxiety." Additionally, it is classified as persistent anxiety as well as transitory anxiety. (From the Vulture, 2014).

Freud distinguished three distinct forms of worry: guilt anxiety, anxiety based on neurotic thoughts, and anxiety based on the perception of reality. A sensation of dread or unease brought on by actual threats existing in one's environment is an example of true anxiety. On the other hand, neurotic anxiety refers to the concern that an individual would lose command of their natural tendencies and engage in actions that will lead to negative consequences. The true cause of neurotic worry is the response of the parent to the kid's impulsive conduct, which is the perception of the outside world held by the youngster. According to Gectan (1997), guilt anxiety might be defined as the dread of one's own conscience.

Anxiety is a powerful motivator, especially when it first starts to set in. A person is able to escape a potentially hazardous situation, control potentially harmful urges, or listen to the voice of their conscience by using this method. According to Gectan (1997), when he is unable to exercise control over his fear, he compares his state of being to that of a helpless infant.

Anxiety or conduct in a manner that may be adversely assessed, or characterized as the fear of revealing anxiety; fear or anxiety in one or more social circumstances in which the person may be judged by someone else. social anxiety disorder; fear or anxiety in one or more social situations in which the person may be judged by someone else. The third most prevalent kind of mental illness is known as social anxiety disorder. Patients who suffered from social anxiety disorder were

found to have significant difficulties in functioning, an increase in suicidal ideation, financial problems, a decrease in work and school performance, and a deterioration in social relations. In addition, these patients used a large quantity of drugs and visited their doctor more frequently (Kartal, 2022).

There is a significant positive correlation between rejection and obsessive-compulsive symptoms, interpersonal sensitization and depression (Tuncer, 2019). There is also a correlation between autonomic disorder and obsessive-compulsive symptoms, depression, anxiety, phobias, paranoid thoughts, psychosis, and interpersonal sensitivities.

Both moms and dads put parenting approaches that include physical or emotional punishment in the same location on the interpersonal cycle: the often-antagonistic quadrant. It is also associated with this parenting style, which is characterized by the belief that mistakes should be severely punished and punished verbally, emotionally, and behaviorally, as well as intense anxiety and hostility (Soygut et al. 2008), as well as the perception that the need for control is in danger (Komurcu & Pekak Soygut, 2017). This belief that mistakes should be severely punished and punished verbally, emotionally, and behaviorally is also associated with this condition. In addition to this, it is connected to antisocial conduct, according to Johnson et al. (2016).

Rejection may be found in civilizations as ancient as they are as contemporary as they are, at any point in one's academic career, in the workplace, in online communities, and in personal relationships. It encompasses all forms of life as well. Because of problems in their interpersonal interactions, we notice that children and young people are often expelled from games and organizations, respectively. There is a substantial majority of individuals who report having encountered some kind of hostility or hostility toward them at some time in their life. According to Williams et al. (2000), being excluded from social activities often results in unpleasant emotional experiences such as anxiety, despair, loneliness, and feelings of isolation.

Because it generates unpleasant emotional experiences such as anxiety, despair, loneliness, helplessness, and isolation, which can be experienced in individuals of all ages and cultures and has a substantial influence on physical health (Williams, 1997), social rejection may also be regarded as a sort of punishment. This is due to the fact that social rejection creates these bad emotional experiences. Rejection sensitivity, on the other hand, is connected to how an individual perceives stress; these are changes that are unique to each person. According to Feinstein and 2020, people who are more sensitive to the feeling of being rejected have a bigger psychological weight as a result of being rejected.

People who suffer from conditions such as depression, social anxiety disorder, or borderline personality disorder are very vulnerable to receiving unfavorable evaluations and being rejected. According to the findings of Gao et al. (2017), having a high sensitivity to rejection was also shown to be strongly and moderately related with depression, various anxiety disorders, as well as loneliness and dysmorphic disorder. People who have a high sensitivity to rejection are more likely to misread and distort the acts of others, which may lead to emotions such as anxiety, according to the Emotionally Cognitive Processing Model (COLAK, GV, KOC, AE, & HOCAOGLU, C. 2021).

People who are very sensitive to the feeling of rejection struggle to form meaningful connections with others and often engage in avoidant actions as a result. They are experiencing a great deal of worry (Celebi, 2016). Because persons with this trait have a tendency to underestimate their need for connection and to repress their unpleasant feelings. Obsessive people, on the other hand, have a propensity to have increased connection demands and a concern with their own unpleasant emotional states. As a direct consequence of this, these individuals are at a higher risk of suffering from anxiety (Ilhan, 2018).

It is natural for a person to have a higher anticipation of being rejected when their emotional needs are not satisfied by the people for whom they are intended. According to Ilhan (2018), anxiety might be caused by an incorrect impression of rejection. People who have a high sensitivity to rejection and who have been rejected in past social circles tend to respond defensively whenever they face a possible rejection sign. These people have a history of being rejected. According to Bozkus and Araz (2015), those who are more anxious about being rejected are more likely to interpret acts that are neutral or positive as a response to being rejected.

The experiences that people had in their previous life come to the forefront, particularly those ones that were family-oriented. According to Ilhan (2018), the foundations of misplaced expectations, fears, and ideas of persons who are very sensitive to rejection may be traced back to their infancy.

According to the findings of a study that was published in 1994 by Downey and Feldman, people's propensity to overreact is increased when they worry that the people to whom they assign meaning would reject them. These maladaptive attitudes were linked with "simple anxiety" by Horney (1937). According to him, anxiety is a painful sensitivity that might arise, however minimally, in circumstances such as rescheduling an appointment, not obtaining an instant answer, or being held waiting (Horney, 1937). He also believes that this anxiety is a result of being kept waiting.

Studies evaluating the sense of parental acceptance-rejection and psychological health have been carried out in Turkey (Isik, 2010; Saritas, 2007; Near, 2011), and these studies are included in the research that has been compiled. Saritas (2007) revealed that psychological distress, depression, eating disorders, anger, and anxiety symptoms were connected with mother acceptance or rejection of a sample of Turkish teenagers (Walsh et al., 2017). This was discovered among Turkish adolescents. According to the findings of a research carried out by Near (2011), feeling rejected by one's parents is a strong predictor of exhibiting symptoms of anxiety, anger, and sadness. However, in research that was carried out by Ihle et al. (2005), a connection was identified between depressive illnesses, anxiety disorders, eating disorders, and the way in which parents are seen to be parenting their children. Examining the information gathered from 707 college students in the research that was carried out in Germany allowed the researchers to calculate the prevalence of the ailment.

According to Ayduk, Downey, and Feldman (2000), individuals who have a high rejection sensitivity are more likely to exhibit violent and hostile behaviors than other people (Ince, 2021). This makes them more susceptible to developing anxiety and depression. To put it another way, persons who go into their social connections with the mindset that they will be rejected are often more combative and antagonistic than others. According to Sertoç (2018), this renders people more predisposed to feelings of worry and despair.

It demonstrates that Turkish parenting is centered on submission and reliance, and that this type of parenting is related with authoritarian views at this point. When assessed for rejection sensitivity in terms of anxiety and anger, democratic parenting attitudes are shown to have a positive connection with rejection sensitivity. The link between democratic attitudes and rejection sensitivity is positive. According to the findings of the study, in general, it can be observed that the socioeconomic position of children has an influence on the anger and anxiety components of rejection sensitivity (Sertoç, 2018). These findings were acquired from the findings of the research.

Director and Cakici (2012) investigated the link between the acceptance or rejection of an adolescent by his or her parents and teenage symptoms of sadness, anxiety, aggressiveness, tiredness, and a poor image of oneself. There was a total of 322 females and 170 males in the 10th and 11th grades that took part in the study. Acceptance and rejection of the child by the parent; control scale from the parent; short

The symptom inventory, which was developed by Sahin et al. in 2002, was used as the research instrument for this study. It was shown that the individuals generally had a positive

perception of their parents' willingness to welcome them. A tenuous link was discovered between feeling rejected by one's parents and exhibiting symptoms of mental health conditions such as depression, somatization, anxiety, anger, and a poor opinion of oneself. It was discovered that the levels of depressive symptoms, somatization, anxiety, negative self-perception, and aggressive behavior rose in correlation with the mother's score on the cognitive control scale.

The impacts of rejection may linger for a long time and manifest themselves in different ways at different stages of development. According to Rising and Rohner's research from 2020, one of the most prevalent symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder is anxiety brought on by a feeling of being rejected.

The psychodynamic school of thought proposes that anxiety may be traced back to a lack of meaningful experiences or a broken relationship with a significant other. Those who suffer from social anxiety, on the other hand, have a persistent fear that they will be humiliated or ignored in social settings. (2011) According to Karamustafalioglu and Yumrukcal.

According to Rohner and Britner (2002), the rejection of parental approval, which is a component of the events that take place throughout childhood, has an effect on the overall development of the person and leads to psychopathology. Another research that focused on the association between general mental health and parental acceptance or rejection found that parental rejection impairs individual psychological adjustment (Bouma, Omer, Verfurst, and Olde Hinkel, 2008). This finding is similar to what was found in the first study.

A person who suffers from detached anxiety, which is a kind of neurotic anxiety, is said to be always tense and uncomfortable throughout their lives, as suggested by Freud. Anxiety disorders cause people to become too sensitive in their interpersonal interactions with others, to have feelings of inadequacy, and to be more prone to melancholy. According to Gectan (1995), when a person is rejected or abandoned for any reason, for two reasons: (1) because he cannot express his anger due to feelings of guilt and helplessness, and (2) to alleviate the anxiety of being separated from the person he loves, he maintains his relationship with that person symbolically by appropriating this person as himself, he maintains his relationship with that person symbolically by appropriating this person as himself.

In conclusion, it has been shown that the actions of a person's parents during their childhood may have a significant impact on how that person's sense of identity develops in the years to come. These behaviors include warmth, caring, and ultimately acceptance. According to Armagan (2019), psychological discomfort, sadness, anxiety, drug use, and future suicidal thoughts and

attempts are all factors that might be mitigated by the absence of parental acceptance throughout a child's formative years. In addition, there were found to be positive and significant correlations between perceived parental rejection, rejection sensitivity, difficulties in emotion regulation, and psychiatric symptoms, and it is known that the findings are mainly comparable to what has been discovered in the literature (Ince, 2020). As a consequence of this, the approach taken by parents is of the utmost significance for the experience of infancy. It is possible to claim that the rejection of one's family, as well as attitudes held in one's relationships with school and friends, can prepare the way for the development of anxiety.

5.1.5. Stress

According to Cakir, Celik, Cirak, and Kaykac (2008), stress may be defined as the mental, physiological, and spiritual difficulties that put psychological and physical strain on living things, restrict them, and occur in response to events. According to Kocyigit (2019), in the 17th century, people thought about stress in terms such as calamity, sorrow, sadness, anguish, and pain. When the available research on the topic of stress is scrutinized, a variety of perspectives and interpretations of the term are found. Stress, as defined by Lazarus and Folkmann (1984), is an unpleasant feeling that develops in response to external forces that are beyond the individual's ability to control. (Lazarus and Folkman, 1984). (Lazarus and Folkman, 1984).

According to Cohen, Kamarck, and Mermelstein (1994), the term "perceived stress" refers to the way an individual views an experience as stressful. One of the most significant elements that might influence human existence is stress. According to Afat (2018), it is a stimulant, and the cognitive levels it produces and one's capacity to deal with stress may vary greatly from person to person. The amount of stress that a person believes they are under as a result of the things that have happened to them is referred to as their perceived stress. According to Asici and Uygur (2017), a person's degree of perceived stress increases in direct proportion to the pessimism with which they see a certain occurrence.

It has been shown to what degree stress reactions, which may occur for a variety of different causes, can pose a hazard to the organism both immediately and over the course of time. The ways in which we react to stress set the stage for the gradual onset of degenerative conditions over an extended period of time. Time may be shortened depending on the frequency and severity of shocks. These illnesses might be physical ailments such as headaches, high blood pressure, and

heart disorders, or they can be psychological or mental diseases (Baltas, 1990). Headaches, high blood pressure, and heart problems are examples of physical diseases.

In the notion of stress, feelings are referred to as "environment and person" feelings. It is described as experiences that result from different kinds of underemotional interactions that are directed toward harmony and how those relationships interact with the environment (in terms of stimuli) and individuals (in terms of needs, motives, and psychological qualities). According to Baltas (1990), the type and quality of a person's emotional reactions reflect how that individual evaluates the interactions (efforts of adaptation) between people and their environment.

For instance, the atmosphere of the home, how children are raised, the dynamics of the family, the viewpoints of the parents, and the ideas and attitudes of adults about events (Baltas, 1990).

According to research, male and female reactions to stress are noticeably different from one another, and these distinctions seem to grow more evident throughout infancy. It was stated in a London newspaper that was published in 1978 that males respond more favorably than girls when they experience different stressors, and that girls are more prone to display worry and despair when they encounter stress (Baltas, 1990). This finding was confirmed by research that was published in 1990.

Therefore, under some circumstances, not having a need satisfied might also entail experiencing emotions of dissatisfaction and melancholy. The mind is permanently altered as a result of all of these frustrations and concerns. These are what are known as "early experiences," and according to Baltas (1990), they are what shape a person's worldview in the future.

The kid sees the mother as an accepting or interested role model and recreates this role model by copying it in his own ego in order to cultivate independence and self-confidence. This is done by adopting the mother as a role model. The more the mother is able to comprehend the kid's requirements and gratify the adolescent's desires, the greater the likelihood that the developing youngster will be self-indulgent. But internal strife may develop in a kid if the parents choose to deny, postpone, or disregard enjoyment. Nevertheless, the dread of being rejected is one of the negative effects that stress may have on our physical health. In addition, feeling rejected by society, family, or friends is another factor that might spark rage (Baltas, 1990).

Statements that are critical, harsh, and too generalized about the individual and his life; this has an effect on people's emotions by keeping them engaged when they are put in stressful circumstances (Guner, 2014).

Research that looked at the association between attachment dimension, schema domain, and psychological stress indicated that areas of disconnection and violated boundaries partly mediated the relationship between avoidant attachment and psychological stress (Bosmans, Braet, & Vlierberghe, 2010). These findings were discovered in research that examined the relationship between attachment dimension, schema domain, and psychological stress.

People who have a high rejection sensitivity have been proven to be at risk in the setting of interpersonal and personal stress, as stated in the research conducted by Ayduk et al. (2000) about strategic self-regulation in response to rejection sensitivities.

According to Gadassi et al. (2014), it is linked to maladaptive reactions to stresses in interpersonal interactions, including rejection, among those who have borderline personality disorder or avoidant personality disorder.

Stressors, dependent stressors (behavior and emotions), and independent stressors (producing stress beyond the person's control) were the focus of another research that looked at the impact of stressors on rejection sensitivity (Liu et al. 2014). In this study, stressors included conduct and emotions. It has been shown that dependent stress variables also play a role in mediating the relationship between rejection sensitivity and depressive symptoms (Liu et al. 2014). Finally, those who have a high sensitivity to rejection speak more about dependent stressors than independent stressors.

The way an individual processes and adapts to stress is directly related to their level of sensitivity to rejection. According to Feinstein and 2020, people who are more sensitive to the feeling of being rejected have a bigger psychological weight as a result of being rejected. On the other hand, the production of the stress hormone cortisol is caused when an individual experiences social rejection or the perceived danger of rejection. It results in an increase in the production of cytokines that promote inflammation. According to DeWall and Bushman (2011), this circumstance may have an impact on progesterone, a hormone that is known to be impacted by shifts in mood, and therefore create stress.

According to Poggi et al. (2019), certain mental diseases, such as social phobia, avoidant personality disorder, and borderline personality disorder, are characterized by rejection sensitivity and severe stress in the face of rejection.

Everyone who is excluded or rejected will have reflex responses, which are involuntary reactions that take place independently of the personal or environmental circumstances involved. That is to say, neither the person nor the environmental factors have a role in determining the kind or intensity of these responses. According to Williams, Forgas, and Hoppel (2005), some of the initial responses to being excluded include forms of psychological suffering such as physical pain, physiological agitation, bad emotions, tension, grief, and wrath.

Adulthood is impacted by how a child feels they were accepted or rejected by their parents. According to Kokdemir (2016), certain children and adults are better able to withstand the effects of stress and are less affected by being rejected.

One of the most significant risk factors for experiencing rejection in adulthood is having experienced rejection throughout childhood and adolescence. On the other hand, it's possible that rejection from parents and peers isn't the primary element leading to rejection-prone qualities. Not just the feeling of being rejected, but also the

According to Ilhan (2018), a multidimensional model of the etiological rejection process that takes into account additional variables including genetic predisposition and chronic stresses is being investigated. In addition, according to the APA (2000), borderline personality disorder is a kind of mental illness that is characterized by instability in interpersonal relationships, self-image, and excessive impulsivity. According to Ilhan (2018), those who have this diagnosis are hypersensitive to the effects of interpersonal tension.

According to Kalek and Lohner (2001), those who have experienced rejection are less emotionally stable and have a lower tolerance for stress.

Research conducted by Rohner, Khaleque, and Cournoyer (2012) found that children who experience parental rejection exhibit less emotional behavior and have a lower tolerance for stress and frustration than children who are accepted. For instance, when they are confronted with relatively little challenges in their day-to-day lives, they experience a loss of pleasure, get furious, and worry. They may have feelings of depression and frowning if they respond in a passive-aggressive manner. If they do not take it into account, they are more likely to lose their temper, get irritated, and be unable to deal with stress in a level-headed manner (Rohner, 1999).

When persons who are sensitive to rejection go through the experience of being rejected, the researchers Maggios, Downey, and Shoda (2000) found that these individuals went through high stress, threats, and negative excitement. Furthermore, these individuals were more prone to depression and had lower levels of personal effectiveness and self-esteem.

Sensitivity to rejection, in particular borderline personality features, borderline personality disorder (Ayduk et al., 2008; Berenson et al., 2016; Staebler, Helbing, Rosenbach & Renneberg, 2011), and depression (Ayduk, Downey & Kim, 2001; Beeson, Brittain & Vaillancourt, 2020). 2006; Harper, Dixon, and Wales. *The Cranes and the Wells*, 2017. (2008), Mersin. 2017 according to Normansell and Wisco. Zimmer Genbeck, Nesdale, Webb, Clerk, and Downey, 2016) ... However, rejection sensitivity is linked to social anxiety (McDonald et al., 2010; Bintas-Zorer, 2015), post-traumatic stress disorder (Wang & Chung, 2020), and hostile self-perception (Breines & Ayduk, 2015), according to a number of research (McDonald et al., 2010; Bintas-Zorer, 2015).

Individuals with high attachment anxiety live in constant fear of being rejected or abandoned by others and are vulnerable to attachment hyperactivity. The goal of this therapy is to reduce the amount of stress and possible dangers that these individuals experience in their relationships. According to Hudson and Fraley (2017), exerting effort that is wasted might lead to the maintenance of negative sentiments and beliefs. Lyon, Clark, Rock, and Murray in 2020, according to Clark.

In conclusion, if he is rejected as a youngster and if he is unable to deal with the post-traumatic stress that results from this, he will suffer from a lack of self-confidence, which will cause him to experience negative repercussions such as unhappiness, a lack of self-confidence, and a lack of compassion as an adult. It's possible that he'll have a personality that's extremely sensitive to the stimuli of the outer world, shy, and lacking in confidence.

5.1.6. Threats of Being Turned Down

Abuse of children, neglect of children, conditional parental love for children, inconsistent behaviors, excessive dominance, and cold, harsh, inflexible attitudes may all be connected with rejection within the framework and run the danger of being rejected themselves. Specifically, danger is increased when parents engage in manipulative activities such as controlling, restricting, intimidating, or manufacturing guilt in their children. In addition, communication problems within the family, reproductive problems between parents, and parental psychopathology can lead to

violent behavior and depression by negatively affecting parent-child relationships. This is especially true when it comes to the use of alcohol and drugs by the parent, which is why it is considered a risk factor (Godleski et al., 2019).

There are a number of factors that contribute to the development of an anxious rejection expectation in adolescence, including maternal sadness during infancy, the mother's dominating attitudes, and severe and demanding attitudes during the play period. Maternal rigidity in childhood and family difficulties in primary school Children who grow up with moms who are very controlling tend to have higher expectations about their ability to get angry as adolescents. To put it another way, there are worries about the control that mothers have over their young children. (Godleski et al., 2019) discovered that parental control in primary school was linked with anger, while anxiety was connected with rejection sensitivity. Both of these associations were shown to be significant. According to Ozen and Guneri (2018), early experiences of bullying, which may be seen as a kind of peer rejection, may predispose children to acquire rejection sensitivity at a later time in life.

When demographic factors were used to conduct an investigation of rejection sensitivity, it was unable to arrive at consistent findings according to gender. Erozkhan (2004) Contrary to this information on the rejection of women, Ibrahim et al. (2015) discovered that although the predisposition scores were higher for women than for men, there was no significant difference between the genders despite the fact that the predisposition scores were higher for women. According to the findings of another research (Saricam, 2011), males are more emotionally vulnerable in the face of rejection than women are. It has been shown that having parents with a poor degree of education makes an individual more sensitive to being rejected (Saricam, 2011).

5.2. Mental Disorders

The early identification of parental rejection as a risk factor for the subsequent development of depressive symptoms in adolescence and adulthood is supported by research. (Erozkhan, 2004; Rohner & Britner, 2002) Research has shown that dads have a particularly significant role in the onset of depression in their children. It has been established that individuals who dread rejection but have also experienced it and those who fear rejection but have never experienced it are at a greater risk of having depressive symptoms in the future than those who do not fear rejection but have experienced it. individuals who fear rejection but have never experienced it are at an even higher risk. Negative views might be the result of anxious anticipation over the possibility of being

rejected. (Normansell & Wisco, 2017) research has shown that there is a link, both cross-sectional and longitudinal, between rejection anxiety and depression.

The likelihood of recovery from depression may be affected by the existence of rejection sensitivity. Depression has repercussions not just for the depressed person but also for others around them; it also causes shifts in perception and causes negative intermediate beliefs to predominate in everyday life. According to Weinstein et al. (2016), the presence of a rejection propensity in patients diagnosed with major depression is a finding that is likely to predict subsequent depressive episodes that are more frequent, more severe, and longer in duration. The prevalence of rejection sensitivity has been shown to be connected with higher depressive episodes in those who suffer from bipolar mood disorder. There was no evidence of a connection between the manic phases. In patients suffering from bipolar or unipolar depression, rejection sensitivity is often connected with somatic discomfort. (Weinstein and colleagues, 2016).

It is considered that persons who have Internet gaming disorder also have a high sensitivity to rejection, and it is believed that people who have a high sensitivity to rejection might utilize the Internet to escape the possibility of being rejected in real-life interactions (Weinstein et al., 2016).

Early parental rejection is strongly linked to substance abuse and behavioral problems, despite factors like as age, gender, and the presence of conflict in the home. This is the case even after controlling for other factors. According to research conducted by Rohner and Britner in 2002, it has been shown that unfavorable views held by fathers are a more significant factor in the development of these diseases.

Sensitivity to rejection and extreme stress in the face of the prospect of rejection are characteristics of a number of mental illnesses, including avoidant personality disorder, social phobia, and borderline personality disorder, amongst others. According to research done by Poggi et al. (2019), having a high sensitivity to rejection is a factor that leads to behavioral disorders, particularly in teenagers who have issues with their personality organization. According to the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-5), which is one of the diagnostic criteria for borderline personality disorder, there is a significant association between abandonment avoidance and sensitivity to rejection (Poggi et al., 2019). Another diagnostic criterion for borderline personality disorder is hypersensitivity to rejection.

There is a persistent urge to regulate the other person's proximity (intimacy) in people who suffer from borderline personality disorder, which may emerge as a consequence of a parent's incapacity to satisfy the child's demands or the child's internalization of the parent's soothing

features. Abandonment and rejection are worries for these individuals because they rapidly feel social rejection and have the potential to become maladaptive by demonstrating maladaptive actions in response to the perception of risk. According to Kutlu (2018), borderline personality disorder is characterized by a rise in aggressive conduct with the development of impulsivity and an accompanying fear of being rejected. According to Poggi et al.'s 2019 research, one of the potential risk factors for the development of borderline personality disorder is a heightened sensitivity to rejection. It has been noticed that violent and aggressive behavior is typical of the responses that narcissists provide to others when they are trusted with their sexual wants. Because the narcissist does not have a stable, accepting, and well-balanced environment outside of themselves, which is a factor in the etiology of parental rejection. (Poggi and colleagues, 2019).

5.2.1. Disorders of Social Anxiety (also known as SPD)

When it comes to the facts and ideas linked with the notion of social anxiety, there seems to be some level of ambiguity, according to a survey of relevant publications and research. In many different types of writing, the terms "social phobia" and "social anxiety disorder" are used interchangeably with the term "social anxiety," and the distinction between the two is seldom discussed. Because of this, there is a great deal of uncertainty about the circumstances under which social anxiety is regarded normal and the circumstances under which it is deemed pathological (Kalkan, 2008). The condition known as "social anxiety disorder," which is a subtype of psychopathology, may develop into "social phobia" if the appropriate preventative measures against social anxiety are not done (Bayramukaya, Toros, & Ozge, 2005). The condition known as "social anxiety" has been the subject of research published in the academic literature. According to research conducted by Leary and Kowalski (1997), despite the fact that the ideas of social anxiety and social phobia are heavily linked, there is still one key distinction between the two.

Even though social anxiety is a topic that has been acknowledged and stressed throughout history, Marks and Gelder (1966) were the first people to define the description of BPD that we are familiar with today. Marks and Gelder (1966) characterized SPD as an extreme anxiety around the prospect of performing in front of other people. Concerning the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM) and BPD. In 1980, the American Psychiatric Association was the organization that first established it as a diagnostic notion. Following the release of the third edition of the DSM, the diagnostic criteria for SPD were updated and included into the most recent version of the DSM-V guideline, which was printed in 2013 (Seyitoglu,2018).

The 'cognition' (automatic thinking) that underlies social anxiety disorder and social phobia is the focus of Beck's cognitive model (Turkcapar, 2009). According to Allen and Rapee (2005), when children are subjected to ambient and internal stimuli, such stimuli are continually regarded as a threat, have an effect on their cognition, and lead them to feel scared and anxious.

An estimated 6.7% to 12% of people suffer from social anxiety disorder (Caballo, Salazar, Iruiria & Hoffmann, 2012; Gonzalez-Diez, Calvete, Riskind & Orue, 2015). This makes social anxiety disorder one of the most prevalent forms of anxiety.

Fear of being poorly appraised by others in social circumstances is at the root of borderline personality disorder (BPD). The individual is concerned that others will see them as feeble, frightening, insane, foolish, uninteresting, or cheesy. Fear of behaving in a manner that is humiliating or embarrassing, such as stuttering or sweating; revealing indications of worry, such as flushing, trembling, or heart palpitations; or being judged poorly by other people. According to Heimberg (2014), those who suffer from BPD have a significant fear of being humiliated and ashamed, being rejected, and causing damage to other people.

People who suffer from social anxiety tend to be reserved, introverted, and antisocial. They also tend to avoid making regular eye contact and talk little. They don't say much until they're asked questions, and they don't appreciate being the focus of attention for any length of time. They hardly ever talk in public and congratulate one another in a very modest manner. According to Mansell-Clarck (1999), p. 422, fear or avoidance behaviors play a significant role in their everyday lives. According to Nezelek (1999, page 796), one of the impacts that might cause anxiety is the fear of being rejected or of not being accepted, which is one of the primary anxieties that individuals who suffer from social anxiety have.

People who suffer with social anxiety often experience the dread of performing in public, as well as eating, conversing, and attending meetings. These individuals are furthermore concerned that others will grasp their concerns and mock them as a result. They are also very sensitive to criticism and being turned down (Friedland-Keinan, 1999, p. 91).

The majority of people who suffer from social anxiety do so largely as a result of a collection of beliefs that come about as a direct result of the relationship and interaction dynamics that they experience throughout their lives. This is a belief that comes along with rejection sensitivity. For instance, "If I say no to someone or get angry, I will be rejected" or "If someone

does not openly show that they love me, I will be rejected." Both of these statements are examples of the concept. Accepted – "I was rejected – and I am worthless" (Mellings Adren, 2000, page 246). The symptoms of social anxiety include the fear of being humiliated, of being disliked, undesirable, detested, or rejected by others; these are all examples of negative circumstances. This involves being sensitive to the expectations that others have of you, having the ability to say no, and being critical of yourself (Segrin, 1999, page 15).

According to Liebowitz et al.'s research (2000, page 185), one of the key characteristics of social anxiety disorder is an extreme sensitivity to being rejected in social situations. A persistent fear of being embarrassed in social interactions and performance settings is one of the defining characteristics of social anxiety disorder, which is sometimes referred to as social phobia. Defining the sensitivity to interpersonal rejection Controlling interpersonal connections, fear of rejection, misinterpreting the actions of others, feelings of inadequacy, hazardous behavior, and avoiding interpersonal settings are all components of social anxiety. According to Erozkan (2007), the overlap between social anxiety disorder and rejection sensitivity is made obvious by the parallels between the two conditions.

In addition, persons who suffer from social anxiety have a heightened sensitivity to the negative effects of social rejection, which is comprised of three distinct components. Anxious behavior, poor self-esteem, and conditions related to social phobia and addiction. In the context of interpersonal interactions, it is well established that submissive or nervous behaviors as well as unfavorable judgments of persons (inferiority complex) play a very significant part in the development of social rejection sensitivity. worrying about how others will affect them in the present time, being reluctant to communicate what they believe out of fear of being rejected, not understanding the emotions of other people or assuming that other people would not understand them (Erozkan, 2007).

Many different hypotheses and models have been proposed to explain social anxiety. According to research that was conducted by Rheingold, Herbert, and Franklin (2003), the field of social anxiety literature reveals that cognitive-behavioral techniques play an important part in both the explanation of social anxiety and its treatment. (1) If a person who suffers from social phobia goes into a setting like that, they run the danger of acting in a way that is insufficient and unsatisfactory. (2) Rejection, a loss of worth, and a damaged social reputation are the results of engaging in these actions. They anticipate a catastrophic resolution to the situation. When a xenophobic individual sees a danger of this kind, they experience anxiety, which manifests itself both physically and behaviorally. Because the uncomfortable bodily symptoms that emerge and

the fear of social unfavorable judgment are accentuated, it is possible that important social signals may be missed (Tezcan, 2015).

According to a number of studies, individuals who suffer from social anxiety see their parents as more protective (Bruch & Heimberg, 1994), more rejecting, and less emotionally supportive when they were children (Bogels et al., 2001). According to the findings of a research that was conducted by Lieb et al. (2000), the overprotective and rejecting attitudes of parents were connected with increasing levels of social phobia in children.

According to Seyitoglu (2018), borderline personality disorder (BPD) is such a severe condition that it interferes with the functioning of many significant aspects of a person's life. According to research published in 2007 by Erozkan, there is a considerable connection between social anxiety and the sensitivity to rejection.

However, a unique early maladaptive schema has been found as being connected with social anxiety disorder by a number of different research. According to the findings of these research, schema domains such as discrimination/rejection, restricted autonomy, and xenophobia are linked to social anxiety (Calvete et al. 2013).

An early maladaptive schema is a sign that an individual's needs are not being met. It is made up of childhood memories, feelings, and physiological sensations that arise as a consequence of life experiences such as abuse, as well as a significant failure to satisfy fundamental needs such as constant and secure attachment, abandonment, neglect, or rejection. Emotional and cognitive processes that are self-defeating that begin to emerge in early childhood and continue to be repeated throughout life are called schemas. Young, Croasco, and Weishaal (2003), as well as Raffaelli, Bernstein, and Young (2011), found that.

5.2.2. The acronym OCD stands for obsessive-compulsive disorder.

One of the most prevalent anxiety illnesses that leads to a discernible decline in an individual's level of functioning is obsessive-compulsive disorder, sometimes known as OCD. According to cognitive theories of OCD symptoms, an essential role is played by the amplification of involuntarily intrusive thoughts that arise from dysfunctional beliefs, as well as the interpretation and meaning of these thoughts. It is generally accepted (Uncuer, 2014) that the establishment of dysfunctional beliefs is influenced by developmental variables such as patterns of parental attachment and the attitudes of the parents themselves.

They also discovered that persons with OCD have an extreme dread of being rejected and abandoned by significant others in their life. This was another finding of their research. According to Meares (2001), people with OCD who are sensitive to the effects of separation and individuation may be more likely to identify potential threats to their attachment requirements as a cause of their symptoms.

As a clinical illustration of the association between parental attitudes and obsessive-compulsive disorder, researchers studying the scale data revealed inconsistent findings. This was owing to the quantity of participants as well as the scale that was utilized. According to research conducted by Cavedo and Parker (1994) and published in Alonso et al. (2004), those who have been diagnosed with OCD are more likely to feel that their family are uncaring, overprotective, and emotionally cold than those in the control group.

In their study, Rohner and Britner (2002) focused largely on the association between parental acceptance-rejection and psychiatric symptoms. They found that, as a result of childhood experiences, parental acceptance-rejection has an effect on general individual development and attracts psychopathologies. Another research that looked at the connection between mental health and parental acceptance or rejection reached a similar conclusion: "Parental rejection has been shown to affect individual psychological adjustment" (Bouma, Ormel, Verhulst, and Oldehinkel, 2008).

Numerous research has shown that a correlation exists between the attitudes of parents and psychopathology. A person places themselves in a psychopathologically precarious situation when they spend their formative years in a dysfunctional or disconnected home. On the other hand, it is not entirely obvious whether parent is responsible for the greater portion of the issue (Ince, 2020). According to Alonso et al. 2004, when looking at the common psychopathology, it can be found that being rejected by one's parents is connected with having obsessive compulsive disorder.

Therefore, it is necessary to conduct research on a wide scale that are capable of explaining the interplay of factors on numerous levels (Uncuer, 2014).

5.2.3. Disturbances of eating

Eating behavior is thought of as a complicated phenomenon that results from the control of a person's physical, cognitive, social, and emotional development by both internal and external variables. In addition to this, it plays a part in the establishment of all social ties, including the

bond between a mother and her newborn child that begins at birth. According to Saygili (1999), eating habit is connected to a variety of both pleasurable and unpleasant events.

Eating disorders and behaviors that are not compatible with one other include clinical perfectionism, poor ego respect, eating to your habits focused family attitudes, social comparisons, media influence, and other factors. It is assumed that demographic and individual factors are both included in the list of variables. Particularly in early infancy, parents' opinions towards rejection, functionality, and social skills are well established (Kurtulus, 2019).

According to the research that has been done in the field of psychology, attitudes are described as the tendencies that are imposed on a person and are the source of that person's emotions, ideas, and behaviors (Smith, 1968; Arkonac, 2008). According to this point of view, attitudes are more of an expression of the individual's more general inclinations that provide the foundation for their behaviors than of the individual's more specific actions. Eating attitude may be described as a person's predisposition to form sentiments, attitudes, and actions linked to food and nutrition (Arkonac, 2008). This notion is related to diet, and eating attitude can be characterized as a person's eating habits.

Eating attitudes may also be conceptualized from the viewpoint that they are established as a result of family and societal influences, as well as early childhood education and development. This covers the preferences that individuals have towards the foods that they consume (Shafran & Robinson, 2004). Eating behaviors that are influenced by a person's choices. What you eat, when you eat, how you eat, how much you eat, and with whom you eat are not confined to biological growth or physiological demands; rather, it is a notion that may alter based on psychological and social factors (Shafran & Robinson, 2004). These variables include: what you eat, when you eat, how you eat, how much you eat, and with whom you eat.

Eating disorders are among of the most dangerous illnesses. Statistics show that throughout the last 30 years, 25% of patients who were diagnosed with anorexia passed away, 25% of patients had a similar course of treatment, 40% recovered, and the remaining patients survived with modest symptoms (Maner 2001).

Many studies have indicated that dysfunctional family connections are an essential factor in the genesis of eating disorders, which is significant when taking into account the connection between perceived parenting and eating disorders. They discovered that early family experiences may carry the risk of having ED, and that a negative family history is a crucial etiology. This information was discovered as a consequence of a research that was conducted by Kinzl et al.

(1994). According to a number of studies, those who have an unreliable family history have a considerably increased risk of developing symptoms of ED, in comparison to those individuals who see their family history as being dependable. People with ED were more likely to judge at least one parent as incompetent, according to the findings of a review of 17 research done by Viesel and Allan (2014).

In a separate piece of research, Waller and Hartley (1994) showed that mothers and dads did not significantly vary in their reported views about the process of standard-setting. It has come to light that people have a tendency to hold the stereotype that dads are less accepting than moms. Even among those who did not have an eating disorder, researchers discovered a correlation between unfavorable eating patterns and perceptions of moms as being less normative and dads as being more rejecting. On the other hand, when participants in the ED group regarded their parents to be unsupportive of them, their eating behaviors became more disordered.

It is considered, on the basis of the relevant research, that women who suffer from ED have multiple parenting experiences connected with being rejected or having excessive expectations placed on them. In Lewis's (1986) research on women with ED, the Thematic Perception tests performed to examine the perceived parental attitudes of women's behaviors revealed that women with ED evaluated their dads as being less loving, hostile, and aggressive than normal samples (Yurtsever, 2014). This finding was reported in Yurtsever's (2014) article.

Canetti, Kanyas, Lerer, Latzer, Bachar, 2008. De Pamfilis, Rabbario, Rossi, Gita, Mazzini, 2003. Kutor, 2009. Vardar, 2015; Calam, Waller, Slade, & Newton, 1990; Canetti, Kanyas, Lerer, Latzer, Bachar, 2008. Research that looked at attachment patterns and discovered that they were extremely essential in the development of eating disorders highlighted the fact that unstable and insufficient interactions between parents and children make it more probable that children would acquire ED in the future owing to a lack of communication between the generations. According to Alantar and Maner (2008)'s research, those who suffer from both ED and insecure attachment also have poor levels of self-esteem and have the belief that they are not good enough. It has been discovered that those with a compulsive obsession style exhibit more dysfunctional eating behavior than those with an anxious attachment style (Keskingoz, 2002). Another study found that participants with a negative attachment style exhibited more dysfunctional eating behavior than participants with an anxious and secure attachment style.

In the research carried out by Toker and Hocaoglu (2009), which examined the connection between dietary routines and the composition of families, it was discovered that the participants

scored better on the eating attitude test. This was one of the findings of the study. A total of 38.9% of respondents said that their mothers were overprotective, while 50.0% said that their fathers were overprotective. The individuals in the same research who had a history of trauma in their families had considerably higher mean scores on the eating attitude test than the participants who had not experienced any trauma. In a similar vein, Agirman and Maner (2010) highlighted the fact that painful family situations experienced throughout infancy and adolescence enhance the likelihood of ED, particularly in bulimic patients. According to the findings of Brady's (2008) research, there is a substantial correlation between experiences of physical violence and ED. According to the findings of the research, individuals of either gender who have experienced domestic abuse, in addition to suffering physical violence, have altered eating patterns.

According to Toker and Hocaoglu (2009), persons who have ED have relatives that judge them harshly and find many aspects of their behavior difficult to comprehend. These families are also considered to have high expectations for their loved ones' achievement. Most persons who suffer from eating disorders are moms. It has been mentioned that they are subject to a significant amount of pressure and are under their control. It has also been stated that this circumstance removes their capacity for self-regulation. (Koroglu and others, 2009).

Turner, Rose, and Cooper (2004) investigated the connection between eating disorder symptoms and the ways in which parents see their children and discovered that mothers tend to worry too much and indulge their children too much. They claimed that the symptoms were protective in the sense that they anticipated ED. In addition, eating disorder schemas play a significant role as mediators, and it is vital to highlight the fact that eating disorder schemas about defectiveness/shame and nesting/dependence explain the connection between these models' attachment to their parents and their eating attitudes. The individual may start to believe that they are imperfect and rejected by the individuals who are important to them when their level of parental anxiety lowers. As a result, people' eating attitudes are influenced by parental indifference and overprotection, both of which contribute to the development of ED. According to Turner, Rose, and Cooper (2004), when a mother is overprotective of her kid, the youngster often develops the false belief that he is unable to handle the challenges and obligations that arise in his day-to-day existence.

In a case study examining the treatment of anorexia nervosa using pharmaceutical therapy and psychodrama approaches, the anorexic patient was shown to have been influenced throughout her life by both her family and her physical state. During the course of her psychodrama research, it was uncovered that she placed a significant amount of significance on physical attractiveness

and that her intimate connection with her mother was unable to be developed in a manner that was both healthy and secure (Ozdel et al, 2003).

McEwen and Flouri (2009), who argued that father control behavior is notably associated to ED, explicitly evaluated the relationship between the style of control utilized by dads and ED symptoms to see whether or not there is a connection between the two. There is no correlation between parental behavioral control, such as monitoring, guiding, or disciplining, and the presence of ED symptoms in adolescents. However, it was shown that fathers' psychological control and overprotective attitudes were closely associated to the symptoms of eating disorders in adolescents. It is possible for a father to exert psychological control over his children by, for example, constantly reminding them of the errors they made as children or isolating himself from them when the children engage in behavior that is detrimental. This may have a bad impact on the children's capacity to manage their emotions and contribute to their overall decline. Because of this, it is possible to think that this father's attitude may drive the person to ED and generate detrimental repercussions in itself, and issues in emotion regulation may create problems for the individual in other areas of psychology (Altinel, 2018).

In light of the information presented here, a summary of the relevant research literature supports the conclusion that difficulties in parenting may be risk factors contributing to the genesis of ED. The acceptance or rejection by one's parents, as well as their attention levels, expectations, and emotional response, seem to be highly crucial factors in the development of an eating disorder.

According to Viesel and Allan (2014), one of the elements considered to originate and/or perpetuate eating disorders is a parent's attitude about their child's eating habits. According to Tetley, Moghadam, Dawson, and Lenordson (2014), poor parenting experiences and unfavorable parental perceptions are regularly targeted for the sake of development. According to Haudek, Rorty, and Henker (1999), parental care in the first few years of a child's life is believed to be a risk factor for the development of eating disorders. Parental care includes care, attention, closeness, and love, as well as addressing the needs of the child.

68% of the people in the research were securely connected, whereas 32% of the people were insecurely attached. Individuals who were insecurely attached had considerably higher ratings on physical exertion. The study included 305 females between the ages of nine and twelve. It was shown that one's attachment style is connected with one's level of self-confidence. Individuals who are insecurely attached were found to have lower levels of self-confidence. persons who have insecure attachments are more prone to experience rejection from others, to

have lower levels of self-esteem, and to have greater levels of weight concern, compared to persons who have safe attachments.

In addition, research has shown a correlation between parental rejection and psychopathologies such as clinical depression, drug abuse and addiction, as well as eating disorders. (Heller, 1996; Amato, 1994; Dominy, 1997).

On the other side, Saritas (2007) revealed that the impression of a mother's approval or rejection in a sample of Turkish teenagers was connected with psychological stress as well as depression, eating disorders, hostility, and anxiety symptoms (Walsh et al, 2007). et al, 2017).

Ihle and colleagues (2005) undertook research to evaluate the connection between depressive illnesses, anxiety disorders, eating disorders, and the way in which parents are seen by their children. According to the findings of the survey, 6.9% of people suffer from eating disorders. It has been reported that this percentage is much greater for students who identify as female. It was revealed that maternal control and overprotective attitudes were connected with dietary psychopathology (Kurtulus, 2019). This was discovered when researchers investigated the connection between eating disorders and the rejection of children by their parents.

Jones (2006) did research to evaluate the link between father-daughter relationships and nutritional psychopathology. The work was published in the journal *Nutrition and Psychopathology*. He contrasted 66 women who had been diagnosed with an eating problem to 50 healthy controls as part of his investigation into the link between people's parental attitudes, basic beliefs, and the psychopathology of eating. fundamental beliefs such as abandonment, shame, and hypersensitivity to damage have been demonstrated to have a mediating role in this predictive association (Kurtulus, 2019). Rejection and excessive protection of fathers both predict the psychopathology of eating, and fundamental beliefs such as these also play a role in the predictive relationship.

Parental rejection, obsessive-compulsive disorder (Alonso et al. 2004), anxiety disorders (Cunha & Santo, 2013; Giaouzi & Giovazolias, 2015), eating disorders (Herraiz-Serran et al., 2015), depression, and suicide are all examples of frequent psychopathologies. It was discovered that crime and behavioral difficulties (Simons, Robertson & Downes, 1988. Kim et al., 2003) and drug usage (Azevedo, Simes, Marques, Cunha & Santo, 2013) are associated (Ince, 2020).

According to Harris (2021), avoidance of experience is at the root of a wide range of mental health issues, including anxiety, sadness, addiction to substances, alcoholism, and eating disorders.

The idea of avoiding unpleasant experiences is one that is often discussed, particularly in more recent studies. When searching the literature (Cowdrey and Park, 2012), sleep quality (Waldeck et al., 2020), impaired eating behavior (Fahrkamp et al., 2019), cancer-related pain and stress (Brown et al., 2020), interpersonal problems (Gerhart et al., 2014), experiential avoidance, attachment (Shear, 2010), fear of death (Belsivo, 2010), suicidal ideation (Roush et al.

When the literature is examined, it has been determined that early maladaptive schemas are associated with various psychiatric disorders such as depression, personality disorders and eating disorders (eg, Hinrichsen, Waller & Emanuelli, 2004: 784-787; Joyev & Jackson, 2004: 467-478; Reeves & Taylor, 2007: 96-104; Riso et al., 2006: 515-529). There have only been a few of research that have investigated the link between early maladaptive schemas and social anxiety. Studies have shown that early maladaptive schemas in areas such as separation and exclusion/rejection, autonomy and achievement limitations, and orientation to others play a role in the development and maintenance of social anxiety (Calvete, 2014: 735-746; Calvete, Orue, & Hankin, 2013a: 278-288; Calvete, Orue, & Hankin, 2015: 85-99; Mairret, Boag, & Warburton, 2014: 171-190; Pinto-Gouveia, Castilho, Gallardo, & Cunha, 2006: 571-584), (Zorer, 2015).

The first maladaptive schemas that are going to be covered in this research are one factor that is hypothesized to be created and/or perpetuated by deficiencies in eating attitude. Young (1999) contends that early maladaptive schemas are the source of psychological issues and are responsible for their development. An obviously disordered schema is one risk factor for the development of eating disorders, and it may arise through interactions with parents during the earliest years of a child's existence (Young, 1999; Batur, 2004; Cooper, Todd, & Wells, 1998; Jones, Leung, & Harris, 2007; Leung, Waller, & Thomas, 1999; Leung, Waller, & Thomas, 1999).; Sines, Waller, Meyer, and Wigley (2008)).

However, while looking at the features of individuals who suffered from bulimia neurosis, it was discovered that their families lacked support and understanding. According to Baydemir (1999), it has been hypothesized that children who grow up in such households may acquire a tendency to throw up as an expression of animosity and rejection towards members of their own family. According to Alden and Taylor (2004), individuals who suffer from social appearance anxiety often and profoundly consider the chance that they would be rejected by other people. The presence of this risk makes it harder for these individuals to exhibit sincerity and warmth in their interpersonal connections.

It is possible to say that feeding and eating disorders are brought on by a failure to build key attachment ties throughout the early years of life. One of these conditions is called rumination disorder, and it's been linked to an increased risk of infant rejection and the anticipation of being rejected. The swallowing and re-chewing of partly digested food without substantial feelings of nausea, desires, or indigestion is the defining characteristic of rumination disorder. After three months, it often begins to manifest itself. Children who have intellectual challenges often engage in this activity as a kind of self-stimulating behavior. As the kid continues the act of feeding, it communicates to the mother that it expects proper and constant care as well as pleasure from her. According to Solmus (2010), ruminative disorders lead mothers to be reluctant to eat and engage in avoidance behaviors. This, in turn, raises the baby's level of rejection and the baby's anticipation of being rejected.

Relationships within the family are one of the most prominent factors that might bring to eating disorders. The majority of people who have been diagnosed with BN have poor family ties, according to a review of their family histories. Patients often report that their parents are cold and uncaring toward them.

On the other hand, it has been shown that the presence of excessive emotions of loneliness and rejection have a role in the development of psychopathological eating attitudes. Studies have indicated a link between eating psychopathology and loneliness, which is very similar to the association between abandonment schema and loneliness and perceived father rejection. However, the results of this research showed that perceived father rejection did not play a mediation function in this relationship. Instead, it was discovered that there was a stronger association between people's experiences of rejection and their dads' perceptions of rejection, and that the perceived father's sense of rejection served as the mediator in the interaction between the rejection sub-dimension (Kurtulus, 2019).

According to Toker and Hocaoglu (2009), the most essential factors that determine how well a family functions are its communication patterns inside the family, its structure, its ties with one another, and the ways in which its members interact with one another. It is hypothesized that feeling rejected by one's parents may have a role in developing unhealthy eating patterns (Cevizci, 2021).

5.2.4. Problems with One's Conduct

Children who have been diagnosed with conduct disorder engage in behaviors such as throwing tantrums, lying, stealing, committing acts of physical violence against people and animals, setting fires, causing damage to property, and engaging in sexual activity against their will. According to Solmus (2010), it is more prevalent in males and teenagers, affecting 6% to 16% of boys but just 2% to 9% of girls.

From the perspective of the attachment process, behavioral abnormalities in relationships, excessive parental control and rigorous discipline, excessive indifference, neglect, insufficient or inconsistent care for children, physical or sexual abuse, growing up in crowded family environments, and orphanages are all factors that might negatively affect a child's ability to form healthy attachments. One may say that these factors are what first led to the development of the condition. According to Solmus (2010), one of the most crucial diagnostic criteria for reactive attachment disorder is the presence of aggressive behavior against animals. This aggressive conduct is a symptom of the disease.

It has been observed that the perceived rejection by the child's parents leads to disorders such as behavioral disorders, substance use, and depression (Ince,2020). The studies conducted by Khaleque and Rohner (2002) indicate that there is a negative relationship between parental rejection and psychological adjustment. In addition, these researchers found that there is a correlation between the two.

According to Rohner and Britner (2002), depression, behavioral disorders, and drug use in adult studies are problems associated to parental acceptance-rejection (Ince,2020). These issues are not influenced by culture and are independent of it.

Many studies suggest that insecure attachment styles are predictors of anxiety, depressive, and behavioral problems in adults, while secure attachment styles are related with healthy processes (Kesebir, Kavzoglu, & Ustundag, 2011). This is based on an examination of the whole body of research that has been conducted. On the other side, persons who have an insecure attachment style have negative expectations about their interactions with other people, they avoid becoming involved in relationships out of fear of being hurt or rejected, and it has been underlined that they are unable to manage their emotions sufficiently (Waters & Cummings, 2000). In addition, persons who have an insecure attachment style are more likely to adopt coping mechanisms (such as repressing their feelings) when they feel threatened or under stress. This

results in an increase in worry and stress, as well as a propensity to fear abandonment and rejection as a result of the poor traits that they themselves possess (Mikulincer & Shaver, 2007).

CHAPTER 6

MENTAL WOUNDS OF REJECTION

6.1. Emotional Wound

Imagine that you are in a waiting area with two people you have never met before. The ball that was sitting on the table is picked up by one of them, and then they both toss it to the other. The receiver flashes a grin, glances around, and then tosses the ball in your direction. Play the game in accordance with its regulations and pass the ball to the person who will start the game. You should be having fun just by taking part in the activity. Imagine for a moment that you are sharing a second waiting room with two completely unknown people. The ball that was sitting on the table is picked up by one of them, and then they both toss it to the other. The receiver flashes a grin, glances around, and then tosses the ball in your direction. Participating in the game should provide you with excitement, but you should also play it fairly and give the ball to the person who is beginning the game. He doesn't waste any time and tosses the ball to the second player. Nevertheless, the second player gives the ball to the first player to take another shot. At first, he tosses it back in His direction. If you continue to do this, you will be removed from the game. In this particular instance, you, yourself, how do you feel about how you believe it hurts? How would you rate your morale? How would you rate your own self-esteem? 2015 according to Winch.

However, when psychologists researched this seemingly unremarkable behavior, they came to an extremely significant conclusion. This indicates that we humans care more than we gives ourselves credit for. The scenario involving tossing is really a complex psychological experiment. Both of the "aliens" we come across throughout the game share our passion for learning and discovery. Each time, the "subject" gets freed after a few shots despite the fact that he is sitting in the waiting room under the impression that he has been called to participate in an entirely other experiment. Dozens of researches have indicated that persons who were not allowed to participate in a shooting game feel severe discomfort at levels that were predicted (Winch, 2015).

Why do the findings of the study make such an impression? At a baseball game, being shunned by two strangers is a very minor kind of social exclusion when compared to other types

of rejection. We all go through life having experienced some kind of rejection at some point. The level of suffering that they bring about is, in point of fact, what really differentiates them from any and all other types of bad emotions. When participants were asked to assess the intensity of physical pain that they were experiencing, psychologists found that people put emotional pain on the same level as the agony associated with giving birth or receiving treatment for cancer. It has also been noted that other negative experiences that generate internal pain, such as profound disappointment, frustration, and anxiety, are far less intense than emotions of rejection (Winch, 2015). Other bad experiences that induce internal pain include.

Apart from other types of emotional scars, the reason why rejection is so painful is because of our evolutionary background. People are often found in groups. In ancient times, being cut off from a social group or tribe meant losing access to essential resources such as food, shelter, and company. This made it very difficult to live. It was the same as being given a death sentence. Because the repercussions of being excluded are so severe, the human brain has evolved a mechanism that serves as an early warning system, which guards us against the risk of being "excluded." According to Winch (2015), we feel a searing agony inside us whenever we get even the tiniest hint of rejection.

Studies on the brain have demonstrated that regions that are active during rejection are also activated during physical pain, and the results are the same as previously. Before beginning the ball-tossing experiment, the scientists gave some of the participants a pain medication in the form of Tylenol. At the conclusion of the trial, those who had taken painkillers reported experiencing much less discomfort than those who had not. Sadly, the similar impact did not seem to be present for negative feelings such as shame (Winch, 2015).

6.2. Animosity and aggressiveness

Rejection often serves as a catalyst and activator for outbursts of rage and hostility. This will make you want to attack the people around you, particularly those who have turned their backs on you. Despite the fact that it was made abundantly apparent that they did not take part in the game, the participants in the experiments were offered the option to shout at an innocent individual after playing a game of cybermall. It was discovered that those who had been rejected sobbed far more loudly and for much longer than those who had not been rejected. In other investigations, the participants were those who had declined the opportunity to take part. People who were rejected were shown to have a fourfold increased likelihood of engaging in behaviors such as

consuming spicy sauce, drinking drinks with an unpleasant taste, and watching offensive films (Winch, 2015).

Regrettably, the propensity to experience anger in response to being rejected may result in even more severe disorders. A violent reaction has been evoked as a result of repeated experiences of rejection. This aggressive response goes well beyond the realm of loud yelling or consuming spicy sauce. In the event that these psychological processes are not handled, the traumatic experiences may, in a relatively short amount of time, become "contaminated" and result in severe psychological harm. After being rejected, there may be wild occurrences, insane news, lovers who have been abandoned seeking vengeance, employees who have been blinded by dismissals, young people committing suicide as a result of mental violence spreading like an epidemic, and many other events (Winch, 2015).

In love relationships, rejection has a significant influence in the development of violent behavior between the partners. Jealousy, a perception of betrayal that goes hand in hand with emotions of rejection, is the primary motivating factor in the commission of the vast majority of violent crimes. A total of 551 instances of husbands murdering their wives have been investigated by researchers, and their findings indicate that roughly half of all murders were motivated by a fear of ending the relationship. The majority of men who admitted to killing their spouses said that they were unable to shake the sensation that they had been rejected. However, a study of school shootings, which included the shooting at Columbine High School in 1999, revealed that in thirteen of the fifteen instances, the perpetrators suffered extreme rejection in their relationships or were shunned from their friends. This was the case even though the Columbine High School shooting was one of the cases studied. It has also been said that the majority of gun assaults are generally intended towards persons who have a history of rejecting them, using psychological violence against them, or making fun of them (Winch, 2015).

6.3. A Shattered View of Oneself

Rejection on a consistent or frequent basis may have a negative impact on our sense of self-worth and cause a great deal of harm. Simply thinking about the times, we were turned down in the past might permanently damage our feeling of self-worth. This response when we are rejected (really, we give ourselves) is extremely typical; nonetheless, it creates the conditions for the scrapes and cuts of our soul to get "infected" in a short amount of time, which ultimately leads to a decline in our mental health (Winch, 2015).

Every one of us has a propensity to take rejection personally. We look for proof of our shortcomings and deficiencies, and when we uncover even the slightest of them, we try to draw the worst possible conclusions about ourselves as a result. We also turn the act of being rejected into an unnecessary and intimate experience, and we have a penchant of overgeneralizing. Even if there is no evidence to support it (such saying "This happens to me all the time" or "I'll never find someone to love me"), it is still OK to believe it. According to Winch (2015), such actions are one of the negative things that people do to themselves that ultimately end up hurting them.

Because of this, dwelling on the errors you've made won't get us any closer to our objective. On the contrary, it makes the existing agony that we are experiencing much worse. Your already damaged sense of self-worth will be destroyed even more if you needlessly blame yourself for anything. According to Winch (2015), being rejected causes us a significant deal of pain and may open up deep scars.

6.4. Feelings of Compatibility and Belongingness

We are born with a fundamental want for other people's approval, which is one of the factors that makes our sense of self-worth so vulnerable to being hurt by rejection. If we are deprived of our feeling of belonging for an extended period of time, not only will our physical and mental health suffer, but we will also have the sensation of being rejected, and we will be unable to form partnerships based on collaboration. Suffering is caused when an individual's desire of belonging is not met throughout their childhood and adolescence, and they are afterwards subjected to rejection. In addition, consistent rejection has the effect of chipping away at one's sense of self (Winch, 2015).

According to Baumeister and Leary (1995), the desire for a feeling of belonging is present in all cultures and all individuals and may be considered an observable universal need. This is because the need for a sense of belonging is similar to many other psychological needs. On the other hand, rejection poses a risk to the ability to satisfactorily fulfill this demand and has a variety of unfavorable repercussions on people. According to Baumeister and Leary (1995), the desire to belong is an essential one, and when that need is denied, we are expected to adopt acts that would assure social approval by others in order to satisfy the urge to belong once again. According to Solak and Tek Ozel (2019), individuals are sensitive to both positive and negative social

information. Positive social information expresses a feeling of belonging and acceptance, whereas negative social information indicates rejection and exclusion.

According to Solak and Tek Ozel (2019), when individuals have anxieties and uncertainties about their desire for acceptance and a feeling of belonging from other people, it might lead them to terminate relationships or take measures that are beneficial to their wellbeing. According to Thoits (2011), protective factors of self-esteem include a feeling of belonging to the society as well as acceptance by the society. According to Jaremka et al. (2013), social marginalization might cause an increased sensitivity to rejection.

As a consequence of this, each person works hard to fulfill the requirements necessary for them to feel like they belong. On the other hand, having ties to a certain location is just as significant as having independence. One of the most complicated human feelings is a sense of belonging. "The human soul, on the one hand, loves freedom, and, on the other, it seeks branches to hold on to. It feels as safe and secure as it clings to," (2020:1735).

THE NEXT CHAPTER

REASONS FOR BEING REJECTED

7.1. Connecting

There are several theoretical similarities between Bowlby's attachment theory and the rejection sensitivity model. According to Bowlby, experiences that a kid has with a caregiver when they are young

The lack of attention, warmth, compassion, and trust that individuals exhibit in their relationships as they become older has a detrimental impact on the conduct of those people. individuals are said to establish a negative self-image and relationship model relating to the terrible experiences they have had, and then strive to reproduce this same pattern in every new relationship they encounter (Bretherton 1992). This is something that has been said by a number of individuals. On the other hand, the rejection sensitivity model that was established by Downey and Feldman (1996) exhibits parallelism with the internal working models. This model explains how cognitive and emotional processes impact behavior within a particular social setting or within interpersonal interactions. Romero-Canyas and Downey (2005) stated that children develop coding strategies that cause misconceptions in their expectations and perceptions with these cognitive-emotional schemas they form based on their experiences of rejection; therefore, he states that they have a

tendency to have a negative perception of events or relationships in their later years, that ambiguous signs are taken over themselves, and that they begin to expect that they will be rejected. Therefore, anxious anticipation of rejection causes people to be extremely cautious against rejection. As a result, when they are confronted with even the slightest sign of rejection in their interpersonal relationships, they interpret it as an act of purposeful rejection, and feelings of rejection emerge (RomeroCanyas and Downey 2005).

Anxiety level and self-confidence were found to be partial mediating variables in the relationship between anxious attachment styles (preoccupied and fearful attachment) and rejection sensitivity (Khoshkam et al. 2012). This was discovered as a result of a study that was carried out on university students. When the research on the topic is analyzed in this context, the results show that anxiety level is a partial mediating variable. Rejection sensitivity is inversely connected with secure attachment, and pupils whose attachment style is characterized by the greatest anxiety have the most rejection sensitivity, according to the findings of another research that was conducted on a similar topic and published in 2009 (Erozkan). Another study that looked at the relationship between rejection sensitivity and attachment dimensions found that high anxiety (the desire to be in close relationships and the fear of rejection) and high avoidance (the emotional avoidance of close relationships) both increased rejection sensitivity and had a negative effect on the person. According to the results of Ozen et al. (2010), the anxiety and avoidance aspects of attachment have significant influence on an individual's sensitivity to being rejected.

As a consequence of this, he stated that depending on the attachment dimensions, children's cognitive processes, the schemas they formed, and the encodings they perceived, they had a tendency to perceive events or relationships negatively in their later years, and they started to anticipate ambiguous signs to be taken on themselves and to be rejected. He also mentioned that this tendency varied depending on the children's attachment dimensions, cognitive processes, schemas they formed, and encodings they perceived. In addition, it was noticed that the amount of anxiety and self-confidence were varied in the association between anxious attachment styles (preoccupied and frightened attachment) and rejection sensitivity. This was a finding that came as a surprise to the researchers. It has been said that it is detrimental to the individual to avoid being involved in relationships in the future, to have an elevated sensitivity to rejection, to be afraid of rejection, to emotionally avoid situations, and to have a high degree of avoidance.

7.2. Parenthood

It is notable that parental attitudes are an essential element in addition to attachment patterns when considering the influence of childhood rejection experiences on the creation of rejection sensitivity. This is the case when taking into consideration the impact these experiences have on the formation of rejection sensitivity. According to a number of studies (Erozkan 2004, Cardak et al. 2012), those who have a perception of their parents as being authoritarian have a greater level of rejection sensitivity than those individuals who have a perception of their parents as being democratic, indifferent, or protective. This result lends credence to the conclusion (McLachlan et al. 2010, Rowe et al. 2015) that those who acquire a sensitivity to rejection as a result of being exposed to a variety of stressful circumstances, including pressure, criticism, rejection, and disapproval from their parents, are more likely to engage in risky behaviors. In point of fact, according to the findings of a research project carried out by Rudolph and Zimmer Gembeck (2014), rejection and negative parenting behaviors (psychological control, a lack of parental warmth, and pressure) are responsible for the development of rejection sensitivity in children. According to Rudolph and Zimmer-Gembeck (2014), marital strife has a detrimental impact on both parents' views toward their own parents, which in turn has an indirect impact on the development of rejection sensitivity in children.

One may claim that parental views are a contributing factor to the rise in children's sensitivity to being turned down or rejected. It can be demonstrated that maternal attitudes are a significant contributor to children's experiences of feeling rejected in situations including disagreements between their parents, pressure, not being tolerated or accepted, apathy, or chilly conduct on the part of the caregivers. In addition, it has been shown that those who have a perception of their parents as being authoritarian have a greater level of rejection sensitivity compared to individuals who have a perception of their parents as being democratic, indifferent, or protective.

7.3. Psychopathology

The outcomes of research conducted on a variety of psychopathologies provide evidence in favor of the hypothesis that an individual's initial experiences in life provide the foundation for an anticipation of being rejected. According to Feldman and Downey (1994), social rejection sensitivity is one of the key components of both social avoidance (such as social phobia and avoidant personality disorder) and social inclusion (such as dependent personality disorder and

borderline personality disorder). According to studies (Blatt and Zuroff 1992, Parker et al. 1992), people who suffer from dependent personality disorder and social phobia report having more negative interactions with their parents throughout their formative years than those who come from normal groups. On the other hand, the majority of attention in more recent research on the topic seems to be directed on borderline personality disorder and Avoidant Personality Disorder. Behavioral impulsive disorder (BPD) is characterized by a high degree of impulsivity as well as an increased inclination towards inappropriate impulsive acts in the event of perceived rejection (Berenson et al. 2011, Coifman et al. 2012). In addition, BPD comprises a high level of impulsivity. As with Borderline Personality Disorder, it has been shown that Avoidant Personality Disorder is linked to maladaptive reactions (rejection) to stresses in interpersonal interactions (Gadassi et al. 2014). In the same vein, it has been found that Avoidant Personality Disorder is similar to borderline personality disorder. According to the findings of related studies, people who suffer from borderline personality disorder and Avoidant Personality Disorder have a high sensitivity to rejection (Berenson et al. 2011, Stabler et al. 2011). Because of this, they are more likely to have a difficult time maintaining healthy interpersonal relationships (Berenson et al. 2016).

In research on psychopathology, it has been shown that the anticipation of being rejected plays a significant role in the development of conditions such as rejection sensitivity, social avoidance (also known as social phobia), avoidant personality disorder, and dependent personality disorder. On the other hand, social inclusion is associated with conditions such as borderline personality disorder and avoidant personality disorder.

7.4. Relationships of a Romantic Nature

People who have a strong sensitivity to rejection are often plagued with issues in every one of their interpersonal connections. On the other hand, it has been observed that a sensitivity to rejection may result in far more significant issues, particularly in romantic relationships, which place a premium on intimacy and proximity and in which individuals are more vulnerable to the prospect of rejection as a result of powerful emotions. People who are very sensitive to rejection see the insensitive and/or unsure conduct of their partners as an act of willful rejection (Downey and Feldman 1996). As a result, these individuals channel their emotions inside or outward to protect themselves from the possibility of being rejected and/or rejected (Downey and Feldman 1996). According to Creasey and McInnis (2001), people feel uncomfortable and unhappy about their relationships because they turn their emotions inside and outward in their romantic

relationships and have to cope with feelings such as despair, loneliness, rage, jealousy, hostility, and aggressiveness. This causes people to feel insecure and unhappy about their relationships. Because of this, the reactions of individuals who have a high rejection sensitivity to their own experiences of rejection can cause relational problems, particularly in romantic relationships where there is a certain closeness and the possibility of rejection is very high; this may cause individuals to have a tendency to keep themselves away from romantic relationships (Creasey and McInnis 2001).

The hypothesis that people with high rejection sensitivity faced destructive problems in their romantic relationships was found to be mostly supported by the research that was done on the literature examining the relationship between rejection sensitivity and romantic relationships (Downey et al. 2000, Romero-Canyas et al. 2010). This was seen when it was discovered that the literature examining the relationship between rejection sensitivity and romantic relationships was researched. In their research, Downey and colleagues (1998) discovered that even if one of the partners in romantic relationships is rejection sensitive, the likelihood of ending this relationship is much higher than that of couples who do not have rejection sensitivity. They state that these people feel more insecure in their relationships and have less relationship satisfaction than couples who do not have rejection sensitivity. At the same time, the findings of this research indicate that women act more adversely than men do in the presence of a prospective debate setting, and that following the conversation, women have much greater feelings of anger than men do. This data lends credence to the theory that women's personal connections are more closely tied to their sense of self than men's are. As a result, circumstances that jeopardize closeness and togetherness may quickly set off women's heightened sensitivity to being rejected. In a different study conducted by Ayduk et al. (2001), the researchers found that women who were highly sensitive to rejection experienced feelings of rejection and displayed a greater number of depressive symptoms when they were abandoned by their partners. However, the researchers found that these same women did not experience feelings of rejection when they separated themselves or decided to leave the relationship by making a joint decision. As a result, these women did not show tendencies toward depression.

According to Downey et al. (1998), those who are sensitive to rejection, whether male or female, engage in a "self-mutilation strategy" in their romantic relationships. People who have a high sensitivity to rejection are likely to engage in self-silencing behavior, which may be characterized as the suppression of one's own emotions and ideas in love relationships. Regarding the aforementioned notion, there is a significant relationship between rejection sensitivity and

depression, as well as between rejection sensitivity and self-mutilation behavior; it has been observed that the self-silencing strategy is a method that both men and women who have rejection sensitivity generally use in their relationships (Harper et al. 2006). In addition, there is a significant relationship between rejection sensitivity and self-mutilation behavior. There is inconsistency in the findings of studies that investigate whether or not the practice of self-mutilation affects a person's gender. Although some of the studies suggest that males are more likely to engage in the practice of self-silencing (Mellin 2008), other study results suggest that women are more likely to engage in the practice of self-silencing (Hafen et al. 2014).

People who have a low sensitivity to rejection are just as likely as those who have a high sensitivity to have conflict with their partners. However, individuals with a high sensitivity to rejection seem to respond much more strongly to these sentiments (such as screaming, cursing, taunting, and threatening to quit the relationship) after experiencing feelings of rejection. (Ayduk and colleagues 1999). According to the findings of another study on the topic that was carried out by Galliher and Bentley (2010), young people who have a high rejection sensitivity have a perception that their relationships with their romantic partners are more distant and argumentative than they actually are. It is also reported that their romantic partners define their relationships with them as being less warm and power imbalanced. According to the findings of the research, those who are more sensitive to rejection both have a more pessimistic outlook on their own relationships as well as a more hostile demeanor toward the partners in such relationships. According to Galliher and Bentley (2010), the degree to which men's sensitivity to rejection and perceived hostility increases is inversely correlated with the level of relationship pleasure experienced by their women. As a result, the data lend credence to the hypothesis that individuals who have a high rejection sensitivity have a more pessimistic outlook on the quality of the relationships in their lives, and that this pessimism leads to behaviors that contribute to a decline in the quality of those relationships.

In a separate piece of research that was carried out by Volz and Kerig (2010), the authors investigated the link that exists between rejection sensitivity and relational insecurity, relational violence, as well as victimization. An endeavor to maintain a connection, despite the fact that it is developing in a bad direction, is what's meant when we talk of relational insecurity. An endeavor to dominate another person physically, sexually, or mentally in a way that results in damage to either party is what's meant when we talk about relationship aggression. According to the findings of the study, it is said that while relational insecurity is a completely mediator variable between rejection sensitivity and aggressiveness, there is no mediator variable between rejection sensitivity

and being a victim. This is in contrast to the finding that relational insecurity is a fully mediator variable between rejection sensitivity and aggression. In other words, it can be shown that individuals who are rejection sensitive are making an attempt to preserve their connection, and as a direct consequence of this emotion, they are more prone to display violent behavior against their partners. The results are taken as meaning that emotional responses to rejection sensitivity induce aggressiveness rather than being a passive victim in a relationship.

In addition, Downey et al. (2000) note that they created two ways to protect males who are sensitive to rejection from really experiencing the rejection that they are sensitive to. One of the aforementioned techniques is to steer clear of intimate connections and to exercise more caution even when they are in a relationship in order to avoid allowing the other person to harm them; the second strategy, on the other hand, is to actively seek out close relationships and to devote an excessive amount of time and energy in romantic partnerships. Because they expected that men with high rejection sensitivity would overreact to the tiniest or ambiguous symptoms of rejection when they grew too reliant on their relationships, researchers have shown that men who adopt the second kind of technique are more likely to resort to a lot of violence in their relationships. As a consequence of this, men who are very sensitive to rejection and who invest very little in the connection avoid entering into social interactions. On the other hand, research has shown that men who spend an excessive amount in the relationship are more likely to resort to violent behavior. In light of these findings, it is possible to explain why men with rejection sensitivity who invest too much in a relationship (in a relationship with serious commitments and promises) may lead them to more violence if they are only rejected by an important person in their life (Downey et al. 2000). This can be explained by the fact that men with rejection sensitivity are more likely to have relationships with serious commitments and promises.

Romero-Canyas et al. (2010) came to the conclusion that individuals who have a high rejection sensitivity participate in actions to impose themselves after suffering rejection in their romantic relationships. As a consequence of this, individuals with high rejection sensitivity are more likely to engage in these behaviors. People's responses to rejection are connected to the fact that the rejection is severe and the fact that the rejection is viewed as a danger to the settings in which the person defines himself (for example, males are rejected by a group of friends, and women are rejected by a person with whom he has a close connection). It was discovered in the research that was carried out in light of this information that women who have a high rejection sensitivity and who were rejected by their romantic partners exhibited the behavior of forcing themselves only when they perceived their rejection as being harsh. On the other hand, it is stated

that they only feel hostile feelings when they experience rejection from people in whom they have little interest. On the other side, it has been observed that males who are very sensitive to rejection have a tendency to participate in the activity of pushing themselves against any and all forms of rejection.

It has been noticed that persons who have a high sensitivity to rejection display actions that are aggressive, forceful, and even resort to violence in romantic and regular relationships. This has been the case in both types of relationships. Because of these habits, it was also said that there was avoidance and avoidance in their relationships. This came as a direct effect of the behaviors.

7.5. There is a correlation between Attachment Theory and Parental Acceptance-Rejection Theory.

In his essay titled "Similarities and Differences between Attachment Theory and Parental Acceptance-Rejection Theory," Rohner (1999) discussed the similarities and differences between these two theories. He drew attention to the fact that these two theories have significant similarities.

The fact that both of these theories use an evolutionary approach is one of the ways in which they are comparable to one another. First, attachment theory postulated that individuals have a built-in propensity to form permanent emotional ties with important persons who cannot be replaced. Attachment theory asserts that the degree to which children believe that they are secure and protected is directly proportional to their attachment processes, as well as the quality of the connections they have, the frequency and quality of the positive replies they get, and the quality of these reactions. The theory of attachment places a strong emphasis on the significance of this evolutionary process of reciprocity as being adaptive. In a similar vein, the Parental Acceptance-Rejection Theory asserts that individuals have an evolutionary biologically based need for gains to obtain favorable replies from their parents or "significant others," whether consciously or subconsciously. This need for gains to receive positive reactions from their parents or "significant others" is based on the desire to receive gains.

These requirements for favorable reactions include the need for reassurance, care, affection, support, love, and sustenance, amongst other things. According to the EKR hypothesis, people have a tendency to provide particular responses in their life when certain requirements are not satisfied or when those needs are met. There is also the belief that these characteristics are shared by all of mankind since they have their origins in the biology of human beings. This is yet

another commonality. Another widely held belief is that one's early life connections might provide insight into one's subsequent romantic partnerships. The parallels that may be seen between the ideas of "internal working model" and "mental representations" to which they relate. To put it another way, it is explained in both of these theories that the first connections formed with significant others serve as prototypes, and subsequent relationships serve as mental representations of those prototypes. One last thing to consider is that both of these ideas contend that children and adults would put up a fight if they are severed from the important persons in their lives who offer main care to them.

According to Rohner (1999), there are distinguishing characteristics between these two hypotheses. The primary distinction between the two theories is that whereas the attachment theory places primary emphasis on the newborn or kid, the PAR theory places primary emphasis on the characteristics of the parent. The age gap between the groups that were analyzed is still another distinction. In the attachment theory, infants and early childhood are taken into account, but in the PAR theory, adolescents and adults are regarded to be those who have reached school age. Recent research has produced two hypotheses that adopt a viewpoint that spans an individual's whole life, from childhood to old age. Observation is the method used in attachment theory to determine whether or not a certain activity is appropriate. Measurement of parental behaviors, according to the PAR theory, may take the form of surveys or interviews.

Attachment theory describes personality as a combination of secure and insecure attachment types, in contrast to the PAR theory, which defines personality by dimensions.

Rohner (1999), who supports both theories, identifies the following as the two most important fundamental issues: first, it helps the concepts of EKR theory such as dependency, independence, defensive independence, and immature addiction; second, attachment theory informs the PAR theory of the baby's development in the first 18 months. However, the EKR theory, namely the personality theory that is included within it, is not a measurement for infants who are under 18 months old.

As a consequence of this, we can state that when all of the kid's needs are not satisfied in the attachment theory, according to the PAR theory, the child's negative view of not satisfying these requirements regardless of whether or not he is conscious of it, that is, the child's rejection schema perception. This is the case whether or not the child is aware of it.

7.6. Sensitivity to rejection in interpersonal relationships

After birth, humans immediately begin to interact with the community that surrounds them since, as social beings, this is an essential part of their nature. It is mentioned that the kid in connections with caregivers or other relevant individuals is exposed to early, long-term, or acute experiences of rejection. In addition, it is stated that these experiences may be intense. However, these experiences teach youngsters to anticipate being rejected when they are in social settings with people, they are close to. As a result of the fact that people place significance on their relationships, these expectations come with an accompanying load of feeling. Therefore, worried anticipations of being rejected might be considered a distinguishing characteristic of separation. These consequences provide the possibility for a feedback loop that might develop into animosity or sadness, so turning a self-fulfilling prophesy into reality. The development of such a dynamic influences a person's views of and actions in interpersonal relationships throughout their whole lifetime. According to Pietrzak, Downey, and Ayduk's (2005) research, individuals who have a feeling of rejection often respond in an extreme manner when they confront ambiguous behaviors in such interactions and are rejected.

It has been mentioned that persons with high sensitivity are adversely influenced not just in romantic relationships but also in settings where they have the chance of meeting new people (Butler, Doherty, & Potter, 2007). This is the case because high sensitivity makes people more vulnerable to the negative effects of others. According to the findings of a research that was carried out in secondary schools by Downey et al. (1998), children who have high rejection sensitivity are more likely to engage in violent and antisocial behaviors as well as have issues with interpersonal interactions. There are cognitive biases associated with rejection sensitivity, particularly in how one deals with and perceives rejection.

It is less probable that a person will lead a socially healthy existence if they have the mindset that they will always be rejected in the new connections they have created or will establish in the future. A person who is concerned about being rejected has limited options available to them when it comes to meeting new individuals. Studies (Chohan & Naeem, 2019; Caglayaner, 2020; Koster, De Maat, Schreur & Van Aken, 2018) have shown that there is a correlation between the sensitivity one has to the experience of rejection and their level of life satisfaction.

According to the findings of the study, there is a substantial connection between sensitivity to rejection in interpersonal relationships and levels of life happiness. To put it another way, an individual's level of happiness in life may be influenced by their willingness to take things in life

as they come, their ability to remain in the "moment," and to live their lives in accordance with the principles they have embraced. The unfavorable events that might occur in a person's life contribute to a decline in the overall amount of happiness that they experience throughout their lives. lowered levels of life pleasure, protective systems, and support from the environment

According to Demirel and Canet (2004), when a person is lacking in something, they may engage in activities that are harmful to themselves. However, the social life of a person who is unhappy with the way their relationships with their friends and family members are going might also be severely impacted by this circumstance. According to research conducted by Downey and Feldman in 1996, having had previous bad experiences might make it more difficult for a person to have subsequent good experiences because these experiences can activate a person's cyclical pattern of feeling rejected.

In addition, research has shown that there is a considerable inverse association between psychological adaptability and the degree to which an individual is sensitive to rejection in interpersonal relationships. According to Downey and Feldman (1996), those who are very sensitive to rejection have a greater range of emotional and behavioral responses than those who are less sensitive to the impact of rejection. It has been hypothesized that the individual's ability to form healthy interactions with his or her surroundings may be negatively impacted by the individual's emotional and behavioral responses, and that the individual's psychological flexibility may also be a factor in how the separation dimension develops.

According to regression analysis, interpersonal rejection sensitivity, life satisfaction, and psychological flexibility significantly predicted life satisfaction; psychological flexibility also significantly predicted life satisfaction; however, when psychological flexibility was controlled for, the significance of the relationship between interpersonal rejection and life satisfaction decreased. On the other hand, it is possible to assert that psychological adaptability plays a substantial role as a mediator in the connection between rejection in interpersonal relationships and levels of life satisfaction. It has been discovered, via research carried out on persons who have a strong sensitivity to rejection, that their attention is directed toward remembering experiences of being rejected in the past.

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